

ASPECT-ACTIONALITY INTERACTIONS IN ÈDO

By

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To God.

And to my loving family: Greg, Millicent, Chioma, Aisosa, Osadebamwe, Aizenosa,
Efosa, Èfè, Ògiè, Èghe, Osayawe

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

1	1 st Person
2	2nd Person
3	Third Person
PST	Past
PRS	Present
PROSP	Prospective
SG	Singular
PL	Plural
PFV	Perfective
PRT	Perfect
FAC	Factative
IPFV	Imperfective
CPL	Completive

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ASPECT-ACTIONALITY INTERACTION IN ẸDO

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This study addresses two issues in the temporal marking system of the Ẹdo language. The first is to present a unified analysis of temporal markers in the language and the second is to classify verbs based on their interaction with the temporal semantics in the language. Data for the study was obtained from 15 language consultants using a questionnaire that comprised of verbs from different thematic groups. The study found that the disagreements in earlier analyses of temporal markers stem from the variation in temporal semantics as a result of aspect-actionality interactions. Verbs were classified into two broad groups - inchoatives and non-inchoatives following the application of actionality diagnostics designed for the language.

CHAPTER 1 GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

Cross-linguistic descriptions of aspectual systems typically focus on grammatical aspect as opposed to lexical aspect (henceforth actionality). This same bias for grammatical aspect applies to aspectual descriptions of individual languages. This has been attributed to the assumption that the inventory of actional classes is universal (Ebert 1995; Filip 2011; Bar-El 2015). Vendler (1957) has served as the most influential account on which verbs are classified based on lexical aspect. This universalist, aprioristic approach to actional classification has been challenged because of some inadequacies of this classification schema which include its inapplicability to all languages (e.g., its inability to account for inchoative verbs in Bantu languages) and inconsistent results in the application of classification diagnostics across languages (Mourelatos 1978; Binnick 1991; Botne 2003a; Nichols 2010; Crane 2011; Hellwig 2011; Persohn 2018). The inadequacies of this approach have led to the proposal of a parametric (idiosyncratic), non-aprioristic bi-dimensional approach to actional classification (Breu 1984; 1994; Bickel 1997; 2000; Johanson 2000a). While this approach has been adopted in the investigation of aspect-actionality in non-African languages (e.g., Romance, and Eurasian languages) and African languages (specifically Bantu languages), with the exception of Siamou (Toews 2015), there is currently no such study in any non-Bantu Niger-Congo languages. This is both a theoretical and typological gap as the absence of such a study makes it impossible to determine the entire range of actional classes cross-linguistically as well as compare

the actional systems of Bantu languages and non-Bantu Niger-Congo languages - of which Edo is an example.

The existing analyses of temporal marking in Edo by different scholars is anything but uniform. For example Dunn (1968:216) argues that the Edo temporal marking system is an 'intricate one' consisting of two tense markers, three aspectual markers and at least six modals. Omoruyi (1991b: 2) argues that "whereas simple past or completive tense is commonly marked by verbal inflections and tonal changes, aspect and modality are marked by the occurrence of auxiliaries".

The goal of this dissertation is to account for the temporal marking system of Edo by developing a description of the Tense-Aspect system of Edo (an Edoid < Niger-Congo language) that takes into account the interaction between temporal-aspectual inflectional paradigms and the lexical dimension.

1.1 Outline Structure of the Chapter

The remainder of this chapter is structured as follows; section 1.2 is a brief review of relevant literature. In section 1.3, I highlight the research gaps to be filled by the study. Section 1.4 presents and briefly discusses the research aims, objectives and specific questions to be answered by the study. Section 1.5 outlines the methodology used in this study with respect to data collection and data analyses. In section 1.6, I discuss the implications of the results of this study for Edo grammar, aspect-actionality interaction theory and typology. Section 1.7 discusses the methodological and other limitations of the dissertation. The chapter concludes with a summary of each chapter to follow in section 1.8.

1.2 Background to the Study

1.2.1 Key theories and Studies

This section briefly discusses the theoretical framework adopted in this dissertation and studies required to understand the context in which this study will be conducted. It presents the context which motivates the research questions. This discussion will be elaborated in chapter 2 which discusses the details of these theoretical positions as well as the data to support the theories.

1.2.1.1 Previous studies in Edo

The major points of contention in the temporal-aspectual marking literature in Edo can be summed under two headings; the temporal categories that are marked in the system and how these are marked

With respect to temporal marking in Edo, previous studies agree that the temporal system of Edo includes both tense and aspect. However, there is disagreement with respect to the specific tense and aspect categories in the system. With respect to tense, Dunn (1968) claims that Edo makes a distinction between past and non-past while (Emovon 1980) and (Agheyisi 1986a) argue in favor of a present vs past vs future distinction. The aspectual marking system is not spared this disagreement. While Dunn (1968) proposes a perfective vs imperfective vs habitual distinction, Emovon (1980) proposes a perfective vs imperfective vs progressive aspectual system, Omozuwa (2003) argues for a perfective/imperfective dichotomy while Omoregbe (2012) is in favor of a perfective vs imperfective vs habitual vs progressive system.

Regarding the TA markers, there is a lack of agreement in accounting for what marks the past tense, completive, perfective aspect, and imperfective aspect, on one

hand, and what temporal category the low tone on the verb marks, on the other. For Dunn (1968) and Omoregbe (2012), past tense is marked by the high tone ‘ ’ on monosyllabic verbs while Aikhionbare (1986), (Agheyisi 1986b), Omoruyi (1991a), Ogie (2003) and Yuka & Omoregbe (2008; 2011), claim that it is marked by the -rV suffix. With respect to grammatical aspect, existing analyses are inconsistent in specifying how perfective and imperfective aspects are marked. Dunn (1968), Agheyisi (1990), Omoruyi (1991) and (Yuka & Omoregbe 2008) claim that the perfective aspect is expressed with *nẹ*, Yuka & Omoregbe (2011) propose that it is marked with the high tone on the verb in addition to *nẹ* while (Omoregbe (2012) argues in favor of the -rV as well as *nẹ*. With respect to imperfective aspect, there have been several proposals as to the specific marker of this aspectual category. Dunn (1968) claims that the imperfective aspect is unmarked in the language, Agheyisi (1980) claims that it is marked by *ghá* while Yuka & Omoregbe (2008; 2011b) as well as Omoregbe (2012) propose that the imperfective is marked by *nẹ* in Edo. The precise temporal category marked by the low tone on the verb has also been a source of controversy in several accounts of tense and aspect in Edo; while Yuka and Omoregbe (2008, 2011) propose a present tense reading, Omoregbe (2012) claims it is a habitual/progressive marker.

1.2.2 Key Theories in Aspect-Actionality Interactions

1.2.2.1 Vendler

Although the actional classification of predicates dates to Aristotle (cf. Binnick 1991; Rosen 1999), Vendler (1957) is the most influential work in the classification of predicates based on their ‘inherent’ lexical aspect. He classified English predicates into 4 classes: states, activities, achievements and accomplishments. Vendler’s classification schema has been modified and extended to other languages. Smith

(1997) adds the class 'semelfactives' to the four classes, a combination which, according to Van Valin (2006), is adequate in accounting for actionality cross-linguistically. The universal adequacy of (neo-) Vendlerian classifications is also echoed by scholars such as Chelliah & De Reuse (2011: 292) who claim that Vendler's classification schema has "stood the test of time". These assertions suggest an unproblematic actional classification terrain; but this is not the case.

Vendler's classification schema has been criticized for the following reason.

(i) The inadequacy of the schema to account for all classes of verbs cross-linguistically (Sasse 2002a; Von Stechow & Matthewson 2008; Crane 2011; Persohn 2018; Kanijo 2019).

(ii) The inapplicability of classification tests cross-linguistically both across classes and between predicates of the same class (Wilhelm 2003; Rothstein 2004; Smollett 2005; Van Valin 2006; Jeschull 2007; Filip 2011; Smith 2013).

(iii) The observation that a predicate with "translational equivalence" across languages may vary in actional character in different languages (Botne 2003a).

(iv) Its inability to account for some classes of verbs, most notably inchoatives (aka two-phase verbs) which lexicalize a change-in-state in addition to the resulting state from the change (Kershner 2002; Sergey Tatevosov 2002; R. Botne 2003; 2008; Botne & Kershner 2008; Seidel 2008; Botne 2010; Lusekelo 2016; Persohn 2017a; 2017b; Gunnink 2018).

The aforementioned challenges with Vendler's classification schema led linguists to search for a more robust classification schema for predicates based on lexical aspect.

1.2.2.2 Radical Selection Theories

One of the approaches adopted to cater for the inadequacies of the universalist, aprioristic (neo-) Vendlerian actional classification schema is the bi-dimensional approach to actional classification. These approaches to actionality are known as bidimensional because they utilize the interaction of both lexical aspect and grammatical aspect in their explication of actionality. One instantiation of this is espoused in Bickel (1997), known as 'selection theories of aspect', that is renamed 'radical selection theory' by Sasse (2002). Within this approach, grammatical aspect and lexical aspect are in a 'strict correspondence relationship (sometimes referred to as operator-operandum relation) such that grammatical aspect markers serve as phase-selectors that pick-out temporal extensions on the time-axis provided by lexical aspect (Sasse 2002:223). Actional properties are not stated in holistic terms, but decomposed into phases; the situation boundary (transition) τ and the phase between boundaries ϕ . The actional properties of verbs are thus expressed as different $\tau + \phi$ configurations. Grammatical aspect within this framework 'highlights' specific actional components. Prominent proponents of the bidimensional approach to classifying actionality include Johanson (1971; 1996; 2000b; 2000a), Timberlake (1985), Breu (1984; 1985; 1994), Bickel (1997), Bertinetto (1997) and Smith (2013).

1.2.2.3 Tatevosov

Another bi-dimensional approach is by Tatevosov. As earlier mentioned in subsection 1.2.2.1, a common assumption is that Vendlerian classes are logical universals hence not subject to cross-linguistic variation. Ebert (1995: 186) writes "most times it is assumed that a verb or verb phrase has the same actional character as its closest English counterpart". Tatevosov (2002: 324) argues for a parametric, non-

aprioristic approach to actionality instead, claiming that “... actionality is a PARAMETER that allows for different settings in different languages”. According to him, cross-linguistic actional types such as ‘stative’, and ‘telic’ are generalizations over the actional systems of individual languages and not semantic primitives.

1.2.3 Current context of aspect-actionality interaction

The bidimensional parametric approach to actionality has been applied in non-African languages such as Romance/Slavic languages (Breu 1980; 1984; 1985; 1994), Eurasian languages (Tatevosov 2002) as well as African languages of the Bantu language family (e.g., Botne, 2003, 2008, 2010; Botne & Kershner, 2000; Crane & Fleisch 2019); Gunnink, 2018; Kershner, 2002; Lusekelo, 2016; Persohn, 2017a, 2017b; Seidel, 2008, among others).

In the context of Bantu languages, the need to adopt the bidimensional parametric approach to actionality was motivated primarily by the existence of inchoative states - verbs which encode both a change of state and the state resulting from the change (Botne 2003; Crane & Fleisch 2016; Persohn 2017; 2018; 2019; Kanijo 2019). These have contributed significantly to the typology of actional classification as they have brought to the fore the grammatical properties of actional systems which are not based on the well-known Perfective/Imperfective distinction as well as the actional characteristics of languages in which inchoative verbs are attested. However, there is no account of a bidimensional parametric actional classification of predicates in any non-Bantu Niger-Congo language except for Siamou (Toews 2015)¹. This dissertation

¹ There have been previous studies of actional classification of non-Bantu Niger-Congo language albeit in the (neo-) Vendlerian tradition such as in Hausa (Abdoulaye 1992), Igbo (Agbo 2013) and Edo (Iyamu 2016).

aims to fill that gap by providing an account of aspect-actionality interactions within the bidimensional parametric framework in Edo a non-Bantu Niger-Congo language.

1.3 Research Aims, Objectives and Questions

1.3.1 Aims

The aims of this dissertation are;

- (i) to resolve discrepancies in accounting for the temporal system of Edo and
- (ii) to classify verbs in Edo on the basis of aspect-actionality interactions.

1.3.2 Research Objectives

The aforementioned aims will be achieved by;

- (i) Specifying the temporal categories encoded by the TAM markers in Edo.
- (ii) identifying and classifying verbs in Edo based on the cluster of actional primitives (phases/change) encoded by verb senses.

1.3.3 Research Questions

This section presents the research questions which this dissertation seeks to answer and the research background that make the research questions necessary..

(i) **Temporal markers in Edo:** The TAM system of any language is an integral part of its grammatical system. Edo is no exception as grammatical categories such as negation are dependent on the TAM system. It will also be shown that the actional system of Edo cannot be adequately accounted for without reference to its TAM marking system. A consistent account of TAM markers in the language is thus important as this will serve as a solid foundation for investigations into other aspects of the grammar of the language including actionality. Hence answers to the following questions will be sought - What is the temporal-aspectual landscape of Edo? How can previous disagreements in the analyses of the TA system of Edo be resolved?

(ii) **Aspect-actionality interpretations in Edo**: Following the observation that actionality should not be approached from a universalist perspective but from a parametric one, the absence of studies in aspect-actionality interactions in Edo, Edooid or any non-Bantu African language (except Siamou) is both a theoretical and typological gap. This dissertation intends to fill this gap by answering the following questions - How does aspect-actionality interaction 'explain' the different Temporal-Aspectual interpretations in the language? How can verbs be classified in Edo based on the interplay between lexical aspect and grammatical aspect dimensions? What are the relevant diagnostics for this classificatory schema?

This study seeks to provide answers to the following research questions. With respect to the TA system of Edo (i) Is Edo a tense, aspect, or mood prominent language? What are the temporal markers in Edo and what temporal categories do they mark?

With respect to aspect-actionality interactions in Edo (ii) What are the possible temporal interpretations when grammatical aspect interacts with lexical aspect in Edo? How can this system of interactions serve as a classification schema for verb senses in the language? What actionality primitives do Edo verbs encode? How can the actional properties of Edo verbs be utilized in classifying verbs in the language? What are the grammatical implications of this classification schema for the language?

1.4 Methodology

1.4.1 General considerations

This study followed the suggestions of Cover (2015) for eliciting TAM categories as well as Bar-el (2015) and Crane and Fleisch's (2019) proposals for conducting

fieldwork research when investigating actionality. The following suggestions were implemented.

(i) Avoid the potential circularity that is typically associated with aspect-actionality interaction by using tests outside of the verbal/aspect system e.g. co-occurrence with adverbials and phasal verbs (e.g. start, stop, finish).

(ii) Distinguish actional interpretations which are entailments from implicatures.

(iii) Pay attention to quantized vs non-quantized arguments. Croft (2012) also notes the effects of (non-) quantization when working with transitive verbs.

(iv) Avoid the effects of researcher native-language interference by providing contextual information or physically acting out situations and corroborating actional interpretations with other native speakers.

(v) Design and conduct exhaustive elicitation sessions. I elicited as many aspect/verb interaction as possible and then streamlined them as important contrasts became apparent in order to avoid pre-conceived notions influencing my understanding of the actional system.

(vi) Conduct semi-structured elicitation sessions; the elicitation process was designed to ensure all paradigms planned for that session were tested while allowing for conversational 'detours' which could provide additional insight.

(vii) Implement interview-style elicitation sessions at the later stages of the elicitation process: I employed a conversational interview style with five consultants in order to discover new meanings/meaning nuances. This also made it possible for the consultants to serve as a check on each other's interpretation.

1.4.2 Consultants

The study made use of 15 language consultants. The choice of consultants was controlled for age variation with the youngest being 22 years old and the oldest being 96 years old. They were all born in Edo speaking communities and grew up using Edo as the primary language of communication and Nigerian Pidgin or standard Nigerian English as a lingua franca.

1.4.3 Data selection Criteria

I created a questionnaire that comprised different verbs from the following thematic groups from (Levin 1993). This was done to eliminate randomness in the choice of verbs and avoid choosing only verbs from a particular class(es) following the suggestions of Crane & Fleisch (2019) on eliciting actional classes across languages.

- (i) Physical processes and changes e.g., *kpòlò* 'be(come) fat', *lé* 'cook'.
- (ii) Perception, emotion and intellectual activity e.g., *ghèé* 'see', *hoèmwé* '(to) love', *rén* 'know'.
- (iii) Psychological state e.g., *gúi* 'be(come) angry'.
- (iv) Motion e.g., *rhùlẹ* 'run'.
- (v) Change of position e.g., *tòtá* 'sit', *dìguẹ* 'kneel'.
- (vi) Labor and everyday life e.g., *bọ* 'build', *dọlọ...yí* 'repair', *giẹ* 'laugh'
- (vii) Communication e.g., *támá* 'tell'

Each verb was then presented within a context and sentence frame which contains one of the TAM paradigms in Edo in order to elicit the actional interpretation(s) associated with that verb-TAM combination.

1.4.4 Constructional paradigms elicited.

Consultants were asked to provide interpretation and grammaticality judgements in verb + TAM paradigm contexts as well as verb + adverbial/phasal verb context. The TAM paradigms that were elicited include factative, past, imperfective, habitual, prospective, perfect, irrealis, persistive (past and present), adverbials and phasal verbs.

1.5.5 Format of elicitation sessions

Elicitation sessions were conducted over Zoom. Prior to the sessions, I selected verbs from seven thematic groups and categorized them into states, activities, achievements, accomplishments and change of states (CoS). This was an initial classification exercise based on the actional classes translational equivalent verbs in other languages such as English and Bantu languages (e.g. Nyamwezi). The final classification of verbs based on aspect-actionality interactions in Edo is based on the application of diagnostics designed in this study. Consultants were then asked to supply the interpretation(s) each verb received when they co-occurred with each of the TAM paradigms as well as the contexts that licensed each interpretation.

1.5 Significance of Research

(i) Actionality is understudied: This has been attributed to the assumption that actional classes are universal. As Bar-el (2015:75) puts it, “the lack of attention to aspectual classes in the language documentation literature can likely be attributed to a commonly held assumption that the inventory of aspectual classes is universal”. This is a false assumption as cross-linguistic investigations into the actional systems of genetically unrelated languages show that languages differ in the ways they encode actional properties.

(ii) Actionality is grammatically relevant: Actional distinctions belong to a set of semantic features with wide application. As Moens & Steedman (2005:17) put it, “part of the meaning of any utterance of a sentence is one of a small number of temporal/aspectual profiles distinguished on a small number of dimensions”. Actional features are significant because of “the way in which they interact with the syntactic and morphological structures in natural languages” (Filip 2011:1191; cf. Dowty 1979:185). For example, the actional feature telicity determines a verb’s interpretation/co-occurrence with certain adverbials.

(iii) Actionality has proven to be relevant in explaining a range of linguistic phenomena. According to Filip (2012:721), actionality’s “usefulness if not necessity, for the explanation of a wide range of language phenomena is well established”. Van Valin (2005) argues based on cross-linguistic studies of genetically diverse languages that actional distinctions are “central to the organization of their verbal systems”.

(i) For Edo: A proper understanding of temporal marking is indispensable in explaining other aspects of a language. By providing a clear account of the temporal marking system of Edo, I intend to provide a solid platform for discussing other grammatical phenomena whose explication depends on the temporal marking system of the language. Secondly, this will be the first bidimensional account of actionality in the language as the only other account of actionality, Iyamu (2016), adopts the universalist Vendlerian approach to actionality. This dissertation will thus bring to the fore how grammatical aspect and actionality interact in the language and how this can be used as a classification schema.

(ii) For language typology: Investigations into actional systems of languages which adopt an aprioristic, bidimensional, parametric approach to classifying verbs exists for Romance, Slavic, Eurasian and Bantu languages. Although Edo is a Niger-Congo language like Bantu languages, its temporal system differs from those of Bantu languages (for example, non-Bantu Niger-Congo languages have a temporal category known as the factative whereas Bantu languages do not). This is the first study of a non-Bantu Niger-Congo language which operates a factative-imperfective (in contrast to a perfective-imperfective system) distinction to account for the interaction between grammatical aspect and actionality. It will thus serve as a reference point for comparing and contrasting actionality systems with Bantu languages on one hand and languages of other genetically unrelated languages on the other hand.

1.6 Limitations of Study

1.6.1 Scope limitations

This study is limited to accounting for aspect-actionality interactions in monoclausal indicative constructions in Edo. Actional interpretations in relative clauses and serial verb construction are not undertaken in this study.

1.6.2 Methodological limitations

The data used in this study were sourced primarily from direct elicitation sessions with consultants and is based on a database of 50 verbs. There was limited use of questionnaires (Dahl 1985) and no secondary data sources. The reason why no secondary sources were used is because written materials in the language are not marked for tone - and tone plays a pivotal role in understanding both temporal marking and aspect-actionality interactions in the language.

1.6.3 Resource limitations

The data collection was done over a period of 8 months over Zoom. This was necessitated by challenges in international travel imposed by COVID-19.

1.6.4 Generalizability

One of the goals of this dissertation is ascertain aspect-actionality interactions in a non-Bantu Niger-Congo language, Edo with the goal of understanding the similarities and differences in the actional systems of Bantu languages and non-Bantu Niger-Congo languages. It is pertinent to point out that such generalizations should be considered carefully as non-Bantu Niger-Congo is not a homogenous group with respect to their temporal marking systems. Hence, insights gained by studying the actional properties of Edo verbs cannot be said to be representative of the actional systems of all non-Bantu languages.

1.7 Road Map

Chapter 1 introduced the study by explaining the background, motivation, significance and methodology employed in data collection for this dissertation. In Chapter 2, I discuss extensively the existing literature and theoretical underpinnings relevant to understanding the key concepts of this study. Chapter 3 is a grammar sketch of Edo. It will discuss in some detail aspects of Edo grammar which need to first be understood in order to fully grasp the temporal marking system of Edo and aspect-actionality interactions. In chapter 4, I present my account of temporal marking in Edo and provide evidence for my claims for each TAM marker. Chapter 5 discusses aspect-actionality interactions in Edo by discussing the resulting interpretation when different verbs co-occur in the context TAM markers, verb interpretations in the context of phasal

verbs/adverbials and how these interpretations serve as a schema to classify verbs in Edo. Chapter 6 summarizes and concludes the study.

CHAPTER 2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses pertinent topics and theories necessary to understand temporal marking and classifying verb senses based on aspect-actionality interactions. Tense and aspect are grammatical categories used to convey temporal information within verb structures in many natural languages (Klein 2013):1-2). Actionality (also called aktionsart (Goedsche 1940); (Garey 1957), lexical aspect (Olsen 1994) “encodes the constituent phases and boundaries that make up a state-of-affairs” (Crane & Persohn 2019). It refers to the inherent temporal phasal characteristics of verbs that are made manifest by its interaction with grammatical aspect.

The aim of this chapter is to present a systematic overview of the core concepts in tense, aspect, actionality as well as the theoretical underpinnings of aspect-actionality interaction. In order to make a meaningful contribution to the field and facilitate understanding of the discussion in this study, it is pertinent to address the terminology used in the literature. This is because, the Tense-Aspect-Mood (TAM) domain attests frequently used terms that vary in meaning across different linguistic theoretical traditions and even within individual studies. It is sometimes unclear how an author interprets two similar but not identical terms, such as "tense" and "aspect," or "past" and "completive." Another common source of disagreement in the literature is with respect to categorial classification of TAM elements i.e., whether to classify a particular TAM marker, like the English Present Perfect, as an aspect or as a tense. Therefore, I will review the definitions of the terms "Tense," "Aspect," and "Actionality”

with the goal to establishing their meanings as unambiguously as possible for consistent use in the present study.

The rest of this chapter is structured as follows. In the next section (2.2), I discuss two key concepts – tense and aspect. Section 2.3 explores actionality in terms of the parametric and non-parametric approaches to actionality while section 2.4 discusses temporal marking in Niger-Congo within a typological perspective.

2.2. Temporal Marking

One of the design features of natural language which sets it apart from other communication systems is displacement (Hockett & Hockett 1960), (Von Stechow & Heim 2011). This property makes it possible for us to discuss things that are not happening right here and now; past, future, and unreal events. Without displacement, we would be limited to the present space and time. Tense, aspect and mood (TAM) are some of the main tools languages use to effect displacement. ‘Temporality’ is a term used by some to refer to the general expression of time (Klein 1994), while for some others (e.g. Binnick 2001), it refers to the location of an event in time relative to the moment of speech, (aka tense). Tense and aspect are “overt, grammatical marking of temporality and aspectuality, respectively “ (Savić 2021: 37). They are classified as verbal categories (Comrie 1976; Malchukov 2009) as they are typically marked in the verb (Comrie 1985; Rose & Beaudoin-Lietz & Nurse 2002; Klein 2013),

In this section, I discuss tense and aspect. It is important to define the concepts clearly because as (Savić 2021: 34) points out, “a special challenge is posed by the frequent terms that exhibit semantic variation in the different linguistic traditions, and sometimes even between individual studies...Another common point of discrepancy in the literature is the classification of one and the same TAM marker (e.g. The English

Present Perfect) as an aspect or as a tense”. In subsection 2.2.1, I define tense and present some of the approaches to the analysis of tense. Subsection 2.2.2 discusses two approaches to the analysis of aspect: the unidimensional approach (2.2.2.1) and the bidimensional approach (2.2.2.2).

2.2.1. Tense

Tense is a deictic category which locates situations in time, typically with reference to the speech time (ST), although it could also be with reference to some other point in time (Comrie 1976, 1985).

Languages which grammaticize this location in time (e.g., French which has past, present, and future tenses) are known as tense languages, while languages which express temporality by other means such as context, adverbials or particles (e.g. Mandarin) are considered tenseless languages. A distinction is usually made between absolute and the relative tense as two subcategories of tense. In this study, ‘tense’ without further specification refers to absolute tense. Absolute tense refers to the grammaticalization of the temporal location of an event in relation to (ST) (Comrie 1976:5, Comrie 1985:9, Binnick 2001:557, Rose et al. 2002:87).

Relative tense refers to the location of an event relative to a contextually specified reference point other than ST (Comrie 1985; Binnick 2001; Lyons 1977).

2.2.2 Aspect

Aspect is also concerned with the expression of tense like tense. However, it differs from tense as it is non-deictic. The lack of a universally accepted definition of aspect has been noted in the literature (Binnick 2001; Guéntcheva 2016), Comrie’s (1976:3) definition of aspect as “different ways of viewing the internal temporal constituency of a situation” has been widely largely used as a start point for in the TAM

discourse. There is a distinction made in the TAM literature between grammatical aspect (also known as viewpoint aspect) and lexical aspect (also known as situation-aspect aktionsart or actionality). This brings us to the distinction made between a unidimensional and bidimensional approaches to aspect. The difference lies in whether an author proposes that there is only one aspect-relevant category (typically grammatical aspect) as is the case with the unidimensional approach or two aspectual categories (grammatical aspect and lexical aspect) in the case of the bidimensional approach.

2.2.2.1. Unidimensional approaches

Unidimensional approaches assume that there is only one set of aspect-relevant semantic primitives. In their strongest form, they use the same set of categories with the same aspectual labels on all levels of grammatical analysis. In some versions, proponents assume only one level (typically the sentence) as grammatically relevant for the manifestation of aspect.

An example of a unidimensional approach to aspect is Verkuyl's (1972, 1993) theory which is centered on the logical structure of the sentence, adopting a strict dichotomy of terminative vs durative events, on one hand and bounded vs unbounded events, on the other. He rejects a classification of predicates based on actionality including Vendler's classification, and claims that "aspect is a non-lexical property of sentence structure, both in non-Slavic and Slavic languages" (Verkuyl 1993:4). One of the reasons for advocating this position is because "lexical-semantic considerations have to be avoided because they often slip into ontological considerations" (Verkuyl 1993:11). As Sasse (2002:25) rightly points out, these problems cannot be solved by 'blurring' the semantic distinctions of grammatical aspect and lexical aspect and

replacing the distinction with a binary syntactic opposition. Instead, a more viable solution lies in a theory which acknowledges the distinction and considers the interaction between lexicon and grammar.

2.2.2.1.1 Problems with unidimensional accounts

The unidimensional approach posits only one aspectual category and does not account for the interactions that exist between view-point aspect and situation-aspect because the unidimensional does not make room for such an interaction. As will be shown in this study, the interaction between these two aspectually-relevant categories can account for the interpretations TA markers have in the context of different verbs. The aspect-actionality interaction will also be used as a basis to classify verbs. Without acknowledging the existence of a second aspectual category, it will be impossible to account for the varied interpretations that arise aspect-actionality interactions and propose a classification schema that is grammatically relevant.

2.2.2.2 Bidimensional approaches

. Bidimensional approaches on the other hand, insist on maintaining a distinction between two such dimensions (typically the sentence and the verb); they however differ with respect to the degree of independence between these two dimensions. Some proponents of the bidimensional approach maintain that aspect and actionality are independent and therefore apply separately (Bertinetto 1997; Smith 1997). Other proponents argue in favor of a distinction in grammatical levels on which aspect and actionality apply but maintain that there is a strong correspondence between aspect and actionality (Bickel 1997).

Bidimensional theories of actionality are a product of later stages in the development of aspect theories. The theories originated in the perfective/imperfective

centered approach to aspect by increasingly considering the relevance of actionality in determining view-point aspect. Within this new approach, actionality is understood as the temporal characteristics of the semantics of verbs/VPs which interact in systematic ways with grammatical aspect; an interaction which was previously ignored by perfective/imperfective viewpoint theories of aspect. One version of the bidimensional proposal conceives aspect and actionality as being in a correspondence relation where the former act as phase-selectors that highlight matching phases made available by lexical aspect. Actionality is a property of verb senses (sometimes of VPs or propositions e.g., Bickel 1997 and Cseto 2000).

2.3 Actionality

In this section, I discuss various approaches to actionality. I discuss (neo)-Vendlerian approaches in some detail because his approach to classifying verbs based on their inherent temporal properties is the most prominent and several universalist classificatory schemas are based on Vendler (1957).

Actionality has been described as having to do with the “intrinsic temporal characteristic of situations” (Sasse 2002: 203), the “pattern of distribution of action through time” (Talmy 2007: 106) or “the way situations unfold in time” (Smith 1997: xiii). It is also said to suggest “the particular way in which [the] verb presupposes and involves the notion of time” (Vendler 1957: 143). ‘Actionality’ has been known by several other terms including aktionsart, aspectual class, aspectual character (Lyons 1977), situation type (Smith 1991), eventuality type (Bach 1996, Filip 1999), action (Bache 1995a, b), state of affairs (Dik 1989), and taxonomic category (Paduceva 1996).

The primary interest of investigation in this domain is “the way in which actional distinctions (...) are played out in the grammar and in the structure and meanings of

words” (Bach 2005: 169). In other words, instances where actionality explains grammatical behavior and constraints in the use of various linguistic phenomena (Boogaart 2004: 1170).

Research in actionality is typically centered on answering the following questions: “what are the aspectually-relevant meaning components/primitives, how are they related to each other and how do they determine the relevant aspectual classes to the exclusion of other classes?” (Filip 2011: 1192). Filip (2012: 721) highlights the relevance of actionality to grammar when she states that its “usefulness, if not necessity, for the explanation of a wide range of language phenomena is well established”.

As noted above, tense, aspect and actionality are temporal categories which operate on different dimensions. Tense and Aspect are grammatical categories, while actionality is a lexical category. It is therefore not surprising to find the grammatical categories influencing the lexical category and vice versa.

(Polančec 2020: 1) writes: “actionality and aspect are related but distinct linguistic phenomena. He distinguishes between them thus: “Actionality is defined as a lexico-semantic and lexico-grammatical phenomena and aspect as a grammatical one”.

One of the ways in which this interaction is manifested is that the grammatical behavior of aspect is mostly determined by actionality. The situation aspect value (actionality) of a predicate may change as a result of the introduction of syntactic elements - a phenomenon known as aspectual shift (e.g. (De Swart 1998; Zucchi 1998; Rothstein 2008). A shift occurs when a single reading is applied to an aspectually ambiguous predicate. For example, 1(a) is ambiguous with respect to telicity as it can be interpreted as Bill was engaged in reading a book in the past but did not complete

the book (atelic reading) or Bill read the book completely (telic reading). On the other hand, (1b) has only one available reading; Bill read the book and completed the event in two hours.

1. (a) Bill read a book (telic/atelic).
- (b) Bill read a book in two hours (telic only)

This shift also happens when the ‘inherent’ aspectual value of a predicate changes. For example, in (2a) the verb ‘sing’ is classified as an atelic verb (with no inherent endpoint) however in (2b) the VP ‘sing a song’ is telic.

2. (a) Jane sang (atelic).
- (b) Jane sang a song (telic)

In a similar vein, (Persohn 2017a: 157) notes that in Nyakyusa, the meaning of the present perfective depends on the actionality of the lexical verb. In the context of non-inchoative verbs like ‘watch’ and ‘come’, it yields a ‘completed act’ interpretation whereas with inchoative verbs like ‘become angry as shown in (3a) and (3b) below.

3. (a) *mu-keet-ile leelo mu-keet-ile leelo! N-iis-ile ne*
 2pl-watch-PFV now/but 2pl-watch-pfv now/but 1sg-come-pfv 1sg
malafyale
 chief
 “You have seen now! You have seen now! I have come as a king.’ [Hare and Hippo]
- (b) *a-kaleele*
 1-be(come)_angry.PFV
 (Default reading:) ‘S/he is angry.’ Persohn (2017a:137)

The grammatical nature of aspect facilitates this interaction since aspect as a grammatical category co-occurs with verbs and this leads to unavoidable interactions between actionality and aspect. These systematic interactions between grammatical aspect and actionality then enable us to determine ‘aspect-sensitive’ classes (i.e.

classify verbs). This is based on the assumption that aspect and actionality are in an 'operator-operandum' relationship; where grammatical aspect markers (e.g. the perfective, progressive) operate on the semantic primitives of actionality (e.g. phases, boundaries). The identification of aspect-sensitive classes in individual languages allows for the 'typologization' of actionality by comparing aspect and actional systems across languages.

Vendler's (1957:144)¹ attempt to "locate and describe the most common time schemata implied by the use of English verbs" is the most influential approach to actionality and is typically taken as the start-off point for most discussions of actionality. This is not to deny the innovation in these approaches as they differ from Vendler's analysis and from one another with respect to proposals to the following questions: is actionality a lexical or structural phenomenon? What are the defining properties for each class? What is the relationship between different classes? Are classes organized hierarchically? Etc.

Vendler's (1957/1967) categories have been accepted by a great number of scholars –albeit with minor modifications (e.g. Dowty 1979; Smith 1991)– **as valid for all human languages**; A typical example is van Valin (2006), who discusses the Vendlerian categories, with the addition of Smith's (1991) category - semelfactives, under the title of "... universals of verbal semantics". This wide acceptance of Vendler's categories is not peculiar to theoretical linguistics but also in the field of descriptive linguistics. (Ebert 1995: 186) notes that in descriptive grammars "most often it is

¹ Vendler's analysis had a couple of precursors such as Ryle (1949) and Maslov (1948).

assumed that a verb or verb phrase has the same actional character as its closest English counterpart”. This ‘bias’ is not absent in language documentation/fieldwork as illustrated in (Chelliah & De Reuse 2010: 92) fieldwork manual, according to which “the defining characteristics of verbs are captured by the semantic classification of Vendler (1957), which has stood the test of time”.

Tatevosov (2002: 322), notes that there is a tacit assumption that the notions on which Vendler’s classes are based are universal (see e.g., Chelliah & de Reuse 2010). Hence, the classes are considered not subject to parametric variation. This implies that verbs in every language would be categorized into the Vendlerian classes as first established for English.

Contemporary cross-linguistic research in actionality has challenged this universal approach to actionality for the following reasons amongst others;

- i. Lack of cross-linguistic application.
- ii. It is sometimes unclear what established diagnostics test for.
- iii. Limitations of tests across predicates of same class

These criticisms prompted a search for approaches to actionality which took into account the idiosyncrasies of individual languages with the ultimate goal of identifying actional classes which are peculiar to specific language families and those which are more widely attested. One such approaches is that proposed by Sergei Tatevosov.

2.3.1. Non-Parametric approaches to actionality: Vendler

2.3.1.1 Vendler’s classes

Vendler classifies verbs into states, activities, achievements and accomplishments. Stative verbs encode static and temporally unbounded events such as state predicate verbs, existential verbs, perception verbs, cognition verbs and

emotion verbs (Van Valin and LaPolla 1997). They encode situations involving homogenous states of affairs with no inherent endpoint. This means that states (unlike nonstates) can be judged true at a moment in time (Dowty 1979). Activity verbs are dynamic and temporally unbounded eventualities. They encode situations as consisting of successive phases over time with no inherent end point. Examples of activity verbs include motion verbs ('run', 'walk') and consumption verbs ('eat', 'drink') (Van Valin 1997:115). Achievement verbs encode punctual/instantaneous events. They take place over such short periods of time that they are perceived as momentary. Examples of achievement verbs include 'hit', 'cut', 'pluck' etc. Accomplishment verbs characterize situations as successive phases but differ from activities in that they encode an inherent endpoint. They have an outcome; a result which is achieved through change over a period. Examples of accomplishment verbs are 'melt', 'dry', 'repair', etc.

These verb classes are typically distinguished in terms of four temporal features; [+/-stative], [+/-punctual], [+/-telic] and [+/-dynamic]. The [stative] feature expresses whether the verb encodes a 'happening'. The distinction between 'telic' and 'atelic' events was proposed by Garey (1957) based on the Greek word 'telos' (goal/purpose). Telic verbs express "an action tending towards a goal" (Garey 1957:106), while atelic verbs describe situations that 'are realized as soon as they begin" (Ibid). The [telic] feature distinguishes verbs with an intrinsic temporal boundary from verbs without one. The feature [punctual] takes into consideration whether an event has internal duration or is instantaneous. The feature [dynamic] refers to whether an event involves action or not.

Activities involve action hence are [+dynamic] while states, achievements and accomplishments are [-dynamic]. The feature composition of each verb class could be captured in a feature matrix as presented in Fig 2 below.

	States	Activities	Accomplishmts	Semelfactives	Achievement	A.accompl
Static	+	-	-	-	-	-
Telic	-	-	+	-	+	+
Punctual	-	-	-	+	+	-
Dynamic	-	+	+	+/-	-	-

Fig 2-2: Feature matrix of Aktionsart classes. Van Valin (2005:33)².

The feature [dynamic] distinguishes events which contain internal changes from one moment of time to another, from non-dynamic (or static) events, which do change from time to time. Punctuality distinguishes durative events, which last for some time, from non-durative events. Telicity distinguishes bounded events, which are “completed” or have an inherent end-point, from atelic/unbounded events, which have no such temporal property.

2.3.1.2 Diagnostics for the classes

In addition to semantic features, Vendler’s classes are also determined based on their collocation potential, interpretation, and entailment construals with temporal modifiers, tense and aspect. Some examples of these tests are (i) – (vi) taken from Dowty (1979:60).

- i. Occurs with ‘in X time’ adverbial (i.e., take X time to V)
- ii. Occurs with ‘for X time’ adverbial (i.e., spend X-time V-ing)
- iii. Occurs with the progressive

² The feature matrix includes two classes not included in Vendler’s original proposal; semelfactives (Smith 1997) and Active accomplishments (van Valin and Lapolla 1997) which are telic uses of activity verbs. This discussion is limited to the original classes proposed by Vendler hence the discussion of these two classes is avoided.

- iv. Occurs with 'almost'.
- v. The progressive entailment test
- vi. Occurs as the complement of stop/finish.

The collocation tests '*in X time*' and '*for X time*' adverbials are used to distinguish statives and activities (atelic verbs), on the one hand from accomplishments and achievements (telic verbs) on the other hand. Statives and activities are acceptable with *for X time*, but not with *in X time* as shown in (8a) and (8b). In contrast, achievements and accomplishments co-occur with *in X time*, but not with *for X time* as shown in (8c–d).

- 4. (a) John loved Mary for /#in two years (stative)
 - (b) John walked for/? in an hour (activity)
 - (c) John painted a picture in/? for an hour (accomplishment)
 - (d) John noticed the painting in/? for a few minutes (achievement)
- (Walková 2012: 502)

Co-occurrence restrictions with the progressive aspect serves to distinguish activities and accomplishments from statives and achievements. As shown in (9a–b) below, activities and accomplishments are acceptable with the progressive, whereas statives and achievements are not, as in (9c–d). Statives are unacceptable with the progressive because they describe events that do not contain internal temporal contours (they are non-dynamic). It is claimed that achievements are unacceptable with the progressive because they are punctual/non-durative in nature.

- 5. (a) John is running (activity)
- (b) John is building a house (accomplishment)
- (c) #John is knowing the answer (stative)

(d) ? John is noticing a stranger (achievement)

Walková (2012:501).

The ambiguity test with *almost* differentiates accomplishment verbs from other aspectual classes. As shown in (6) below, only accomplishments are ambiguous with *almost*, i.e., they either mean that the event did not occur at all (as in other classes) or the event began but was not completed. All examples below are from Walkova (2012).

6. (a) *John almost loved Mary* means he did not love her (stative)

(b) *John almost walked* means he did not walk (activity).

(c) *John almost painted a picture* means either (i) John did not begin painting at all, or (ii), John began painting but did not finish (accomplishment).

(d) *John almost noticed the painting* means John did not notice the painting (achievement).

Walková (2012:502).

The progressive entailment test distinguishes activities from accomplishments. As shown in the examples in (7) below, from Kearns (2000:216). For activities (7a), the progressive entails that the event reached its endpoint, but this reading is not available in accomplishments, as shown in (7b). As shown in (8b) and (8d), statives and achievements do not license the progressive; thus, their occurrence with the entailment test is redundant.

7. (a) *John was walking in the park* entails John walked in the park

(b) *John was building a house* does not entail John built a house.

It is further argued (e.g. Walkova 2012) that because accomplishments are the only class of verbs which encode both a duration and an endpoint, they can occur as

the complement of finish. All other classes are infelicitous with finish. This is illustrated in 8 below.

8. (a) John finished painting a picture (Accomplishment)
- (b) #John finished loving Mary (Stative)
- (c) #John finished walking (Activity)
- (d) #John finished noticing the painting (Achievement)

Walková (2012:502).

The phasal verb *stop* requires its complement to have duration. Hence, achievements do not license it. This is exemplified in 9 below; citing examples from Walková (2012, p. 502).

9. (a) John stopped loving Mary
- (b) John stopped walking
- (c) John stopped painting the picture
- (e) #John stopped noticing the painting

2.3.1.3. Problems with tests

Despite the wide acceptance of Vendler's aspectual classification of predicates, his system has not been without some criticism. This will be discussed under the following sub headings: the lack of cross linguistic application (2.6.4.1), the question of what temporal features the diagnostics test for and the lack of consistency in the classification scheme even within the same class, the question of what is being classified – verb, verb phrase or verb sense? - the question of what the diagnostics test and the lack of consistency in the classification scheme even within the same class, the presence of verbs which do not exhibit the actional characteristics of Vendlerian classes

(e.g., atypical achievements/accomplishments), actional classes unaccounted for (e.g. inchoatives) and redundant phasal verbs in some languages.

2.3.1.3.1 The Lack of Cross-linguistic Application

Bar-el (2015:78) reports that Squamish (and in fact all other Salish languages) and Dene Suline (Athapaskan) do not exhibit sensitivity to the for X time/in X time distinction which serves to distinguish telic verbs from atelic verbs. In Dene Suline, there is only one time adverbial which covers the ‘in an hour’ and ‘for an hour’ meaning. Hence the telicity contrast based on this test is not available for these languages (Wilhelm 2005:75). Activities and accomplishments both license the time adverb and, in some cases, the same predicate yields both ‘in x time’ and ‘for x time’ interpretations. This is also the case of Edo which does not make the ‘for/in x time’ distinction to distinguish between telic vs atelic verbs, but uses one construction, *ya x time V* translated as ‘use x-time to V’ to distinguish verbs which encode a culmination (accomplishments) from those which do not. Verbs which do not encode culmination have a ‘spent x-time V-ing’ i.e., engaging in an event for x time. With verb which encode event culmination, a ‘spent x time to complete V-ing’ is obtained in the context of *ya x-time V*. This will be used as a diagnostic in chapter 5 to distinguish between accomplishments which encode

2.3.1.3.2 What is being classified?

It is typical to find both verbs (e.g. ‘to run’) and verb phrases (e.g., ‘run a mile’) simultaneously used as units of actional classification within the Vendlerian tradition of actional classification. As Sasse (2002: 216) notes: “One of the most problematic aspects of the literature in the [Vendlerian] tradition is its general vagueness with respect to the level of linguistic analysis on which the time-schemata obtain”. In this

study, the actional diagnostics and classification schema apply to verb senses not verbs.

2.3.1.3.3 What do Diagnostics Test?

Carlson (1977) notes that collocation with the progressive as a diagnostic for stativity is suspect as this diagnostic distinguishes stage-level from individual-level predicates (a point also made by Kratzer 1995). Most individual-level predicates are stative i.e., they encode permanent states while most stage-level predicates are nonstative as they encode temporary states. As (14a-b) shows, the progressive is more felicitous with stage level construals than with those of individual level interpretations.

10. (a) My socks ??lie/are lying under the bed.

(b) New Orleans lies/??is lying at the mouth of the Mississippi.

Lakoff (1966) also points out that three of the so-called stativity tests actually test for agentivity. These tests are collocation with *force/persuade*, collocation with agent-oriented adverbs such as *carefully* and *deliberately* and the ability to be licensed in an imperative construction. Example 15 below shows that constructions in which agentivity is attributed to an entity (such as a rock) which lacks agency, the verb is infelicitous as in (15a-c) even with a non-stative such as *roll*. In (15d-e) where the rock no longer has an agentive reading, the verb *roll* is felicitous.

11. (a)? I persuaded the rock to roll down the hill.

(b)? The rock rolled down the hill carefully/deliberately.

(c)? Roll down the hill, rock!

(d) The rock was rolling down the hill.

(e) What the rock did was roll down the hill

2.3.1.3.4 Limitations of Tests Across Predicates of Same Class

As earlier pointed out, Vendler's classes are typically taken for granted and as Bar-el (2015:79) points out, "little time is spent accounting for predicates that either do not fall into the expected classes, or the typical predicates that sometimes deviate from the behavior predicted by standard tests". Achievements have been the most problematic in this regard. It has been previously argued that achievements do not license the progressive aspect because of their punctual nature, as shown in (16a)

12. (a) * The firecracker is popping. (Van Valin 2006:159)

However, as Smith (1997) shows, some achievement predicates license the progressive aspect as shown in (11b).

(b) He was winning the race. (Smith 1997:46)

This shows that even within the same language there could be disagreement on the class membership within a given class.

2.3.1.3.9 'Finish' as a redundant test for telicity in Bantu

Vendler's tests predict that only telic verbs (such as accomplishments) are compatible with finish. The test is therefore supposed to distinguish between accomplishment and activity verbs. For example.

13. (a) John finished writing a letter (Accomplishment).

(b) ? John finished walking (Activity).

Based on examples from Nyakyusa and Southern Ndebele, Crane and Persohn (2019) show that a bounded/single-task-like reading is available for both activity-like (14) and accomplishment-like (15) verbs - as well as give a terminative reading with the phrase 'in X time'/ 'take X time'. Persohn (2017: 120–121), following Binnick (1991: 176) refers to such activity verbs as having "quasi-accomplishment" senses.

Activity-like verbs

14. (a) Southern Ndebele

uSipho u-cul-ile ng-emizuzu elitjhumu

1A.Sipho SP1-sing-PFV.DJ LOC-4.minute 4.ten

'Sipho sang in ten minutes.' (i.e., he finished that song or portion of the music in that time) (Crane ms.)

(b). Nyakyusa

Eeg-ile akabalilo akapimba uku-kosomol-a

SP1.take-PFV 12.time 12.short INF-cough-FV

'S/he took a short time to finish coughing.' (i.e., overcome illness)

(Persohn 2017: 120)

Accomplishment-like verbs

15. (a) Southern Ndebele

uSipho u-tlol-e i-ncwadi ng-amalanga amabili

1A.Sipho SP1-write-PFV.CJ 9-letter LOC-6.day 6.two

'Sipho wrote a letter in two days.' (he finished it)

(Crane ms.)

(b) Nyakyusa

eeg-ile iisala joosa uku-lembuk-a

SP1.take-PFV 9.hour 9.all INF-awaken-FV

'S/he has taken a whole hour to wake up.'

(Persohn 2017: 124)

Examples 14 and 15 thus show that the telicity test in Bantu based on compatibility with 'finish' is redundant as it does not differentiate telic verbs from atelic verbs i.e., accomplishments from activities.

2.3.1.4 Some problems with the Non-parametric actionality account

The non-parametric approaches to actionality stems from the observation that the universalist approach does not account for some phenomena in the aspect-actionality domain such as verb classes not predicted by the non-parametric approach and even for classes predicted, different phasal compositions are attested as compared to those predicted.

2.3.1.4.1 Achievements which lexicalize a coming-to-be/resultant phase in Bantu

Based on data from three Bantu languages (Nyakyusa, Ndali and Sukwa), Persohn (2018) shows that some verbs in these languages which would be classified as Vendlerian achievements encode a coming-to-be phase and/or a resultant-state phase in addition to their punctual-change-of-state characteristic. As earlier noted one of the diagnostics for achievements is their incompatibility with the progressive aspect, which has been attributed to their punctual nature. Persohn (2018:5-9) however shows how certain verbs in Nyakyusa (M31) which parallel achievements in English license the progressive aspect as shown in 1 below.

- 1 (a) *a-lɪ pa-kʊ-fwa*
NCL1-COP NCL16(LOC)-NCL15(INF)-die
's/he is dying'
- (b) *a-lɪ pa-kʊ-kalala*
NCL1-COP NCL16(LOC)-NCL15(INF)-be(come)_angry
's/he is getting angry / about to be angry'
- (c) *n-dɪ pa-kʊ-kola ii-bwe*
1SG-COP NCL16(LOC)-NCL15(INF)-grasp/hold NCL5-stone
'I am grasping a/the stone.' Persohn (2018:5-6)

He however notes that not all achievement-like verbs in Nyakyusa license co-occurrence with the progressive; the verb *-aga* 'find, encounter' does not license the progressive as shown in 17d below.

1. d **tʊ-lɪ pa-kw-aga bi-kʊ-lyɑ*
1PL-COP NCL16(LOC)-NCL15(INF)-find NCL2-PRS.IPFV-eat
(Intended: 'We are about to encounter that they are eating.')
- Persohn (2018:6)

So why do some achievement-like verbs license the progressive and others do not? Persohn (2018) claims this is an indication that the verbs which license the progressive encode a pre-culminative phase (aka coming-to-be phase).

One such diagnostic proposed by Persohn (2018) to identify verbs which encode a coming-to-be phase in Nyakyusa is a single-reading interpretation with the phasal verb *-anda* ‘begin, start’ as shown in (2) below.

2. (a) *um-oojo gw-angv bo gw-and-ile vku-fwa*
 NCL3-soul NCL3-POSS.1SG as NCL3-begin-PFV NCL15(INF)-die
n-dinku-ku-kumbuka vgw gwe N-TWA
 1SG-NARR-2SG-remember PRON.2SG PRON.2SG NCL1-lord
 ‘When my life was ebbing away (lit. My soul, when it had begun to die), I remembered you, LORD.’ (Jonah 2:7)

- (b) *and-ile vku-kalala*
 NCL1.begin-PFV NCL15(INF)-be(come)_angry
 1. ‘S/he has begun to get angry.’ (now)
 2. ‘S/he has begun to get angry (e.g., frequently)

- (c) *n-and-ile vku-kola iibwe*
 1SG-begin-PFV NCL15(INF)-grasp/hold NCL5-stone
 1. ‘I have begun to grasp a/the stone (now).’
 2. ‘I have begun to grasp a/the stone (e.g. frequently).

Examples (2b-c) show that the phasal verb in Nyakyusa is ambiguous between a single-event reading and a plurality of event reading. However, it is the single-reading interpretation that is of interest here. Not all verbs of this type license this reading as the verb *-aga* ‘find/encounter’ which does not license a single-event interpretation shows in (2d) below;

- 2 (d) *tw-and-ile vkw-aga bi-ku-lya*
 1PL-COP NCL15(INF)-find NCL2-PRS.IPFV-eat
 ‘We have begun to find them eating (e.g., each time we pass by their house).’
 not: ‘We have just begun to find them eating.’

Persohn (2018:7)

Indications that inchoatives (previously classified as achievements) lexicalize a resultant state phase comes from the co-occurrence of these verbs in a persistentive aspect³ + perfective construction. Consider the examples in 3 below.

Nyakyusa (Persohn 2018:8)

3. (a) *ii-kuuka* *li-kaali* *li-fw-ile*
 NCL5-store NCL5-PERS NCL5-die-PFV⁴
 'The store is still closed (lit. still dead).'
- (b) *a-kaali* *a-kaleele*
 NCL1-PERS NCL1-be(come)_angry.PFV
 'S/he is still angry.'
- (c) *n-gaali* *n-gol-ile* *ii-bwe*
 1SG-PERS 1SG-grasp/hold-PFV NCL5-stone
 'I am still holding a/the stone.'
4. Ndali (Botne 2008: 102)
li-kaali *li-bal-ite*
 NCL5-PERS NCL5-be(come)_bright-CMPL
 'It (sun) is still shining brightly.'

Not all Change of state verbs are acceptable in this frame as Persohn 2018 shows with the Nyakyusa verbs *-fika* 'arrive' and *-bifwa* 'ripen' in 5 below.

5. (a) * *a-kaali* *a-fik-ile*
 NCL1-PERS NCL1-die.PFV
 (intended: 'S/he is still present due to his/her arrival.')
- (b) * *ama-tooki* *ga-kaali* *ga-bifiifwe*
 NCL6-banana NCL6-PERS NCL6-ripen.PFV
 (intended: 'The bananas are still ripe.')
- Persohn (2018:8)

³ The persistentive aspect denotes that an event continues to hold from an earlier point until a later point (typically the moment of speech). It corresponds roughly to the adverbial 'still.'

⁴ Change of state verbs (aka inchoatives) have a present state reading when combined with perfective/completive morphology. Inchoatives will be discussed later in the paper.

In order to express a persistent state, other grammatical constructions such as an existential construction (6a) or a nominal predicate featuring verb-to-adjective derivation needs to be used.

6. Nyakyusa (Persohn 2018:8)

a-kaalɪ *a-li=po*
 NCL1-PERS NCL1-COP=NCL16(LOC)
 'S/he is still present'

According to Persohn (2018) this suggests that a resultant state is encoded in the lexical dimension, which is selected by the persistive aspectual operator. In other words, 'to die', 'to be(come) angry' or 'to grasp/hold' but not 'to arrive' or 'to ripen' lexicalize a resultant state in Nyakyusa. He further claims that the Vendlerian classification system does not predict these differences in the combinatory possibilities between these verbs and aspectual operators.

2.3.1.4.2 Accomplishments which lexicalize a resultant phase in Bantu.

Persohn (2018:12) points out that Bantu data suggests that the class of accomplishments is not a homogenous class. Some verbs in Nyakyusa (7b) such as *-fwala* 'dress, wear' and *-gaala* 'be(come drunk)' or Ndali (8) *-fuula* 'undress', typically receive a stative reading with the perfective aspect. The ability of the verbs to collocate with persistive aspect indicates that the resultant state is lexicalized in these verbs, as shown below.

Nyakyusa (Persohn 2018:12)

7. (a) *(a-kaalɪ)* *a-gaal-ile*
 NCL1-PERS NCL1-be(come)_drunk-PFV
 'S/he is (still) drunk.'
- (b) *(a-kaalɪ)* *a-fwele* *(ii-koti)*
 NCL1-PERS NCL1-dress/wear.PFV (NCL5-coat)
 'S/he is (still) dressed (wearing a/the coat).'

Ndali (Botne 2008: 99)

8. (a-kaalí) a-fuul-íte
NCL1-PERS NCL1-undress-PFV
'S/he is (still) undressed.'

Not all accomplishment-like verbs yield this interpretation in this context, as Persohn (2018) shows with the Nyakyusa verbs/VP *-talalɪla* 'cool (intr.)' or *-lya ɪnguku joosa* 'eat a whole chicken' below;

Nyakyusa (Persohn 2018:13)

9. (a) *ifi-ndʊ fi-kaalɪ fi-talaliile
NCL8-food NCL8-take-PERS NCL8-cool.PFV
(intended: 'The food is still cold.')
- (b) *a-kaalɪ a-l-iile ɪn-gʊkʊ j-ooosa
NCL1-PERS NCL1-eat-PFV NCL9-chicken NCL9-all
(intended: 'S/he is still full from eating a whole chicken.')

This data suggests a distinction within the class of accomplishments between those verbs which lexicalize a resultant phase (e.g. *-gaala* and *-fuula*) and those which do not (e.g., *alalɪla* 'cool (intr.)' or *-lya ɪnguku joosa*) and hence the need for a further sub-division of the class of accomplishments within Bantu.

2.3.1.4.3 Atelic accomplishments in some Bantu languages

One of the defining properties of accomplishments is that they are [+telic]. In other words, they have an inherent endpoint. Savić (2017) presents data from Xhosa to show that in this language, the boundedness of some accomplishments is more of an implicature than an entailment. Consider the example in (10) below.

- Xhosa
10. (a) ndi-fund-e le ncwadi
SP1SG-read-PFV.CJ PROX9 9.book
'I (have) read this book.'
- (b) Ndi-fund-e le ncwadi kodwa a-ndi-gqib-anga
SP1SG-read-PFV.CJ PROX9 9.book but NEG-SP1SG-finish-NEG.PFV
'I read (engaged myself in reading) this book, but I did not finish it.'
(Savić 2017: 66)

Example (10a) is a presentation of a typical accomplishment verb. It is telic because the event reaches its end-point when the book has been read. Example (10b) however shows that this temporal entailment (of the event reaching an endpoint) can be cancelled in Xhosa as the conjoined clause says otherwise (that the speaker did not finish reading the book and hence the event did not reach an endpoint).

Following work by (Talmy 2000) and Levin (2015), Martin et al. (2016) show how some accomplishments trigger an inference that the act described by the verb root affects the object at least partially. In some languages such as Xhosa, this inference is cancelable (11). It appears that agency plays an important role here; in (11a), with a fully agentive human subject, the inference is cancelable - allowing for an activity interpretation of the washing event. In (11b), however, with *imvula* 'rain' as the subject, the conjoined sentence was unanimously judged to be contradictory.

Xhosa (Crane and Persohn 2019:334)

11. (a) uSipho u-hlamb-e imoto yakhe, kodwa
 1A.Sipho SP1-wash-PFV.CJ 9.car 9.POSS1 but
 i-sa-ngcol-e njenga-ku-qal-a
 SP9-PRS-be(come)_dirty-PFV.CJ like-15(INF)-begin-FV
 'Sipho washed (engaged in washing) his car, but it is still as dirty as before (sic!).

- (b). #imvula i-hlamb-e indlela, kodwa
 9.rain SP9-wash-PFV.CJ 9.road but
 I-sa-ngcol-e njenga-ku-qal-a
 SP9-PRS-be(come)_dirty-PFV.CJ like-15(INF)-begin-FV

Intended: 'The rain washed the street but it is still as dirty as before (sic!)

Speaker comment (paraphrased): "If the street is as dirty as before then all the rain did was to rain." (Persohn fieldnotes).

2.3.1.4.4 The presence of Inchoative verbs in some languages

Inchoative verbs "serve to express a change of condition or location of the subject; many of them characterize the change or transition from one state to another" (Botne 1989:149). According to Polancec (2021:469), they are verbs which "lexically

encode a transformation”. They are also known as two-phase verbs because they encode both a preparatory phase and a resultant phase.

Membership of inchoatives is not always consistent across languages, thus lending credence to the call for a parametric approach to actionality. For example, in Wanga (Botne 2010: 46), the predicate *chin.ja* ‘carry’ is an inchoative predicate whereas its English translation equivalent is an activity.

The presence of inchoatives in a language also has implications for its grammatical system, For example, Nichols (2015:24) suggests that languages with basic inchoative forms tend to have restrictions on the adjective word-class as is the case in many Bantu languages.

Vendler classes are typically defined in terms of binary features which serve as primitives of the classification schema. For example, activities are argued to have the feature combination [- stative], [- telic], [- punctual] and [+ dynamic]. This analysis best suits accounting for ‘simple’ events i.e., events which encode only a phase or transformation but not both. As inchoatives encode both the change of state and the resulting state, the feature matrix is unable to account for inchoatives as an actional class.

2.3.2. Parametric approaches to actionality

The section also discusses a more recent parametric approach to verb classification based on the interaction between lexical aspect and grammatical aspect as advocated by Tatevosov (2002) and Botne and Kershner (2000).

2.3.2.1. Tatevosov

Two central points of Sergei Tatevosov's (ST henceforth) theory are bi-dimensionality and the central position of grammatical aspect (Tatevosov 2002a: 318). According to Sasse (2001:3),

Unidimensional approaches proceed from the assumption that there is only one set of aspect-relevant semantic primitives, a single conceptual dimension in terms of which aspectual phenomena on all representational levels can be analyzed and described ... By contrast, bidimensional approaches insist on the distinction of two such dimensions.

ST's theory of actionality is based on four genetically unrelated Eurasian languages; Russian, Bagwalal, Mari and Tatar. Beyond his 2002a publication, he has developed his theory in two recent accounts, i.e., Tatevosov (2015; 2016). Tatevosov's approach is primarily designed to implement cross linguistic comparison, thus making it one of a few theories suited for typological actionality.

Tatevosov's model is built around the interaction of two cross-linguistic (universal) aspect grams (perfective/PFV and imperfective/IPFV) and the varied temporal interpretations verbs receive when they combine with aspect grams. These interactions then serve as a criterion for categorizing predicates into actional classes.

Tatevosov posits five universal meanings: states, processes, entry into states, entry into processes and multiplicatives. A state is a situation that does not involve any change over time (Dik 1994, De Groot 1995: 33) or does not constantly require a new input of energy to continue (Comrie 1976: 49). Processes involve change over time and at each moment require a new input of energy to continue (Comrie 1976). Entry into a state is a label assigned "whenever a situation referred to has attained its resultant

state” Tatevosov (2002a:330). The label entry-into-a-process is assigned if “a sentence refers to a situation that terminates producing a new situation. The only difference is that ‘a new situation’ is not a state, but a process” Tatevosov (2002a:331). Finally, Multiplicative refers to situations that repeat many times with the same participants and occupy a single time span. These actional meanings are considered universal, cross-linguistically relevant and taken as primitives (p. 334).

The aspect grams PFV and IPFV are each associated with particular actional meanings. Verbs differ with respect to actional construals ‘generated’ by aspect grams. The interpretations which this interaction yields are then grouped into two sets: one for the perfective and the other for the imperfective. The two sets form an ordered pair which constitutes the actional characteristic of a verb or predicate.; a set of verbs with identical actional characteristics constitute an actional class (Arkadiev 2009: 59).

As an illustration, consider a subset of verb classification from Mari (Uralic);

Representative of Class	Actional meanings in the PFV	Actional meanings in the IPFV	Actional Characteristic
užaš ‘see’	entry into a state (ES), state (S)	state (S)	$\langle \{ES, S\}, S \rangle$
purlaš ‘bite’	entry into a state (ES)	state (S)	$\langle ES, S \rangle$
kijaš ‘lie’	state (S)	state (S)	$\langle S, S \rangle$

Figure 2-2. Actional characteristics of the three Mari actional classes adapted from Polanec (2017)

In figure 2-2 above, the verb *užaš* 'see' in the PFV has two possible interpretations, 'saw' (S) and 'caught sight' (ES), whereas in the IPFV it means 'sees' (S). The verb *purlaš* 'bite' in the PFV means 'bit (ES)', while in the context of the IPFV it means 'holds in teeth' - it cannot mean 'held in teeth (S)' in the PFV like *užaš* 'see'. The verb *kijaš* 'to lie' means 'lay (= was in a horizontal position)' in the PFV and 'lies' in the IPFV. It differs from the former two verbs by the absence of the ES meaning – it cannot mean 'lay down (i.e., moved into a horizontal position)'.

An actional characteristic is defined as a pair of sets, e.g., <ES, S> for *purlaš* 'bite'. The first member of the set is the actional meaning based on the PFV gram and the second applies to the IPFV gram. The pair is enclosed in angle brackets and each member is separated by a comma. It is possible for both sets to contain more than one element. For example, in Table 1, the verb *užaš* 'see' allows for two meanings in the context of the PFV form (state – S, and entry into a state – ES).

With respect to the methodology of choosing verbs on which actional classification will be based, ST advocates using a sample of 100 verb meanings selected from different thematic groups: being and possession, motion, physical processes and changes, physiological states and processes, labor, and everyday life, speech and sound production, perception, emotions, intellectual activity, phasal and modal verbs.

Based on St's observation of actional properties across different languages, he differentiates between classes which are peculiar to a language/language family versus those that cross-linguistically attested; he refers to the latter as crosslinguistic actional

types (CLATs) - a parallel to the term crosslinguistic gram types of Bybee and Dahl (1989). He argues that “crosslinguistic actional types should be viewed as a generalization over the actional systems of **individual languages**⁵, and not as semantic primitives” (Tatevosov 2002a:324). There are ten proposed CLATs, which are given in below.

- (i) Stative <**{state}**, **{state}**>
- (ii) Atelic <**{process}**, **{process}**>
- (iii) Strong telic <**{entry into a state}**, **{process}**>
- (iv) Weak telic <**{entry into a state, process}**, **{process}**>
- (v) Punctual <**{entry into a state}**, **{n.a}**>
- (vi) Strong inceptive-stative <**{entry into a state}**, **{state}**>
- (vii) Weak inceptive-stative <**{entry into a state, state}**, **{state}**>
- (viii) Strong ingressive-atelic <**{entry into a process}**, **{process}**>
- (ix) Weak ingressive-atelic <**{entry into a process, process}**, **{process}**>
- (x) Multiplicative <**{multiplicative process, entry into a state}**, **{multiplicative process}**>

There are many more CLATs than Vendlerian classes, which indicates that the traditional Vendlerian classification is insufficient and cannot capture the existing crosslinguistic variation in actionality.

One of the implications of Tatevosov’s approach is that classes are expected to be subject to variation i.e., languages will parameterize actional classes. In addition, translational equivalent predicates in different languages will be subject to variation.

⁵ Emphasis is mine.

One other innovation of ST's approach as pointed out by Plungjan (2011: 119), is that in Tatevosov's proposal, the actionality of a predicate is determined at the lexical tier unlike most other approaches to actionality (including Vendler's) which are based on determining the actional character of a word-form of the predicate in a context; which then determines the actional class of the predicate. In contrast, ST's approach involves integrating the actional meaning of multiple grammatical (aspectual) forms of the same predicate in a single characterization, on which the actional class is subsequently based. In other words, "the actional class of the predicates is defined not on the level of the predicate in context, but rather as a sum of actional meanings available to the predicate in various contexts" (Polanec 2017).

ST's approach differs from those of many formal approaches to actionality in English in the sense that there is no "basic" form, upon which the actional class is derived. Within these approaches, the actional character of the simple past is considered the 'basic' form while that of the progressive is considered derived. The traditional approach to classification is referred to as context-based while Tatevosov's approach is sense-based.

This model has been tested a diverse set of languages including Eurasian languages such as Russian, Mari (Uralic), Bagvalal (Nakh-Dagestania), three Turkic languages – Karachay-Balkar, Tatar and Tuvan, Adyghe (Arkadiev 2009), Lithuanian (Arkadiev 2011), Tundra Nenets (Khanina 2008), Nanai (Oskolskaya 2017).

2.3.2.2. Botne and Kershner

Botne & Kershner (2000) built on the work of Freed (1979) to propose an actional classification of verbs based on the phases encoded by verbs. These phases are an

initial/inceptive phase (onset), a middle phase (nucleus) and a final phase (coda). The nucleus phase determines the actional character of the verb.

Within this framework all events have a nucleus while the other two phases (onset and coda) are optional. Verbs are therefore classified based on the phase(s) encoded in verbs as identified by diagnostics such as their interpretation when they co-occur with grammatical aspect, temporal adverbs and phasal verbs.

Botne and Kershner apply this classification scheme to Zulu (Bantu S.42) to classify verbs in the language into two broad categories - Inchoatives and non-inchoatives. Inchoatives (Vendler's achievement) are characterized as encoding a punctual nucleus in addition to an obligatory coda (a result phase). Non-inchoatives on the other hand, possess a durative nucleus in addition to an optional onset or coda.

Based on this model, (Botne 2003; 2008; 2010) sub-classifies Vendlerian achievements into four sub-classes viz. Acute achievements, inceptive achievements, transitional achievements and resultative achievements. All four subclasses share the property of having a durative nucleus but differ with respect to whether they encode an onset or a nucleus.

Within this approach to verb classification, Vendlerian activity verbs are characterized as having a durative nucleus while accomplishment verbs encode a durative nucleus plus coda phase. Based on evidence from Bantu, accomplishment verbs are further subdivided into two classes: single accomplishments and transitional accomplishments. Single accomplishments encode a punctual coda (hence have culmination) while transitional accomplishments encode a durative coda plus result state. Botne proposes that within this schema, states have no internal structure.

This framework has been adopted in the actional classification of several Bantu languages including Seidel (2008) for Yeyi, Kershner (2002) for Sukwa, Crane (2011, 2013) for Totela, Persohn (2017b) for Nyakusa, Lusekelo (2016) for Swahili and Gunnick (2018) for Fwe. These studies share similarity with Botne's works with respect to accounting for actional classes in terms of the phases encoded by verbs and the phasal structure proposed for actional classes. However, some notable modifications to Botne and Kershner's (2000) schema include Kershner's (2002) proposal to subclassify activity verbs in Sukwa based on the duration of the nucleus into extended duratives (with a longer duration), instantaneous duratives, which have a shorter duration, and periodic duratives which have a regular cycle. Seidel (2008) shows that inceptive achievements are not attested in Yeyi while Persohn (2017b) argues that stative verbs are unattested in Nyakyusa because there is no diagnostic to distinguish them from change-of-state verbs. Crane (2011, 2013) argues that although statives are attested in Totela, they should be analyzed as having a durative nucleus instead of as lacking internal structure.

The evidence above once again points to the need for a parametric approach to actionality as non-parametric approaches are too generic to 'handle' the complexities of actionality across languages.

2.4. Temporal marking in Niger-Congo

2.4.1 Temporal marking in Bantu

In this section, I highlight the peculiarities of the Bantu temporal marking system. It was asserted in the previous chapter that within Niger-Congo, there are similarities and differences in the temporal marking systems of Bantu and non-Bantu languages. The purpose of undertaking this comparative and contrastive task is to identify the

temporal marking features that are responsible for the similarities and differences in their actional systems. Some temporal features that distinguish Bantu languages from non-Bantu languages include.

(i) Bantu languages are morphologically synthetic having a tendency towards inflectional grammatical expression rather than a lexical or syntactic expression of grammatical categories. Non-Bantu Niger-Congo languages on the other hand are mostly analytical languages expressing grammatical categories with grammatical tone, lexical items, and syntax.

(ii) Bantu languages make fine-grained distinctions within several time divisions (especially with respect to the past and future). According to Nurse (2008: 22), more than 80% of Bantu languages have more than one past category, over 70% have two or three past tenses, 10% have four pasts and 17% have a single past. With respect to future tense, 56% have one or no futures, 41% have two or three while a very small handful have four or five future tenses.

(iii) Formal expression of the distinction between itive and ventive categories: The itive category encodes action away from the speaker while ventive is used to encode action towards the speaker. Many Bantu languages encode itive as an inflectional category in the verb in the form of (*-ka) while a smaller number encode ventive.

(iv) The presence of anterior aspect is marked suffixally: About 66% of Bantu languages mark anterior aspect (aka perfect) with the suffix '-ile' (Nurse 2008:24). Some non-Bantu languages do not have the anterior and even when they do, they are nearly always marked analytically.

(v) The presence of an inflectional persistive aspect: The persistive aspect is used to encode situations which held at some point (typically in the past) and holds later (typically at utterance time). In European and some Bantu languages, this is expressed with an adverbial in the context of imperfective aspect e.g., English ‘still’, German ‘noch (immer)’, French ‘toujours’. However, in many Bantu languages, the persistive is expressed inflectionally, often as *-ki- (Nurse 2008:24).

(vi) The presence of narrative tense: Many Bantu languages attest the affix -ka- whose main (but not only) function is to show that an event or chain of events follow a preceding event.

(vii) Difference in temporal marking systems: The temporal marking system of Bantu languages can generally be characterized as consisting of both tense and aspect markers whereas most non-Bantu languages can best be analyzed in terms of aspect alone (Nurse 2018:13).

(viii) The presence of the factative: The factative is peculiar to non-Bantu Niger-Congo languages and was first identified in Welmers (1973: 346). It has a past, complete interpretation with non-stative predicates but produces a current, non-past, incomplete interpretation with states.

2.4.2 Temporal marking in Edo

2.4.2.1 Previous Studies

The tense/aspect system of Edo has always been difficult to characterize. Dunn (1968:216) writes in the first introductory grammar of the language: “the verbal system in Bini⁶ is an intricate one, having the composition of tense, aspect and modality. The

⁶ Bini is an alternative name for Edo introduced by colonialists. It is no longer in use as it is considered foreign and reminiscent of the colonial era.

verbal system basically has two tenses, past and non-past; three aspects, perfective, progressive and habitual; and at least six modals”. The complications in accounting for the tense/aspect system of Edo are reechoed in a contemporary account of temporal marking in the language by Yuka and Omoregbe (2011:1) when they say that the “specification of temporal distance in the language is more complex than has been recognized by previous studies”.

In the rest of this section, I present the analyses of temporal marking in Edo as proposed by different authors with the goal of highlighting the disagreements in accounting for tense/aspect phenomenon in Edo.

2.4.2.1.1 Dunn 1968

Dunn (1968:6) argues that Edo has both tense and aspect which are marked by particles and tone. He claims that in some clauses, tense combines with aspect in an implicit manner. He identifies the following categories with the temporal marking system of the language; habitual, present, past complete, past continuous/progressive, progressive, past tense and present continuous - the future is marked by a modal. A summary of the categories proposed by Dunn and what they are marked with is given in the table below⁷;

Category	Marker	Example
Habitual	Low tone on the verb	<i>í miè ọ̀rẹ̀n ẹ̀ghẹ̀ hiá</i> 1.SG. see.HAB 3.SG time all 'I see him always.'

⁷ Examples are stated as in Dunn (1968)

Past complete	High tone on first syllable of the verb	Èdó í kéré Edo 1.SG come.from. PST COMP 'I come from Edo'
Past Prog.	ghara	í ghàrà tiè èbé 1.SG PST.PROG read book 'I was reading a book'
Progressive	ghá	_____
Past tense	-rv ⁸ suffix	Àmè rhò-rè òdè water be-PST yesterday 'It rained yesterday'
Present. continuous	Low tone (CV verbs) Low-High (CVCV/CVV)verbs High-Low 'Stative verbs'	í múdià 1.SG stand 'I am standing'
Perfective	nè	i họn nè 1.SG hear PFV 'I have heard'
Past perfective	High tone V + nè	ì tié èbé nè 1.SG read.PST book PFV 'I have read (a book)'
Future	ghá	ì ghá riè èvbàré 1.SG FUT eat food 'I will eat'

⁸ The Edo -rv suffix is a verbal suffix made up of /r/ (The voiced alveolar approximant) and a phonologically conditioned vowel which depends on the form of the last vowel of the verb stem (Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ 2012)

Figure 2.1. A summary of Dunn's (1968) analysis of temporal markers in Edo

I would like to note at this point that Dunn's definitions for some of these categories are inconsistent with traditional definitions of tense/aspect categories. For example, he defines the past completive as a marker for an action or prediction completed in the past with no relevance for the future (a definition which mostly resembles that of simple past tense). The question at this point is (based on the definition provided) how does this marker differ from the past tense? He also defines the past perfective as a marker used to refer to an action which has been completed in the past, which has relevance to the present situation - a definition typically attributed to the present perfect.

2.4.2.1.2 Omoruyi (1991)

Omoruyi (1991:2) argues that "whereas simple past or completive tense is commonly marked by verbal inflections and tonal changes, aspect and modality are marked by the occurrence of auxiliaries". According to him, the simple past tense is marked by the -rV suffix, for example.

12. (a) *íghó wí-rì*
money lose-PST
'The money was lost'

(b) *Èwé wú-rù*
goat die-PST
'The goat died'

Omoruyi (1991:2)

He claims that the past tense suffixes basically refer to a completed action or state in relation to the time of the utterance (Omoruyi 1991:3) - giving an aspectual definition to a tense label. In the same vein, he asserts that "if an Edo verb (especially a monosyllabic verb) expresses the non-past, it bears a low tone but when it expresses

the past tense, the tone changes to high” (Omoruyi 1991:4). This assertion by Omoruyi (1991) raises the question as to what exactly marks the past tense; The -rV suffix or the high tone?

Another discrepancy in Omoruyi’s account of tense and aspect in Edo is his definition of past tense. He claims that “the past tense expresses actions or events which have been completed ... the non-past tense usually expresses actions and events whose occurrences are habitual, customary or which are ongoing” (Omoruyi 1991:4)”. It appears that his definition of the past tense is that of the completive aspect.

Like Dunn (1968), Omoruyi (1991) claims that Edo has both tense and aspect. He claims that the perfective is marked by *nẹ* which he glosses as ‘already’. He goes on to say the verb in such constructions bears a high tone because the action expressed is in the past. Omoruyi illustrates the perfective aspect with the example below.

13. *Òzó rrí èvbàré nẹ*
Ozo eat.PST food already
'Ozo has eaten'

This example raises suspicion because the so-called perfective marker is glossed as an adverb ‘already’ and secondly, the free translation of the sentence is in the present perfect which is atypical of perfective markers.

2.4.2.1.3 Yuka and Omoregbe (2008)

Yuka and Omoregbe (2008) argue in favor of a tense and aspect system for Edo. They propose that Edo makes a distinction between present, past and future tenses. Past tense is marked by the -rV suffix. For example.

14. (a) *gbè – gbéré* => dance - danced
(b) *gbà – gbàré* => tie - tied
(c) *fi – fíri* => throw – threw

Yuka and Omoregbe (2008:10)

One criticism against the data presented in their analysis is that they did not provide sentential data or the contexts in which the data was elicited. Like Omoruyi (1991), they claim that the past tense is marked by both the -rV suffix and a high tone on the verb (Yuka and Omoregbe 2008:123).

According to their analysis, the low tone on CV verbs and low-low tone pattern on transitive CVCV/CVV verbs mark present tense. Intransitive CVCV/CVV verbs have a low-high tonal pattern.

With respect to aspect, they argue that Edo language makes a distinction between perfective and imperfective aspect; perfective aspect is marked by *nè* while imperfective aspect is marked by *né* - once again the particle is glossed as the adverb 'already'. It might be reasonable to hypothesize at this point that *ne* is a temporal adverb and not an aspectual marker as it appears in both perfective and imperfective constructions.

15. (a) *ò lè èvbàré né*
 he pres-cook food prog-already
 'He is already cooking food'

(b) *ò lé èvbàré nè*
 he pst-cook food non-prog-already
 'He has already cooked food'

Yuka and Omoregbe (2008:128)

This section has shown the disagreements in the accounts of several authors in accounting for temporal marking in Edo. The sources of disagreements are (i) Does Edo employ a tense or aspect system; or both (ii) what does each of the temporal markers encode and what marks each temporal category.

2.4.2.1.4 Current proposals

In chapter 4, I make the following proposals.

- a. The high tone marks the factative (default aspect).

- b. The low tone marks the imperfective aspect.
- c. Nẹ is a phasal polarity item which literally translates to 'already'.
- d. The -rV suffix marks completive aspect.

CHAPTER 3 A SKETCH GRAMMAR OF ẸDO

3.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses aspects of Ẹdo grammar relevant to understanding the data presented with respect to the aspectual specification and actional classification of verbs in the Ẹdo language. It presents and synthesizes previous studies in Ẹdo required to seamlessly navigate the data presentation and analyses in chapters 4 (where I discuss temporal marking in Ẹdo) and chapter 5 (where I discuss the actional tests used to diagnose verb classes in the language). The sections of this chapter discuss Ẹdo phonology in section 3.2, Ẹdo nominal morphology in 3.3. Section 3.4 addresses Ẹdo morphosyntax and section 3.5 summarizes and concludes the chapter.

3.2 Basic Phonology Ẹdo

This section discusses the sound system of Ẹdo including its phonemes, tone system, syllable structure, phonological rules, tonemic rules and orthographic conventions adopted in this study. The discussion is built on the work of Omozuwa (2010), who has done extensive research in the phonetics and phonology of the Ẹdo language.

3.2.1 The Ẹdo sound system

3.2.1.1 Ẹdo vowels

Omozuwa (2010:164) proposes that “Ẹdo has seven oral and five nasal vowels: [i, e, ε, a, u, o, ɔ, ɪ, ẽ, ã, ũ and ɔ̃] i.e., a total of twelve vowels. The twelve vowels are phonemic since they contrast in minimal pairs of words”. He provides the following minimal pairs as evidence for the phonemic status of these vowels.

1. (a) /i/ vs /e/

[fi] fi ‘play’ vs [fè] fè ‘be cured/be rich’

[si] si ‘pull/smoke’ vs [sè] sè ‘sew’

- (b) /e/ vs /ɛ/
 [dè] dè 'fall' vs [dɛ] dɛ 'buy'
 [èdɛ́] èdɛ́ 'grey hair' vs [èdɛ́] èdɛ́ 'day'
- (c) /ɛ/ vs /a/
 [ùvè] ùvè 'bone' vs [ùvà] ùvà 'shared portion of meat'
 [jɛ́] yèɛ́ 'admire' vs [jǎ] yàá 'go and ...'
- (d) /i/ vs /u/
 [sì] sì 'pull' vs [sù] sù 'accompany'
 [fì] fì 'throw/shoot' vs [fù] fù 'be calm'
- (e) /u/ vs /o/
 [rù] rù 'do' vs [rò] 'to be cheap'
 [sù] sù 'accompany' vs [sò] sò 'shout'
- (f) /o/ vs /ɔ/
 [òhá] òhá 'bush' vs [òhá] òhá 'bride'
 [kpòlò] kpòlò 'sweep' vs [kpòlò] kpòlò 'be big'
- (g) /e/ vs /o/
 [fè] fè 'be rich' vs [fǒ] fòó 'exhaust'
 [èsó] èsó 'some' vs [ósó] ósó 'evil spirit'
- (h) /ɛ/ vs /ɔ/
 [tè] tè 'rebel (vb)' vs [tò] tò 'to live long'
 [xɛ́] khèɛ́ 'wait for' vs [xǒ] khòɔ́ 'be strict'
- Ọmọzuwa (2010:164-167)

He also provides the following evidence in (2) as evidence for the presence of phonemic nasal vowels (as against nasalized vowels)

- 2 (a) /i/ vs /ĩ/
 [sì] sì 'crawl/smoke (vb)' vs [sĩ] sìn 'filter'
 [ìkí] ìkí 'a coil' vs [ĩkí] ìkín 'loin'
- (b) /ɛ/ vs /ɛ̃/
 [vè] vè 'belch' vs [vɛ̃] vèn 'wrestle'
 [ihé] ihé 'load' vs [ihɛ̃] ihèn 'a curse'
- (c) /a/ vs /ã/
 [tà] tà 'say/tell' vs [tã] tàn 'tall'
 [dà] dà 'drink (wine)' vs [dã] dàn 'hop'
- (d) /u/ vs /ũ/
 [ù] ù 'be' vs [ũ] ùn 'be' (verb)

[sù] sù ‘accompany’ vs [sũ] sùn ‘tough/well grounded’
[bũ] bùú ‘meet (someone)’ vs [bũ] bùún ‘break’

(e) /ɔ/ vs /õ/

[kò] kò ‘plant’ vs [kõ] kòn ‘be stupid’
[hõ] hòò ‘wash’ vs [hõ] hòón ‘build up wealth’

Ọmọzuwa (2010:167-

168)

3.2.1.2 Edo consonants

Edo has twenty-seven (27) consonants: twenty-two oral consonants and five nasal consonants. The oral consonants can be subdivided into eight stops /p, b, t, d, k, g, kp̄, gb̄/ (Edo has a symmetrical stop system), ten fricatives /f, v, s, z, x, ɣ, h, j, w, β/, three rhotics /r, ɾ, ɻ/ and one lateral stop /l/. The five nasal consonants in Edo are /m, n, ŋw, ŋ, m̄/. Evidence for the phonemic status of these sounds is provided by the minimal pairs in (3) below.

3 (a) Stops

/p/ vs /b/ => [pjě] piẹn ‘press’ vs [bjě] biẹn ‘slice’
/t/ vs /d/ => [tĩ] tìn ‘fly (verb)’ vs [dĩ] dìn ‘be brave’
/k/ vs /g/ => [kà] kà ‘count’ vs [gà] gà ‘serve’
/kp̄/ vs /gb̄/ => [kpè] kpè ‘wash’ vs [gbè] gbè ‘dance/kill’

(b) Fricatives

/f/ vs /v/ => [òfě] òfẹn ‘rat’ vs [òvě] òvẹn ‘sun’
/s/ vs /z/ => [sè] sè ‘sew’ vs [zè] zè ‘be hard’
/x/ vs /ɣ/ => [xǎ] khàá ‘say’ vs [ɣǎ] ghàá ‘share’
/x/ vs /h/ => [àxé] àkhé ‘pot’ vs [áhé] áhé ‘path in a farm’

Ọmọzuwa (2010: 170-173)

The phonemic sounds, description and orthographic representations are presented in tables 1 and 2 for vowels and consonants respectively below.

Phonetic symbol	Phonetic description	Orthographic representation
/i/	Close-front unrounded vowel	‘i’
/e/	Close-mid unrounded vowel	‘e’
/ɛ/	Open-mid unrounded vowel	‘ẹ’
/a/	Open-back unrounded vowel	‘a’
/u/	Close-back rounded vowel	‘u’
/ɔ/	Open-mid back rounded vowel	‘o’
/o/	Close-mid back rounded vowel	‘o’
/ĩ/	Close-front unrounded nasal vowel	‘in’
/ẽ/	Open-mid unrounded nasal vowel	‘en’
/ã/	Open-back unrounded nasal vowel	‘an’
/ũ/	Close-back rounded nasal vowel	‘un’
/õ/	Open-mid back rounded nasal vowel	‘on’

Figure 3-1 Edo phonemic vowels

Phonetic symbol	Phonetic description	Orthographic representation
/p/	Voiceless bilabial stop	‘p’
/b/	Voiced bilabial stop	‘b’
/t/	Voiceless alveolar stop	‘t’
/d/	Voiced alveolar stop	‘d’
/k/	Voiceless velar stop	‘k’
/g/	Voiced velar stop	‘g’
/kp/	Voiceless labial-velar stop	‘kp’
/gb/	Voiced labial-velar stop	‘gb’
/β/	Voiced bilabial fricative	‘vb’
/f/	Voiceless labio-dental fricative	‘f’
/v/	Voiced labio-dental fricative	‘v’
/s/	Voiceless alveolar fricative	‘s’
/z/	Voiced alveolar fricative	‘z’
/x/	Voiceless velar fricative	‘kh’

/ɣ/	Voiced velar fricative	'gh'
/l/	Voiced alveolar lateral	'l'
/h/	Voiceless glottal fricative	'h'
/r/	Voiced alveolar trill	'rr'
/ɾ/	Voiceless alveolar trill	'rh'
/ɹ/	Voiced lateral approximant	'r'
/j/	Voiced palatal glide	'y'
/w/	Voiced velar glide	'w'
/m/	Bilabial nasal	'm'
/n/	Alveolar nasal	'n'
/m̥/	Labio-dental nasal	'mw'
/ŋw/	Labial-velar nasal	'nw'
/ɲ/	Palatal nasal	'ny'

Figure 3-2: Edo phonemic consonants

3.2.2 Phonological Processes

There are several phonological processes which explains the discrepancy between the phonemic level (underlying representation which reflects the knowledge of native speakers) and the phonetic level (surface representation which reflects the observed speech patterns of native speakers. The proposals and examples are taken from Omozuwa (2010:206-246). The phonological processes attested in Edo are,

(i) Nasal assimilation: Nasal assimilation is the 'spread' of nasality from an inherent nasal segment to an oral segment, thus causing the oral segment to bear some nasality. There are two types of nasal assimilation – progressive and regressive. The former involves the spread of nasality to a following segment while the latter involves spread of nasality to a preceding segment. Examples of progressive nasal assimilation in Edo are presented in (4) while examples of regressive nasal assimilation are presented in (5).

4 (a) /ómí/ → [ómí̃] ‘yam (species)’

(b) /ùnù/ → [ùnù̃] ‘mouth’

(c) /àṛó/ → [àṛó̃] ‘wine’

(d) /èṅwé/ → [èṅwé̃] ‘breast’

(e) /òṃémé/ → [òṃémé̃]

Ọmọzuwa (2010:206-207)

Example (4) shows that all Ẹdo nasal consonants can spread the nasal feature to any oral vowel. In the case of regressive nasal assimilation, an oral sound segment is nasalized in anticipation of the production of a nasal consonant. According to Ọmọzuwa (2012:207), “instances of regressive nasal assimilation occur only when the alveolar lateral approximant [ɹ] precedes any of the five inherent nasal vowels ...” as illustrated with example (5)

5 (a) /íṣṣí/ → [íṣṣí̃] ‘beg’

(b) /òṣṣí/ → [òṣṣí̃] ‘marriage’

(c) /àṣṣí/ → [àṣṣí̃] ‘animal/meat’

(d) /òṣṣí/ → [òṣṣí̃] ‘a scholar’

(e) /óṣṣí/ → [óṣṣí̃] ‘plum/pear’

Omozuwa (1993) provides acoustic evidence to show that the only Ẹdo consonant that can be regressively nasalized is the alveolar lateral approximant [ɹ] contrary to the claim in Amayo and Elugbe (1986), that Ẹdo orals stops preceding a nasal vowel are released with nasal plosion.

(ii) Vowel elision: Vowel elision is the deletion of an underlying vowel in certain contexts. Ẹdo is an open syllable language (i.e., all words begin and end in a vowel) and in addition does not permit word-initial nasal vowels. Hence, when two words are used sequentially in an utterance, it is inevitable that two vowels co-occur across word boundary. In this context, V1 (the vowel before the boundary, i.e., the last vowel of the

friend # POSS # Óbá (king) 'Óba's friend'

(iv) Consonant deletion: According to Ọmọzuwa (2010:227-231), there are three contexts in which consonant deletion occurs in the Edo language viz. the deletion of lax consonants, deletion of /m/ and /ŋ/ in tri/poly-syllabic nouns and consonant deletion in reduplicative formatives. All the examples presented to demonstrate this phenomenon are taken from Ọmọzuwa (2010:227-231).

(a) Deletion of lax consonants

The deletion of lax consonants [ɹ] (the voiced alveolar lateral approximant) and [h] (the voiceless glottal fricative) in rapid speech. This is exemplified in (9) below.

9 (a) /àɹò/ => [àò] 'eye'

(b) /ìɹò/ => [ìò] 'thought'

(c) /ùí/ => [ùí] 'two hundred'

(d) /òkàò/ => [òkàò]

Examples of the deletion of the voiceless glottal fricative in rapid speech is shown in (10)

10 (a) /èhá/ => [ea] 'three'

(b) /ihà/ => [ià] 'divination'

(c) /òhóyè/ => [òóyè] 'lie (n)'

h-deletion is blocked when both [h] and [ɹ] occur in the same word with three or more syllables (whether contiguous or not). In this context [ɹ] is deleted since it is weaker than [h] as shown in (11)

11 (a) /ihò.ì/ => [ihòì] 'nothing'

(b) /úhá.ò/ => [úháò] 'forehead'

(c) /óhió.ò/ = [óhjólò] 'loneliness'

(b) Deletion of /m/ and /ŋ/ in tri/poly-syllabic nouns

These nasals are deleted when they occur in tri/poly-syllabic nouns and the adjacent vowels following the deletion of the consonant are identical. It is also to be noted that these consonants are not attested in the C1 position in this context, except where C1 and C2 are identical, in which case C1 is deleted. Examples illustrating the deletion of /m/ and [ɱ] are presented in (12).

- 12 (a) /ùhúmǹù/ => [ùhúù] ‘head’
 (b) /ùxùmǹù/ => [ùxùù] ‘medicine’
 (c) /èkpàmákú/ => [èkpàá!kú] ‘iron roof sheets’

(c) Consonant deletion in reduplicative formatives in Èdo

Following Abimbola and Oyelaran (1975: 45), Omozuwa (2021:230) defines reduplicative formatives as “formatives with a sequence of two identical non-syllabic segments each followed by single identical vowels”. In Èdo words with a $V_1C_1V_2C_2V_3(C_3V_4)$ sequence, where $C_1 \equiv C_2 \neq C_3$ and $V_2 \equiv V_3$, or where $C_2 \equiv C_3 \neq C_1$ and $V_3 \equiv V_4$, the first of the identical consonants (i.e., C_1) is deleted in rapid speech as shown in (13).

- 13 (a) /ósísí/ => [óísí] ‘gun’
 (b) /óbóbò/ => [óóbò] ‘flower’
 (c) /égógó/ => [éógó] ‘bell/gong’
 (d) /èkpékpéjé/ => [èékpéjé] ‘duck’
 (e) /élélégúmàzà/ => [éélegúmàzà] ‘hunch back’

3.2.3 Tone system

3.2.3.1 Tonemes

According to Omozuwa (2010:173), “Èdo contrasts two tonemes, Low and High in the nominal class, and two tonemes Low and Rising in the verbal class. The two basic tones on nouns in the language form four tonal patterns in disyllabic nouns of the

VCV type as follows: $\acute{V}C\grave{V}$, $\acute{V}C\acute{V}$, $\acute{V}C\acute{V}$ and $\acute{V}C\grave{V}$ ". He presents the following tonal minimal pairs as evidence for the claim. Examples are taken from Omozuwa (2021:173-177)

14 (a) Low-Low vs High-High

/iḡò/ iḡhò 'horn' vs /iḡó/ iḡhó 'money'

/òwè/ òwè 'leg' vs /ówé/ ówé 'broom'

(b) Low-Low vs Low-High

/òkò/ òkò 'parcel' vs /òkó/ òkó 'nest'

/èvè/ èvè 'hernia' vs /èvé/ èvé 'weeping'

(c) High-High vs Low-High

/úgú/ úgú 'name of a clan' vs /ùgú/ ùgú 'vulture'

/òtḗ/ òtḗn 'juice' vs /òtḗ/ òtḗn 'a relation'

(d) High-High vs High-Low

/óló/ ólò 'grinding stone' vs /ólò/ => [ólò] ólò 'witch'

/úbí/ úbí 'a historical personality' vs /úbì/ => [úbì] úbí 'a slap'

(e) Low-High vs High-Low

/òhá/ òhá 'bush' vs /óhà/ => [òhâ] óhà 'big needle'

/àkó/ àkó 'portion' vs /ákò/ => [ákò] àkò 'pepper fruit'

Examples of monosyllabic verbs in which the low and rising tones contrast are shown in (15)

15 (a) /dè/ dè 'fall' vs /dḗ/ dḗé 'tie'

(b) /gbè/ gbè 'kill/dance' vs /gbḗ/ gbḗé 'cross'

(c) /tà/ tà 'say' vs /tǎ/ tǎá 'imitate'

3.2.3.2 Tonal processes

Based on acoustic evidence, Ọmọzuwa (2010:246) makes a distinction between vertical tonal assimilation and horizontal tonal assimilation.

Vertical tonal assimilation is attested in disyllabic words where a low tone immediately preceding a high tone affects the high tone by ‘reducing’ the pitch of the high tone in question. He proposes that such high tones which have been ‘pulled down’ are still perceived as high tones. This leads to the tonal process known as downdrift, defined as “a successive lowering of Highs after lows in contiguous syllables” (Ọmọzuwa 2010:246). The following tonal rules were proposed to account for tone realization and vertical tonal assimilation.

- i. A sequence of high tones without intervening low tones is realized on the same pitch level.
- ii. A sequence of low tones (with or without intervening high tones) drifts down in pitch.
- iii. A high tone preceded by a low tone in $\dot{V}CV$ words (e.g., *èbé* ‘book/leaf’) drifts down in pitch.
- iv. A high tone immediately followed by a low tone is realized as a falling tone in Edo.

Horizontal tonal assimilation, also known as downstep is a tonal process where a high tone is lowered following three ordered phonological processes viz downdrift, vowel elision and tone shift. This process occurs only in the context of $VCV \# (\acute{o}ghé) \# VCV$ formatives and the tonal combination across word-boundary is High (H) # Low (L). Other tonal combinations across word boundary do not result in downstep. This is exemplified in example (16).

16 (a) /úwé # òwá/ => [ùwó!wá]
inside house ‘inside the house’

- (b) /úwé # ówá/ => [úwówá]
 inside stall => 'inside the stall'

In example (16a) the downstepped high tone [ó!] is derived as follows. First, /e/ undergoes downdrift (because it is followed by a low tone syllable as a sequence of high tones with an intervening low tone), the next phase of the process is the elision of /e/ and lastly, the surviving tone of the elided vowel shifts to /o/. There is no down step process in (16b) because the tones across word-boundary (HH) do not provide the context for downstep as it blocks the first phase (downdrift) of the downstep process.

3.3 Nominal morphology

In this section, I discuss aspects of the nominal system of the Edo language required to understand the data presented in this work. In subsection 3.3.1, I present and discuss the Edo pronominal system and 3.3.2 is concerned with the number marking system in Edo.

The information and data provided in this section on the Edo NP is derived from Uchihara (2010) and Omoregbe & Aigbedo (2012) which are studies on the pronominal system of Edo.

The Edo NP is made up of an obligatory noun and pre/post nominal modifiers. The attested structural patterns in the NP are presented in (17).

- 17 (a) Determiner + Noun => né ágá 'the chair'
 DET chair

- (b) Noun + Determiner => òkpiá nà 'this man'
 man DEM

òmó ní 'that child'
 child DEM

- (c) Determiner + Noun + Determiner => nè ágá ní 'that (particular) chair'
 DET chair DEM

- (d) Noun + Adjective => ìkpiá kpàtàkì 'important men'

Nouns can also be derived from verbs by prefixation (18), circumfixation (inserting verbs between the *ù...mwẹ* formative) (19a) and compounding (19b).

(18) *lèlé* 'follow' => *ì-lèlé* 'procedure'

fé 'be rich' => *ẹ-fẹ* 'wealth'

hiọ 'urinate' => *à-hiọ* 'urine'

khiàn 'walk' => *ò-khián* 'a walk'

wú 'die' => *ù-wú* 'death'

gbúgbó 'make farm' => *ọ-gbúgbó* 'farmer'

19 (a) *gbé* 'dance' => *ù-gbé-mwẹ* 'dancing'

rhòó 'praise' => *ù-rhòó-mwẹ* 'praise worship'

(b) *ẹkó* 'stomach' *rhiẹnrhiẹn* '(be sweet)' => *ẹkórhiẹnrhiẹnmwẹ* 'pleasure'

ègbé 'body' *bàlọ* 'pain' => *ègbébàlọmwẹ* 'hot temperedness'

Example (18) shows that the vowels [i, e, a, o, u, ɛ] can be prefixed to derive nouns from verb. In example (19), the circumfixation of the verbs *gbé* 'dance' and *rhòó* 'praise' to form the gerunds 'dancing' and 'praise worship respectively'. Nouns can also be formed from N + V + *mwẹ* compounds as demonstrated by the derivation of the nouns 'pleasure' and 'hot temper' from 'stomach + (be) sweet + *mwẹ*' and 'body + (be.in) pain + *mwẹ*' respectively.

3.3.1 Pronominal system

Uchihara (2010) points out that Edo pronouns distinguish three persons (1st, 2nd, 3rd) and two numbers (singular and plural). The language also operates four series of pronouns viz. the subjective series (used for transitive, intransitive and copula subjects), the objective series (used for transitive object and possessive constructions), the emphatic series (used for emphasis such as in cleft constructions) and the copulative

series (used for copula subjects). Edo pronouns are presented below in Table 1 (taken from Uchihara (2010)).

	Subjective	Objective	Emphatic	Copulative
1.sg.	<i>i</i>	<i>mwén</i>	<i>mē̄</i>	<i>imε</i>
2.sg.	<i>u</i>	<i>wé</i>	<i>wē̄</i>	<i>uwε</i>
3.sg.	<i>ɔ</i>	<i>éé</i>	<i>(i)yē̄</i>	<i>ɔriε</i>
1.pl.	<i>ma</i>	<i>ímá</i>	<i>mā̄</i>	<i>ima</i>
2.pl.	<i>wa</i>	<i>úwá</i>	<i>wā̄</i>	<i>uwa</i>
3.pl.	<i>íyán</i>	<i>íyán</i>	<i>íyán</i>	<i>íyán</i>

Figure 3-3: Edo pronominal system

3.3.2 Number marking system

Edo has three plural formation strategies viz suppletion (20a), reduplication (20b) and the periphrastic marker *ávbé* (20c).

- 20 (a) òkpiá ‘man’ => ìkpiá ‘men’
 òmó ‘child’ => èmó ‘children’
 èghélè ‘youth’ => íghéle ‘youth (pl)’
 òmwá ‘person’ èmwá ‘people’
- (b) òwá ‘house’ => òwówà ‘houses’
 òbó ‘hand’ => òbóbó ‘hands’
 ìsán ‘stool’ => ìsìsán ‘stools’
- (c) ékítá ‘dog’ => ávbé ékítá ‘dogs’
 èbé ‘book’ => ávbé èbé ‘books’
 úkpòn ‘cloth’ => ávbé ukpòn ‘clothes’

In Edo, [+Human] common nouns can be pluralized by vowel change of the first vowel in the word as shown with (20a). The first sound of the word if [o, ε] => [i], while if [ɔ] => [e]. Other nouns cannot be pluralized using this method.

3.4 Basic Morpho-Syntax

3.4.1 Word order

The basic word order of Edo clauses is S(subject) V(erb) O(bject) as shown in example (21).

21. (a) **S V O**
Òsàsú rri èvbàré
Osasu eat.IPFV food
'Osasu is eating'

(b) **S V O**
Ìvié bọ òwá
Ivie build.FAC house
'Ivie built a house'

The extended word-order of Edo clauses can be represented as S (particle) VO (Adverbs). The particles could be aspectual particles (22a), phasal particles (22b) or modals (22c). The optional adverbial slot could be filled by temporal adverbs (22d) or manner adverbs (22e).

22.(a) Ìyòbọ ghá tiè èbé
lyobo PROSP read book
'lyobo is reading/will read'

(b) Òsàzẹ khiàn yè ẹwù
Osaze about.to wear shirt
'Osaze is about to wear a shirt'

(c) Néné ọmọmọ sètín khiàn
DET child MOD walk
'The child can walk'

(d) Òkhuó só ìhuán nóde
woman sing.FAC song yesterday
'A woman sang yesterday'

(e) néné òkpiá rhùlẹ m̀nièm̀niè
DET man run.IPFV slowly
'The man is running slowly'

3.4.2 Serial verbs

Serial Verb Constructions (SVCs) have been recognized as a feature of many Kwa languages (Christaller 1875; Essegbey 2003; Ameka 2006, among others). Stewart (2001: 12) defines Serial Verb Constructions as “a single clause in which two or more finite verbs occur without any marker of coordination or subordination, sharing a single structural (and semantic) subject and a single object”. He proposes based on data in Èdo that there are only two types of SVCs – resultative and consequential. With resultative SVCs, “the action of the first verb brings about the result that is denoted by the second verb” (Stewart 2001:13). In other words, there is a cause-effect relationship between the verbs in addition to the absence of a time-lapse between the situations they encode. An example of a resultative SVC is shown in (23a).

23. (a) Òzó sùá ágá dé.
Ozo push chair fall
(Ozo push.FAC chair fall.FAC)
'Ozo pushed the chair down' Stewart (2001:13)

Consequential SVCs, on the other hand, are SVCs in which the verbs express a sub-sequential relationship i.e. the events, and they are ordered in a precedence-consequence relation (Gruber 1992a, 1992b).

- 23 (b) Òzó lé èvbàré rhié-nè Úyi
Ozo cook food give-to Uyi
(Ozo cook.FAC give.to.FAC Uyi)
'Ozo cooked the food and gave it to Uyi.'

Thus, (23b) indicates that Ozo cooked the food and gave it to *Uyi*, but it is possible that he could have done something else with the food (e.g. sold it instead). However, in the case of resultative SVC there is a ‘cause-effect’ relationship between

the action encoded by the first verb and the result encoded by the second verb unlike the case with resultative SVCs which have an ‘action-result’ relation.

Aspect-actionality interactions within SVCs is not discussed in this study as it falls outside the scope of this dissertation.

3.4.3 Verbal affixes

There are three verbal affixes in Èdo – two suffixes and one circumfix. The suffixes are the -rV suffix which and the pluractional -lv suffix. The circumfix *u...mwẹ* forms gerunds from verbs in the language. Discussion on the -rv completive marker will be deferred to the next chapter (chapter 4) where the temporal/aspectual marking system is explained in detail.

The pluractional suffix is referred to in the literature as the -lv suffix because “it is made up the voiced alveolar lateral stop /l/⁹ and a vowel which is conditioned by the last vowel of the verb stem to which it is attached¹⁰. Examples illustrating the suffix realization rules is presented below in (24) from Ọmọruyi (1986b:70).

Verb	Verb + Suffix
24 (a) <i>dè</i> ‘buy’	<i>dè-lé</i> ‘buy repeatedly’
(b) <i>vù</i> ‘uproot’	<i>vù-ló</i> ‘uproot repeatedly’
(c) <i>fì</i> ‘throw’	<i>fì-ló</i> ‘throw repeatedly’
(d) <i>gbè</i> ‘kill/break’	<i>gbè-lé</i> ‘kill/break repeatedly’
(e) <i>tà</i> ‘say’	<i>tà-ló</i> ‘say repeatedly’

⁹ /l/ is realized as [n] when the nucleus of the last syllable of the verb is a nasal vowel.

¹⁰ The following vowel alternation rules were proposed by Amayo (1976:117-118)

(a) if the last vowel of the stem is high, the suffix vowel is /o/ or /õ/, depending on whether the stem vowel is oral or nasal.

(b) If the last vowel of the stem is low, the vowel of the suffix is /ɔ/ or /õ/ depending on the nasality of the stem vowel.

(c). If the stem vowel is neither high nor low (i.e. a mid-vowel vowel), all the features of the stem vowel are copied onto the suffix.

(f) <i>sùn</i> ‘crawl’	<i>sùn-nọ</i> ‘crawl repeatedly’
(g) <i>bùún</i> ‘break’	<i>bùún-nọ</i> ‘break repeatedly’
(h) <i>tín</i> ‘fly’	<i>tín-nọ</i> ‘fly repeatedly’
(i) <i>sàán</i> ‘jump’	<i>sàán-nọ</i> ‘jump repeatedly’
(j) <i>mìe</i> ‘squeeze out liquid’	<i>mìe -nẹ</i> ‘squeeze out liquid repeatedly’

Previous analyses of the suffix include (i) it is a (verbal) plural marker (Ọmọruyi 1986b:70), (ii) it “... marks a multiplication of the activity designated by the verb/iterative marker” (Yuka and Ọmọrẹgbẹ (2010:13), (iii) it “encodes repetition of the action designated by the verb” (Ọmọrẹgbẹ 2012:195). Iyamu (2016:65-66) however proposes that the disagreements associated with specifying the meaning of the -lv suffix could be resolved when the interaction between transitivity, punctuality/durativity and telicity (actionality primitives) is considered. He claims that the function of the suffix is to extend events by ‘atelicizing’ them (i.e. changing telic events to atelic events). He proposes that [+punctual + telic] verbs are temporally ‘extended’ by the -lv verbal extension - which then results in an iterative reading. Similarly, [- punctual + telic] verbs are extended by pluralizing the direct object (in the case of transitive clauses). [-telic] Edo verbs do not license the -lv suffix as [-telic] events are unbounded and hence require no extension. Iyamu goes on to argue that this is the reason why state verbs and activity verbs do not license the -lv extension as they are [-telic], The data in (25a-c) below, illustrate the iterative reading [+telic, +punctual] verbs receive when affixed with the -lv.

- 25 (a) Ẹnyẹ kìn lègàá èrhán
snake CPL.coil round tree
(snake coil.FAC round tree)
‘A snake coiled round a tree’
- (a’) Ẹnyẹ kìn-nọ lègàá èrhán
snake CPL.coil-lv round tree
(snake coil-PLUR round tree)
‘A snake repeatedly coiled round a tree’
- (b) Íránmwè sá né ọmọmọ

black.ant CPL.bite DET baby
 (black.ant bite.FAC DET baby)
 'A black ant bit the baby'

(b') Íránmwè sà-ló né ọmómó
 black ant CPL.bite-lv DET baby
 (black ant bite-PLUR DET baby)
 'A black ant repeatedly bit the child'

(c) Ívìn dé nyà ùhúnmwù né òwá
 coconut CPL.fall on head DET house
 (coconut fall.FAC on head DET house)
 'A coconut fell on the roof top'

(c') Ívìn dè-lé nyà ùhúnmwù òwá
 coconut CPL.fall-lv on head house
 (coconut fall-PLUR on head house)
 'Coconuts fell repeatedly on the roof top'

Iyamu (2016:66)

Examples (26) below present evidence from Iyamu (2016) showing the temporal extension of [+telic, -punctual] verbs suffixed with the -lv extension by 'pluralizing' the subject in intransitive clauses and the object in transitive clauses.

26 (a) ékítà wú nódè
 dog CPL.die yesterday
 (dog die.FAC yesterday)
 'A dog died yesterday'

(a') ávbé ékítà wù-ló nódè
 PL dog CPL.die-lv yesterday
 (PL dog die.FAC-PLUR yesterday)
 'Many dogs died yesterday'

(b) Érhà mwè bọ òwá yè èkó
 father POSS CPL.build house in Lagos
 (father POSS build.FAC house in Lagos)
 'My Father built a house in Lagos'

(b'') Érhà mwè bọ-ló òwá yè èkó
 father POSS CPL.build-lv house in Lagos
 (father POSS build-PLUR house in Lagos)
 'My father built several houses in Lagos'

(c) Íràn má ọmwá yè èguàè
 3.PL.SBJ CPL.mould person in palace
 (3.PL.NOM mould.FAC person in palace)

‘They moulded the statue of a person in the palace’

(c') Íràn mà-nọ òmwá yè èguàè
3.PL.SBJ CPL.mould person in palace
‘They molded statues of people in the palace’

In examples (26 a-c), sentences are presented without the -lv extension suffixed to verbs with the aim of contrasting them with -lv suffixed verbs in 26(a')-(c'). It is important to note that it is the internal argument of the verb that bears the effects of the temporal extension and never the external argument in transitive clauses. The generalization in respect of [+telic, +punctual] verbs stated above validates Ọmọruyi's (1986) claim that the -lv suffix 'pluralizes' subjects and objects in intransitive and transitive clauses respectively. It however appears that Ọmọruyi (1986) based his arguments only on [+telic, -punctual verbs] without taking into consideration [+telic, +punctual] verbs which have an iterative reading when combined with the -lv extension. The data in (26a' - c') also raise questions about the claims made by Yuka and Ọmọrẹgbẹ (2010) that the -lv extension supplies a repetitive/iterative reading to verbs which license the -lv suffix. It appears this claim was made taking into account only [+telic, + punctual] verbs without considering [+telic, - punctual] verbs. Iyamu (2016) provides additional evidence for this claim based on the observation that only [+ telic] verbs license the suffix as shown in (27).

- 27(a) fẹ 'rich' - *fẹ-lé
- (b) fù 'gentle' - *fu-ló
- (c) gbín 'blunt' - *gbìn-nọ
- (d) bà 'shine' - *bà-lọ
- (e) khián 'walk' - *khiàn-nọ
- (f) kpé 'wash' - *kpè-lé
- (g) khué 'swim' - *khuè-lé

The -lv extension thus serves to ‘untelicise’ verbs by extending them indefinitely thus making them temporally unbounded as [-telic] verbs such as inchoative verbs which encode a change of state plus a result state and activity verbs do not license the suffix.

The circumfix *u...mwẹ* is used to form gerunds from verbs before predicate cleft in Edo. Stewart (1998) notes that verbs from all classes (inchoatives (28c), unaccusative (28d), transitive (28e) and unergative (28f)). Examples of verbs in their citation forms with the circumfix from Stewart (1998) are presented in (28).

- 28 (a) sùá ‘push’ – ùsùámwẹ ‘pushing’
 (b) hìá ‘try’ – ùhìámwẹ ‘trying’
 (c) kpòlọ ‘be.big’ – ùkpòlọmwẹ ‘being.big’
 (d) dé ‘fall’ – ùdémwẹ ‘falling’
 (e) khiẹn ‘sell’ – ùkhiẹnmwẹ ‘selling’
 (f) só ‘shout’ – ùsómwẹ ‘shouting’
 (g) lé ‘cook’ – ùsómwẹ ‘cooking’

Example (29) demonstrates gerunds derived by circumfixation in the context of predicate cleft constructions.

29. (a) Úyì kpòlọ
 Uyi be.big
 (Uyi big.FAC)
 ‘Uyi is big’
- (a’) ù-kpòlọ-mwén ọré Úyì kpòlọ
 Nom-be big-NOM FOC Uyi be.big
 (NOM-be.big-NOM FOC Uyi big.FAC)
 ‘It is fat that Uyi is fat’
- (b) Úyì só
 (Uyi shout.FAC)
 ‘Uyi shouted’
- (b’) ù-só-mwén ọré Úyì só
 Nom-shout-Nom FOC Uyi shout
 (NOM-shout-NOM FOC Uyi shout.FAC)

'It is shouting that Uyi did'

(Stewart (1998) cf. Ajiboye (Ajiboye 2001:4))

Stewart (1998) also notes a constraint on the gerundization of verbs; gerundization and verbs from which cognate nouns can be derived by prefixation are mutually exclusive. In other words, any verb that can derive a cognate noun by prefixing a vowel does not license the gerundive circumfix. This is demonstrated with example (30) below.

30. Verb	Cognate	Gerund
(a) hió 'urinate'	à-hió 'urine'	* ùhiómwẹn 'urinating'
(b) khián 'walk (V)'	à-khián 'walk (N)'	* ùkhiánmwẹn 'walking'
(c) wẹn 'suck (V)'	è-wẹn 'suck (N)'	* ùwẹnmwẹn 'sucking'
(d) kpá 'vomit (V)'	è-kpá 'vomit (N)'	* ùkpámwẹn 'vomiting'

As shown with example (30) verbs which have a cognate derived from the prefixation of /a/ or /e/ to the verb do not license forming gerunds by the circumfixation of *u...mwẹ*.

3.4.4 Negation

Previous studies of negation in Edo (Ọmọregie (1983); Agheyisi 1986; Ọmọruyi 1986, 1989, 1991; Imasụn 1997a, 1997b) identify three negative markers in the language viz. *í*, *má* and *ghé*. According to Eṅbuomwan and Usenbo (2019: 98), "in Edo language, negation is achieved by placing a negative marker before the first verbal element of a clause". Example (31) demonstrates how negation works in Edo.

- 31 (a) Ímádé má rri èvbàré
Imade NEG.PST eat food
'Imade did not eat'
- (b) Ímádé í rri èvbàré
Imade NEG.PRS eat food
'Imade is not eating'

- (c) *Ímádé, ghé rrí èvbàré*
 Imade NEG.IMP eat food
 'Imade, do not eat'

Past negative events are marked by *má* (31a), present negative events are marked with *í* (31b) and *ghé* (31c) marks negation in imperative constructions.

3.4.5 Verbs vs adjectives

The purpose of this subsection is to discuss two lexical categories which in many languages are distinct and not interrelated but in Èdo, the adjectival lexical class has been called to question and is argued to be derived from stative verbs.

Welmers (1973:274) warns that in Niger-Congo languages, one should be “suspicious of ‘adjectives’”, because what appears to be adjectives may be complex constructions that can be ‘decomposed’ into simpler parts.

Previous studies of the adjectival category in Èdo include Omoruyi (1986), Agheyisi (1986), Imasuen (1993), Omoregbe (2003), and Omoregbe and Aigbedo (2012). Agheyisi (1986: xx) claims that adjectives are “predominantly ideophonic” in Èdo and can be subdivided into derived and underived adjectives. Underived adjectives are those which on the surface appear to be ‘bare’ (i.e. without any grammatical element added) as shown in (32a-32c) whereas derived adjectives are stative verbs + the relativizer *né* (32d-32f).

- 32 (a) *dán* ‘evil, bad’
 (b) *kẹkàn* ‘bare’
 (c) *mòsèè* ‘very beautiful’
 (d) *nwẹrẹn* ‘to be thin’ => *nénwẹrẹn* ‘thin’
 (e) *khèrhé* ‘to be small’ => *’nékhèrhé* ‘small’
 (f) *mòsé* ‘to be beautiful’ => *némòsèè* ‘beautiful’ (Agheyisi, 1986:xxi)

Like Agheyisi (1986), Omoruyi (1986) proposes that ‘pure adjectives’ can be derived from verbs which he calls ‘adjectival’ verbs. Yuka and Èvbuomwan (2016)

however propose that there are no adjectives in Edo; adjectival concepts are encoded by complement clauses/phrases. They claim that a series of ordered phono-syntactic processes combine to realize the surface form of so-called adjectives. The processes in question are pronominalization (the replacement of a nominal with the resumptive pronoun *ò*), segment deletion (the elision of the vowel of the relativizer *né*) and finally contraction (the merging of the surviving consonant of the deletion process with a verb), These phono-syntactic processes are exemplified in (33) below.

33 (a) Base form:

Èfósà dẹ òkọ, né òkọ kpòlọ, né òkọ mọ̀sé.
 Efosa buy.pst canoe that canoe be.big, that canoe be-beautiful

(b) Pronominalisation:

Èfósà dẹ òkọ, né ò kpòlọ, né ò mọ̀sé.
 Efosa buy.pst canoe that 3SG be.big, that 3SG be-beautiful

(c) Segment deletion:

Èfósà dẹ òkọ, n_ ò kpòlọ, n_ ò mọ̀sé
 Efosa buy-pst canoe that 3SG be-big, that 3SG be-beautiful

(d) Contraction:

Èfósà dẹ òkọ, nọkpòlọ, nọmọ̀sé
 Efosa buy.pst canoe that.is.big, that-is-beautiful

(e) Final (rapid speech) utterance:

Èfósà dẹ òkọ nọkpòlọ, nọmọ̀sé.
 Efosa buy.pst canoe that-is-big, that-is-beautiful

'Efosa bought a beautiful big canoe'

As will be shown in chapter 5, this study does not propose the presence of stative verbs as there were no tests to prove that Edo attests 'pure states'. Instead, I propose that what has been referred to as stative verbs (or adjectival verbs by Omoreuyi

1986) are inchoative verbs (also known as change-of-state verbs) which encode a change-of-state + result-state phasal structure.

3.5 Summary and conclusion

In this chapter, aspects of Edo grammar relevant to understanding the analyses of temporal marking (chapter 4) and actional classification of verb senses in the language was presented. First, the phonology of Edo was discussed (section 3.2) including the phonemes (and their orthographic representation), phonological processes and tone system (tonemes and tonemic rules). Edo has 27 consonants and 12 vowels, attests four phonological processes (nasal assimilation, vowel elision, consonant deletion, glide formation) and two types of tonal assimilation (vertical and horizontal). Section 3.3 presents the nominal morphology of Edo. In particular, the pronominal and number marking systems were discussed. The language attests four series of pronouns (subjective, objective, copulative and emphatic) and uses three plural formation strategies (suppletion, reduplication and a periphrastic marker *ávbé*). The final section of the chapter (section 3.4) discussed aspects of the morphosyntax of the Edo language. Topics discussed include the canonic word-order of the language, serial verb constructions, verbal affixes, negation and 'stative verb' vs adjective debate. Edo is an SVO language, attests serial verb constructions, has only three verbal affixes (the -rV completive marker, the pluractional -lv suffix and the circumfix *u...mwẹ* which forms gerunds from verbs), three negation markers (*í* which marks present negation, *má* which marks past negation and *ghé* which marks negation in imperative clauses) and does not attest adjectives,

In the next chapter, I discuss the temporal/aspectual 'landscape' of Edo. I present current analyses of temporal/aspectual markers in the language and propose

some alternative analyses with the goal of resolving some disagreements in accounting for the tense/aspect system of Edo. This will prove to be important as these markers serve as actional tests in chapter 5.

CHAPTER 4 TEMPORAL MARKING IN EDO

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents and discusses the strategies employed by the Edo language to encode temporal marking categories. The goal of the chapter is to offer alternative analyses to some of the ‘resources’ Edo uses to encode temporal and aspectual meaning earlier proposed in the language considering the lack of agreement in the literature on temporal/aspectual marking. Some of the points of disagreement include for example, whether Edo is a tense or aspect dominant language. As earlier discussed in chapter 2, Aikhionbare (1986) and Agheyisi (1986) argue that the temporal categories in Edo are tense markers, Omozuwa (1991) argues that they are aspectual categories differentiated by prosody (grammatical tones) and Dunn (1968), Emovon (1980), Omoruyi (1991), and Ogie (2008) take a position in favor of a hybrid system (i.e. a ‘blend’ of tense and aspect). I show in this chapter that Edo is an aspect prominent language. The specific category each marker encodes has equally been a source of disagreement across different accounts of temporal marking in Edo as will be shown in the following sections.

Another reason for discussing these temporal markers is to introduce them as a key ‘ingredient’ in the classification of verbs in chapter 5. As earlier pointed out in chapter 2, the bidimensional approach to actional classification relies on the aspectual phases ‘highlighted’ by the grammatical aspect/tense categories of the language in question. In other words, the varied temporal interpretations predicates receive when they cooccur with grammatical aspect operators, will be shown to arise because of the aspectual phase(s) made available to be selected by the grammatical aspect operators.

4.2 Aspectual distinctions

4.2.1 The Factative

The term *factative* was first brought to the fore by Welmers (1973:345-348) who observed “that some languages use a single construction to refer to past time for active verbs, and present time for stative verbs”. He proposed the term factative to refer to this phenomenon because “the construction expresses the most obvious fact about the verb in question, which in the case of active verbs is that the action was observed or took place, but for stative verbs is that the action obtains at present.”

Nurse et al (2016:25) explains the linguistic characteristics of the factative as follows,

“Factative has two characteristic features. Structurally, it is nearly always an unmarked form, either a zero form or the least marked aspectual form in a language. In contrast with Imperfective, it will generally be the unmarked form. Functionally, when used with non-stative or dynamic verbs, it typically represents past, complete, situations, but when used with stative verbs, it represents current, non-past, incomplete, states, that is, presents or futures”.

There are typically four strategies for marking the factative (i) the factative could be unmarked (ii) it could be marked by affixes on the verb (iii) It could be marked by prosody (iv) It could be doubly marked i.e., using a combination of two of the earlier mentioned strategies (Nurse et al. 2016:29). Examples of languages with the factative include Degema (1), Godie (2) and Ijo (3).

Degema (Delta-Edoid)¹

1. (a) *mɪ-dí-īn*
1.SG-eat-FAC
(1s-eat-FAC)
'I ate'
- (b) *o-mí-ín*
3.SG-be.wet-FAC
(3s-be wet-FAC)
'It became wet/It is wet.'

Kari (2002: 179)

Godie (Eastern Kru)²

2. (a) *ɔ kù*
3.SG die.FAC
(3s die.PFM)
'He died/He is dead'
- (b) *ǒ jūbò dɛ*
1.PL know.FAC something
(they know.PFM something)
'They know something.'

Marchese (1986: 29)

(ibid:31)

Kolokuma (Ijoid)³

3. (a) *i bo-mí*
1.SG come-FAC
(1s come-FAC)
'I came.'
- (b) *akú -mí*
become.bitter-FAC
'It is bitter.'

Williamson (1991: 148)

Examples (1), (2) and (3) show the factative markers in each language (-*in*, low tone and -*mí*) yielding two different aspectual interpretations depending on the actionality of the predicate in the clause. In the case of 'dynamic' predicates (1a, 2a and

¹ The factative in Degema is marked by the -(V)n enclitic which encodes "past time" when used with dynamic verbs and "non-past time" or with stative verbs. The tone pattern of the root combined with the "factative enclitic" is a downstep.

² The authors opted for the term 'performative' which is an alternative term for 'factative' hence the gloss 'PFM'. In most Eastern Kru languages, the factative/performative is marked by the low tone.

³ The factative in Kolokuma is marked by the suffix -*mi*.

3a), a past/complete interpretation is derived whereas when used with stative/inchoative predicates, a present state interpretation is derived as shown with (1b), (2b) and (3b).

In the case of Èdo, the high tone (on monosyllabic verbs or the last tone bearing unit in bi-/multi-syllabic verbs) has previously been analyzed as a past tense marker (Dunn 1968; Ọmọzuwa 2003; Yuka & Ọmọregbẹ 2011; Ọmọregbẹ 2012) and a perfective marker (Yuka and Ọmọregbẹ 2011). In this section, I provide evidence to show that the high tone in the above specified contexts marks the factative.

Previous accounts of TAM marking in the language identified prosody as an integral instrument in the temporal marking system of Èdo. Dunn (1968:6) argued that the high tone on the first syllable of the verb marks past complete as shown in (4) below.

4. Èdó í ké-rrè
 Edo 1.SG originate-come
 (Edo 1.SG come.from-PST.COMP)
 'I come from Edo' Dunn (1968:6)

Yuka and Ọmọregbẹ (2011) mention the high tone on transitive CV verbs as one of two strategies for marking past tense in Èdo⁴. The examples in (5) were used to support this analysis.

5. (a) Ọ́ dẹ́ èbé
 3.SG buy.FAC book
 (he pst-buy book)
 'He bought a book'
- (b) Ọ́zó sá àmẹ́
 Ozo fetch.FAC water
 (Ozo pst-fetch water)
 'Ozo fetched water'

⁴ The second strategy is the -rv suffix with intransitive verbs. This is discussed in more detail in section 4.3.

- (c) *Èki kpé òkpán*
 Èki wash.FAC plates
 (Èki pst-wash plates)
 'Èki washed plates'

Yuka and Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ (2011:12)

Although Yuka and Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ (2011:17) write that the perfective aspect in Èdo is marked as high tone (identical with that which marks simple past tense in Èdo)", they do not provide data to illustrate the tonal marking of the perfective in Èdo.

Finally, Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ (2012:127) proposes that "... past tense in the language is marked by a high tone on the verb while the so-called –rV suffix marks perfectivity. The –rV suffix is thus, an aspectual and not a tense feature". She argues that because the verbs in (6) are not suffixed with the -rV suffix, the high tone is responsible for the past event interpretation of those verbs as shown in example (6).

6. (a) *Úyì dẹ ẹwé vbè ẹki*
 Uyi buy.FAC goat PREP market
 (Uyi pst-buy goat in market)
 'Uyi bought a goat in the market'

- (b) *Òzó lẹ́ọ́ úkpọ̀n mwẹ́*
 Ozo iron.FAC cloth POSS
 (Ozo pst-iron cloth my)
 'Ozo ironed my cloth'

- (c) *Ọ̀ kpòlọ́ ọ̀wá nódẹ́*
 3.SG sweep.FAC house yesterday
 (He pst-sweep house yesterday)
 'He swept the house yesterday'

Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ (2012:133)

I disagree with Dunn's (1968) analysis that the high tone marks past tense. The analysis is problematic, because the verb *ké rrè* which means 'come.from' is a compound verb made up of the verb *ké* which indicates origin/source of motion and the verb *rrè* 'come'. It is also difficult to see how the sentence in (4) encodes a past and/or completive event as the resulting meaning of the verb in (4) is 'X hails from/is an

indigene of Y', which is an individual-level state reading that cannot be temporally bounded.

Yuka and Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ's (2011) proposal which argues for a past/perfective interpretation for the high tone, does not capture the range of temporal nuances associated with the high tone syllable in Èdo because this analysis does not consider the interpretation of inchoative verbs, such as *dín* 'to be(come) brave' and *fé* 'to be(come) rich'. These verbs have a present result-state interpretation when suffixed with the high tone on the last tone-bearing unit of the verb - a reading atypical of past tense markers.

The need for an alternative analysis of the high tone is therefore required for two reasons (i) the evidence for proposing that the high tone in Èdo marks past tense or perfective aspect is based on the English translation of constructions with verbs bearing the high tone as no contextual cues were provided with any of the translations. (ii) inchoative verbs were not considered in the proposal of previous analyses. I therefore present evidence in favor of accounting for the high tone as the factative⁵ (Welmers 1973; Faraclas 1984; Faraclas et al 2007) built on two 'clues' (typological and structural) and one evidence (functional) beyond translation equivalents and which accounts for the interpretation of the high tone with different verb types.

1. Typological clue

⁵ Hewson (2012:518-519) proposes the term 'performative' instead of factative for two reasons (i) The potential to confuse it with the *term factitive*, and (ii) Performative captures a wider range of functions than those specified for the factative by Welmers. I follow Nurse (2016:26) in retaining the term 'factative' because it is typologically more familiar.

Niger-Congo languages are known to be aspect-prominent languages. Nurse et al. (2016:25) states that “while a minority of Niger-Congo families have tense contrasts, all have aspect. Five aspects are widespread in Niger-Congo: Factative (FAC)/ Perfective (PFV), Imperfective (IPFV), Perfect (PFT), Progressive (PRG), and Habitual (HAB)/Iterative”. Nurse et al. (2016) argues that although it is typical to make a binary aspectual distinction between perfective and imperfective aspect (see e.g., Comrie 1976:25), most Niger-Congo languages operate a factative-imperfective temporal system. Out of 21 non-Bantu Niger-Congo languages surveyed by Nurse et al. (2016), only four (19%) have perfective and not factative – and even the absence of the factative in these four languages is doubtful⁶. Languages with a factative-imperfective distinction span across different subgroups of the Niger-Congo family including Kabiye (Gur), Kisi (South-Atlantic), Jukun (Benue-Congo), Godie (Kru), Ewe (Kwa), Ijo (Ijoid), Ejaghem (Ekoid-Bantu), Degema (Volta-Niger), Yoruba (Volta-Niger) and Doyayo (Adamawa) (Nurse et al. 2016:29).

Although this is not fool-proof evidence that the high-tone on the verb in Edo marks the factative instead of simple past tense or perfective aspect, it is a pointer that we are more likely to be dealing with an aspectual form (given the typological prominence of grammatical aspect in languages of this area) than a tense category, on one hand, and a reason why we should be a on the lookout for the ‘factative’ category, on the other. Subsequently, I present further evidence based on the structural and functional characteristics of the high tone in favor of my analysis.

⁶ This is based on the diagnostic criteria used. A lack of ‘hard evidence’ for the factative was taken as presence of the perfective.

2. Structural clue.

As stated earlier, one of the defining structural characteristics of the factative is that it is either zero-marked or the least marked aspectual form in the language. Nurse, et al (2016:29) argues that although not all instantiations of the factative are unmarked, if one of the two (i.e., factative or imperfective) is unmarked, it is likely to be the factative.

In the Edo language, the high tone on the verb is the base form of most verbs as observed in out-of-context lexical elicitation of verbs⁷. Evidence for this is provided in the Edo-English dictionary (Agheyisi 1986) and corroborated by direct elicitation by consultants in this study. I carried out a survey of all verb lexemes in the dictionary. Out of 1,130 verb entries observed, 1,034 (91.5%) bore the high tone on the last syllable while 96 (8.5%) had a low tone on the final syllable. I also observed that most of the verbs bearing a low tone on the final syllable (80 representing 8.3%) were V + N compound verbs where the last syllable of the noun bears an inherent low tone. This is illustrated in (7) below.

7. (a) tá 'talk' + òhóghè 'lies' => tòhóghè '(to) tell lies'
- (b) ré⁸ 'eat' + òyà 'insult; humiliation' => rrioyà 'to incur insult'
- (c) si 'to reduce in size/capacity' + àmè 'water' => siámè 'to become emaciated'
- (d) kpé 'wash' + íghò 'horns' => kpíghò 'to struggle/compete with someone'
- (e) dó 'to be in full session' + èkì 'market' => dóẹkì 'to trade in wares'

To further illustrate the role of the tones of nouns in a V+N compound, consider the pair *zìghó* 'spend money/pay a fine' vs *zìghò* 'to grow horns' in (8) where the low

⁷ i.e., in response to the question 'How do you say X (verb) in Edo'?

⁸ When this verb is followed by its direct object, it becomes *rrí*.

tone on the last syllable of (8b) is as a result of the last syllable of the word *íghò* 'horn' bearing a low tone whereas *íghó* 'money' does not.

8. (a) *zè* 'to spend (money)/pay a levy/fine' + *íghó* 'money' => *zíghó* 'spend money/pay a fine'
(b) *zòó* 'to germinate/sprout' + *íghò* 'horn' => *zíghò* 'to grow horns'

16 out of the 96 verbs were not attributable to a V+N compound with a final low-tone syllable. 9 of the 16 were monosyllabic verbs which could not be decomposed any further (9a-9c) while 7 had a 'suspicious' V+N structure but could not be broken down into meaningful V and N components (9d-9f).

9. (a) *kuè* 'agree (to something)'
(b) *rèè* '(to) arrive'
(c) *tákhìrì* 'to perform single/multiple somersaults in the air'
(d) *wíkà* 'to struggle along/make a great effort'
(e) *sòtè* 'to defy/rebel against'

I therefore propose that since the high tone is the default tone shown by most verbs bearing the high tone in citation form, the high tone marks the factative as one of the characteristics of the factative is that it is an unmarked (or the least marked) temporal category.

3. Functional evidence.

One of the defining characteristics of the factative is that it has different temporal interpretations depending on whether it is cooccurring with a state/inchoative verb or with a non-state/non-inchoative verb. In other words, it serves as a 'partition' between states/CoS verbs, on one hand and non-inchoative verbs, on the other. With the former, the factative yields a present state reading while with the latter, a past

interpretation is achieved. This property of temporal semantic variation between the present and past differentiates the factative from the perfective which has a default bounded-past interpretation with most predicates. Example (10) shows the factative with inchoative verbs (10a-10d), while examples (11) illustrates the factative with achievement verbs (11a and 11b), an accomplishment verb (11c) and an activity verb (11d).

- 10.(a) *Òsàsú ghòghò*
 Osasu happy.FAC
 'Osasu is happy'
- (b) *Èkpò Ímádé kpòlò*
 bag Imade big.FAC
 'Imade's bag is big'
- (c) *Ìnyá nà kẹkẹ*
 yam DEM rotten.FAC
 'This yam is rotten'
- (d) *òkhuó ní mósé*
 woman DEM beautiful.FAC
 'That woman is beautiful'
- 11.(a) *Áísósà guòghò ògò*
 Aisosa break.FAC bottle
 'Aisosa broke (a) bottle(s)'
- (b) *Ètínòsà sàá íbórò*
 Etinosa shatter.FAC ball
 'Etinosa shattered a ball.'
- (c) *Èfósà bó òwá*
 Efosa build.FAC house
 'Efosa built a house.'
- (d) *ómòmọ ná viẹ*
 baby DEM cry.FAC
 'This baby cried.'

Bohnemeyer and Swift (2004) proposes a similar analysis for a comparable phenomenon in Inuktitut (12), German (13) and Russian (14) – in which the aspectual reference of clauses depends on the telicity of event predicates. Although the difference in aspectual reference in Edo is not based on telicity, but the presence or absence of a change-of-state phase, this illustrates that aspectual reference in languages could be based on a few temporal-semantic parameters such as stativity, telicity, durativity etc.

Inuktitut - INU⁹

12. (a) *Anijuq.*
 ani-juq
 go.out-PAR.3.SG
 'He/she went out.'

(b) *Pisuttuq.*
 pisuk-juq
 walk-PAR.3.SG
 'He/she is walking.'

Bohnemeyer and Swift (2004: 267)

German - GER¹⁰

13. (a) *Als ich Marys Büro betrat, schrieb sie an einem Brief.*
 When I Mary's office entered.PST wrote.PST she at a letter
 'When I entered Mary's office, she was writing a letter.'

(b) *Als ich Marys Büro betrat, schrieb sie einem Brief.*
 When I Mary's office entered.PST wrote.PST she a letter
 'When I entered Mary's office, she wrote a letter.'

Bohnemeyer and Swift (2004:268)

In the Inuktitut language, unmarked verb forms can occur with both telic and atelic predicates, but the temporal reference in both cases differs depending on the

⁹ Inuktitut, is a language spoken by the Inuit people of Quebec. It has temporally zero-marked verb forms which occur with both telic and atelic predicates; However, its interpretation differs depending on the telicity of the predicate in question. Constructions which encode telic event predicates have a perfective interpretation and those encoding atelic predicates have an imperfective interpretation (Swift 2004). Zero-marked forms in the language are contrasted with marked forms that encode perfective viewpoints in clauses with atelic predicates and imperfective interpretations in clauses with telic predicates.

¹⁰ (Standard) German lacks overt aspect marking altogether. There is a preference for interpreting atelic descriptions (past or present) imperfectively, while telic descriptions in the same tenses are preferentially interpreted perfectly (cf. Bohnemeyer (1998)).

telicity of the predicate. Telic-event predicates have a perfective interpretation, as in (12a) with the predicate *ani* ‘go.out’, while atelic predicates such as *pisuk* ‘walk’ have an imperfective interpretation, as in (12b). Example (13a) differs from (13b) with respect to the partitive construction *an einem Brief* which entails that only a part of the letter was written, thereby rendering the description atelic as the event did not culminate (cf. Krifka (1992)). The only available reading for example (13a) is that the writing event was ongoing simultaneously with the entry event, hence an imperfective interpretation. In contrast, (13b) suggests that the beginning of the writing event coincided with the entering, thus yielding a perfective interpretation for the writing event.

Russian – RUS¹¹

14. (a) *Vcera ja stavila knigi na polku dva chasa.*
 Yesterday I put(PST) books(PL) on shelf two hours
 ‘Yesterday I put books on the shelf for two hours.’

(b) *Vcera ja po-stavila vse knigi na polku za dva chasa.*
 Yesterday I TEL-put(PST) all books(PL) on shelf in two hours
 ‘Yesterday I put books on the shelf in two hours.’

Bohnenmeyer and Swift (2004:272)

The difference between (14a) and (14b) is one of atelicity attributed to (14a) referring to an indefinite set of books, while (14b) refers to a definite one. Russian does not have a definite article (definiteness interpretations are triggered by telic verb prefixes) so the delimitation of the set of books in (14b) is ‘forced’ by the universal quantifier *vse*. This renders the event predicate encoded by (14b) quantized and thereby telic. The time adverbials selected further reflect the telicity contrast – *dva chasa* ‘for two hours’ in (14a) is a durative adverbial, while *za dva chasa* ‘in two hours’

¹¹ In Russian, unprefixated verbs are (mostly) atelic while telic predicate are mostly encoded by prefixed verbs (or suffixed with the ‘semelfactive’ marker *-nu*).

in (14b) is a time-span adverbial. Crucially, the atelic *stávit'* is acceptable in (14a), but not in (14b), while the telic *po-stávit'* is acceptable in (14b), but not in (14a).

Bohnenmeyer and Swift's (2004) analysis rests on the premise that in these languages, clauses not overtly marked for grammatical aspect (hence marked with 'default' aspect) implicate 'event realization'. The past/completed time reference associated with clauses not overtly marked for aspect in these languages is based on telicity in combination with principles of Gricean pragmatics; clauses with atelic predicates such as 'walk' (12b), 'write' (13a) and *stavila* (RUS) 'put' (atelic) receive an imperfective interpretation while clauses with telic predicates such as *ani* 'go.out' (12a), *pisuk* 'write.a.letter' (13b) (Inuktitut) and *po-stavila* (Russian) 'put' (telic) get a perfective interpretation. Likewise, the atelic predicate *pisuk* 'walk' (Inuktitut) and the partitive NP *an einem Brief* 'part of a letter' (German) in the context of a predicate which could be described as an activity/active accomplishment in the Vendlerian sense, have imperfective interpretation whereas telic predicates *ani* 'go.out' (Inuktitut) and non-participial NPs e.g. *einem Brief* 'a letter' in the aforementioned context have a perfective reading.

The factative system in many non-Bantu languages can thus be analyzed in similar terms as a temporal system where default aspect (clauses not overtly marked for aspect) implicates event realization (i.e. the occurrence of the event encoded in the verb in the case of non-inchoatives and a result state following a change-of-state) as determined by the state/CoS vs non-inchoative status of predicates in the clause. While the former gets a present temporal interpretation, the latter are interpreted as past/complete.

The default aspect marking in Inuktitut, Russian and German differs from the factative in Bantu languages in that the former is based on the feature [telicity] whereas the latter is based on the presence or absence of a change-of-state in the phasal structure of the predicate in question.

In summary, previous accounts of the high tone in Edo relied solely on translation equivalence and did not take into account inchoatives in proposing a past/perfective interpretation for this temporal marker. I propose a factative analysis for the high tone based on a typological clue (The factative-imperfective split is attested in most languages typologically related to Edo), a structural clue (The high tone is the default tone of verbs and the factative is mostly unmarked in languages in which it is attested) and functional evidence (the high tone has a past interpretation with non-inchoatives but a present reading with inchoatives).

4.2.2 Low Tone marks imperfective aspect in Edo

The low tone (on monosyllabic verbs and the last syllable of bi/multi-syllabic verbs) in Edo has been analyzed as a present tense marker (Omozuwa 2003; Yuka and Omoregbẹ 2011; Omoregbẹ 2012), a habitual aspect marker (Omoregbẹ 2012) and progressive aspect (Omoregbẹ 2012). In this section, I analyze it as an imperfective marker in the broad use of the term subsuming both progressive and habitual readings.

The imperfective aspect is one of five aspectual contrasts argued to be widespread in Niger-Congo in Nurse (2016:25). A binary aspectual distinction is typically made between perfective and imperfective. (e.g., Comrie 1976:25). However, most Niger-Congo families distinguish between factative and imperfective (in the widest sense). The term 'Imperfective' has two different meanings in the non-Bantu languages

surveyed by Nurse (2016). In some of the languages, it serves as a broader category, representing the only type of incomplete aspect that contrasts with the factative (or perfective) aspect e.g., in Bambara (15) and Degema (16) languages.

Bambara (Manding, Mande)

15.(a) *ń bέ tága*
1.SG IPFV leave
'I'm leaving'

(b) *ánw bέ bàmw gén*
1.PL IPFV crocodiles hunt
'We hunt crocodiles'

Idiatov (2000)

The imperfective *bέ* in Bambara encodes both the progressive (15a) and habitual (15b). It will be shown that this is also the case in Edo.

Degema

16. *ójí má-máñíné ínúm*
3.SG 3.SG-learn something
'3s studies/is studying'

(Kari 2002:188)

The imperfective aspect in Degema is unmarked i.e., the interpretation of an unmarked verb is imperfect present.

However, in some other Niger-Congo languages, the imperfective is one of several incomplete categories, along with progressive, habitual, iterative, and others (for example in Aghem (Hyman 1979) a Grassfield Bantu language has imperfective (-*ag*) and habitual (post-verbal *tsigha*); while Jukun (Storch 1999: 190) has imperfective (-*ri*-) and habitual aspect (-*nomtí*-).

In both cases, the imperfective aspect encodes a situation from within - the situation has begun, it is ongoing, and is likely to continue. On the other hand, the progressive aspect is a more specific type of imperfective aspect that focuses on the

temporal space around the time of reference. It is not clear at this point why imperfective aspect as marked by the low tone is incompatible with inchoatives..

As mentioned above, previous studies analyzed the low tone as a present tense marker (Yuka and Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ 2011) or an aspectual marker marking progressive aspect (Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ 2012) or habitual aspect (Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ 2012). Yuka and Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ (2011:372) propose a present tense analysis for the low tone in Ẹ̀do stating that “... present tense is marked on the transitive CV verb stem as a low tone. On the transitive CVCV verb stems, it is reflected as low-low and a rising tone on transitive CVV”. This is illustrated in example (17) below.

17. (a) Ota lẹ̀ èvbàré
Ota cook.IPFV food
(Ota pres-cook food)
'Ota is cooking food'

(b) Úyì kpòlò òwá
Uyi sweep.IPFV house
(Uyi pres-sweep house)
'Uyi is sweeping the house'

(c) Ọ̀zó lẹ̀ọ́ úkpòn
Ozo iron.IPFV cloth
(Ozo pres-iron cloth)
'Ozo is ironing cloth'

Yuka and Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ (2011:342)

The sentences in (17) show verbs with the low tone (low (L) on C̀V (17a), LL on C̀VC̀V (17b) and rising on C̀V́V́ (17c) verb types) having a progressive reading, although they are glossed as present. This appears to be corrected later in the paper when they propose that “... progressive events are marked by both the low tone on CV verb stems; by low-low tones on CVCV stems and by a rising tone on CVV verb stems for present transitive derivations” (Ibid:375).

Omọrẹgbẹ (2012:160) claims that “the habitual aspect in Èdo is realized in three ways (a) simple habitual marked by low tone on the verb (b) past habitual marked by the verbal form *ghá!rá* and future habitual marked by *ghára*”. The examples in (18) were presented as evidence for this proposal.

18. (a) ọ̀ sò ìhuán
 3.SG sing.IPFV song
 (he pres-sing song)
 ‘He sings/He is singing’

(b) Úyì ghá!rá mwẹ́é íghó
 Uyi PST.PROG have money
 ‘Uyi used to have money’

(c) Òtábọ́ ghára lè èvbàré gié írán
 Otabọ́ FUT.PROG cook food PREP 3.PL
 (Otabọ́ fut-ASP cook food to them)
 ‘Otabọ́ will be cooking for them’

Omọrẹgbẹ (2012:161)

Example 18 (a) shows a low tone on a monosyllabic CV verb *sò* ‘sing’ having two interpretations – progressive and habitual. She accounts for this by proposing a covert progressive marker *ghá* in this sentence. As I demonstrate later in this chapter and in chapter 5, *ghá* is a prospective marker with a progressive reading available only with atelic verbs such as *so* ‘sing’.

I demonstrate with the following aspectual diagnostics that although it is easy to mistake imperfective aspect with present tense (because of some overlap in temporal semantics), they can be distinguished because imperfectives are expected to have both progressive and habitual interpretations.

As predicted by Comrie’s (1976:25) aspectual hierarchy, imperfective aspect is compatible with a habitual reading whereas present tense markers which encode only progressive aspect are not. For example, (19a) shows that the progressive aspect in

English (encoded by the suffix *-ing*) is incompatible with a habitual interpretation, while (19b) shows the temporal compatibility between the imperfective and a habitual reading in French.

English progressive

19. (a) *I was eating eggs for breakfast every morning.

French (France) imperfective

(b) Je mang-eais des oeuf-s chaque matin.
 1SG.NOM eat-IMPF.PST INDEF.PL egg-PL every morning
 'I ate eggs every morning'

As earlier shown, one of the interpretations of a low tone marked final syllable is a habitual reading. This is further illustrated in (20) below with sentences showing compatibility with habitual temporal adverbials.

20. (a) *Òróbòsà bọ òwá úkpò hià*
 Orobosa build.IPFV house year all
 'Orobosa builds houses every year'
 [Context: In response to the question 'How often does Orobosa build houses?']

(b) *Ìyòbọ gbèn èbé èdẹ hià*
 lyobo write.IPFV book day all
 'lyobo writes books everyday'
 [Context: In response to the question 'How often does lyobọ write books?']

(c) *Ímádé mọ ẹtó òwié hià*
 Imade weave.IPFV hair morning all
 'Imade weaves her hair every morning'
 [Context: In response to the question 'How frequently does Imade weave her hair?']

The possible grammatical cooccurrence between the low-tone final syllable and a habitual interpretation in Edo is an indication that it is an imperfective marker and not a present tense marker (Yuka and Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ 2008, 2011; Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ 2013) because the temporal semantics of the imperfective is broader than the present. In fact, Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀

(2012:142) validates this analysis when she states that “what we are calling present tense in Edo is actually present (tense), progressive and habitual which are aspectual. This analysis presents tense and aspect phenomena as inseparable”.

In summary, previous analysis of the low tone in Edo were based on the translation of verbs with the low tone. Hence, different interpretations (present, progressive, habitual) of this marker were proposed in isolation. I have shown that the low tone marks imperfective aspect in Edo as it encodes a progressive/continuous reading and a habitual interpretation. – a combination not associated with markers of either present tense or progressive/habitual aspect.

4.2.3 *ghá* Marks Prospective Aspect in Edo

The preverbal temporal marker *ghá* previously analyzed as the imperfect aspect marker by Agheyisi (1990) and as a future tense marker by Yuka and Omoręgbę (2011, 2012) is shown to be the prospective marker in Edo in this section. Comrie (1976:64) defines prospective aspect as, “a state ... related to some subsequent situation”. Dik (1997:239) argues that the difference between prospective aspect and future tense is that future tense states only that some situation occurs at a time after the present moment (i.e., ST), while prospective aspect states that the subsequent event has present.

According to Agheyisi (1990:79), “The imperfect is marked by the particle *ghá* ... the particle expresses the imperfect aspect of progressive”. She provides the sentence in example (21) below as evidence for this claim.

21. (a) *Òzó ghá kpòló*
Ozo PROSP sweep
(Ozo IMPF sweep)
'Ozo is sweeping'

Agheyisi (1990:79)

In the same vein, she argues that “in sentences with stative verbs, the future tense marker is the preverbal particle *gháá* ... However, with non-stative verbs, the future tense marker is *ghá*” (Agheyisi 1990:78). Examples 21(b) and 21(c) show her examples in support of these claims.

21. (b) *Òzó gháá mwèén íghó*
 Ozo PROSP have money
 (Ozo FUT have money)
 ‘Ozo will have money’

21.(c) *Òzó ghá rrè*
 Ozo PROSP come
 (Ozo FUT come)
 ‘Ozo will come’

Agheyisi (1990:78)

When *gháá* cooccurs with non-stative verbs, it expresses future-progressive (21d) while *ghá* with stative verbs encodes future-inchoative (21e).

21. (d) *Òzó gháá rrí evbare*
 Ozo PROSP eat food
 (Ozo T-A eat)
 ‘Ozo will be eating’

21.(e) *Òzó ghá mwèén íghó*
 Ozo PROSP have money
 (Ozo T-A have money)
 ‘Ozo will have money’ i.e., ‘Ozo will become rich.’

(Agheyisi 1990:78)

Agheyisi (1990:78-79) concludes that *ghá* “is more basically a mood particle serving to mark a wide range of irrealis meanings (IM) such as potential, obligation, optative etc.”. The sentences in (22) were provided to show the additional modal readings of *ghá*.

22. (a) *èdè ghá gbè vbè égógó ìsèn* (potential)
 day PROSP break ADP clock five
 (day IM break at clock five)
 ‘The day will break at 5 o’clock’

(b) *ízè (òré) ì ghá ré* (optative)
 Rice FOC 1.SG PROSP eat

- (rice FCI IM eat)
 'It is rice that I shall eat'
- (c) Té ù ghá rù iwinnà nìí (obligation)
 IRR 2.SG PROSP do job DEM
 (IM you IM do work that)
 'You will have to do that work' Agheyisi (1990:78-79)

First, it is not clear what Agheyisi's (1990) position is on the status of *ghá* because at different times, it is referred to as an imperfect(ive) marker (21a), future tense marker (21b and 21c), tense-aspect marker (21d and 21e) and an irrealis marker (22a, 22b and 22c).

I argue against the imperfect(ive) analysis because the habitual reading is not available to the temporal morpheme *ghá* unlike verbs affixed with the low tone. Since imperfective aspect is typically ambiguous between a progressive reading and a habitual interpretation (not progressive-prospective/irrealis), I argue that *ghá* is not an imperfective marker – instead as argued in section 4.2.2 the imperfective is marked by the low tone in Edo. I also argue that *ghá* does not mark future tense because a temporal marker that appears to be ambiguous between the progressive and future/prospective cannot be a tense marker (since tense is a deictic temporal relation, the future tense indicates that an event follows the speech time on the timeline). Lastly, I argue that *ghá* is not an irrealis marker. This is based on previous analyses as well as my observation that *ghá* is different from *ghà* (Agheyisi 1986; Omoreuyi 1991; Omoregbé 2012). While the former is a temporal marker which marks prospective aspect, the latter is a subjunctive¹² mood marker. According to Agheyisi (1986:57), *ghá* is a tense/aspect

¹² The choice to gloss *ghà* as the subjunctive is mine as Agheyisi (1986) simply translates it as 'if/when' for the conditional reading and 'would have' for the counterfactual interpretation.

particle that marks the present progressive and/or future tense (23a), while *ghà* is an auxiliary that marks conditionals (23b) and counterfactuals (23c).

23. (a) Ọ́ ghá viẹ
 3.SG PROSP cry
 (3.SG PROG/FUT cry)
 'He is crying/He will cry'
- (b) Ọ́ ghà rré, ù ghi rhié ne enren
 3.SG.NOM SUBJV come 2.SG COND give BEN 3.SG.ACC
 'If/when he comes, give it to him'
- (c) Akpawẹ i mwen igho, i ghà dẹ ọre
 COUNTF 1.SG have money 1.SG SUBJV buy 3.SG
 'If I had money, I would have bought it' Agheyisi (1986:57)

Ọmọruyi (1991:7-8) argues that both the mood and temporal readings of *ghá* should be treated as one morpheme – an aspectual auxiliary marker (AAM). He writes.

“The auxiliary *ghá* performs a variety of functions when it modifies verbs in sentences. When it bears a high tone and the verb it modifies bears a low tone, the aspect it marks ranges from the future to the present continuous...If, however the action expressed by the verb is unfulfilled, the tone borne by this AAM changes from high to low.”

He provides the sentences in (24a) and (24b) to illustrate the workings of this claim

24. (a) Ọ̀sàró ghá tiẹ èbé
 Osarọ PROSP read book
 (Osarọ AAM read book)
 'Osarọ will read/ is reading a book'
- (b) Ọ́sàró ghà tiẹ èbé¹³
 Osarọ MOD read book
 (Osarọ AAM read book)
 'Osarọ should have read a book' Ọmọruyi (1991:8)

¹³ Ọmọruyi (1991) claims that the high tone on the first syllable of the name *Osarọ* is as a result of tone shift following the deletion of the optional clause-initial particle *té*.

I agree with Agheyisi's (1986) proposal that *ghá* and *ghà* are different morphemes because they mark different grammatical functions. While the former marks a temporal grammatical function (prospective), the latter marks the subjunctive mood.

I argue that *ghá* marks prospective aspect because it is the default interpretation when elicited in out-of-the-blue contexts and it is the interpretation available to all verbs. When elicited in 'neutral' contexts i.e., without background information, e.g., 'what is the meaning of *Òsàrọ ghá tiè èbé?*' consultants provide the prospective reading. Only when asked if there are other possible interpretations, do they provide progressive/continuous reading. Secondly, the ambiguous reading of *ghá* is not available to all verbs. Example (35) shows that only the prospective interpretation is available for the verbs *digué* 'kneel' (35a) and *digiẹn* 'squat'.

25. (a) *Nòsá ghá digué*
Nosa PROSP kneel
1. # 'Nosa is kneeling'
2. 'Nosa is going to kneel'
- (b) *Nòsá ghá digiẹn*
Nosa PROSP squat
1. # 'Nosa is squatting'
2. 'Nosa is going to squat'

So, if *ghá* is a prospective marker, why then does it have a progressive reading with some verbs? Why is a progressive interpretation only available for some verbs and not others? What type of predicates license ambiguous reading and why? In the next chapter (chapter 5) of this dissertation, I show that these questions can be answered when an analysis considers the influence of the phasal structure of predicates. The ambiguous interpretation is only available to atelic predicates (i.e., activities cf. Vendler 1967). Other verb types do not license continuous interpretation because they do not

meet the above criteria, so will only receive the prospective reading. As earlier mentioned, the presence of true statives in Edo is doubtful but inchoative predicates are attested in Edo. Inchoatives are not atelic and so do not license the progressive interpretation in the context of *gha*.

In summary, the different analyses (imperfect(ive), future tense, modal) proposed for the prospective marker *ghá* stems from (i) relying on translation equivalents for decoding the temporal semantics of the marker (ii) not considering the impact of actionality on the temporal interpretation of predicates (as in the case of proposing *ghá* as an imperfective marker because it has a progressive reading in addition to a prospective reading with atelic verbs).(iii) failure to distinguish *ghá* the temporal marker from *ghà* the subjunctive marker (Omoruyi 1991). In this section, I have highlighted the sources of the different readings attributed to the prospective marker and argued why *ghá* is neither a future tense marker, imperfective/progressive marker nor a modal marker. It is not an imperfective/progressive marker because this interpretation is limited to atelic predicates, it is not a modal/mood marker because *ghá* is different from *ghà*, the former bears a high tone and is a temporal marker while the latter bears a low tone and is a mood/modal marker. I argue against the future tense analysis because it is unexpected that a tense marker which encodes a deictic temporal relation would be ambiguous between future and progressive as is the case with atelic verbs.

4.2.4 Suẹn-ghá ... nẹ marks inceptive aspect in Edo

The inceptive aspect encodes the beginning of an event or the temporal point prior to the beginning of an event. In some Bantu (e.g., Nyamwezi) and non-Bantu languages (e.g., Swedish), the inceptive is marked periphrastically by the translational

not entirely clear. I propose that it encodes some degree of certainty/expectation that the event will continue beyond the reference time (which is typically ST). The presence of *nẹ* is also not out of place in these constructions as it indicates that an event which began prior to the reference time, continues beyond the reference time and is relevant to the present.

The inceptive can have varied interpretations based on the actional characteristics of the predicate of the clause. This will be illustrated and discussed in more detail in the next chapter where I show how the phasal structure of predicates explain the temporal interpretations of different predicates in the context of aspectual markers. In example 27 (a), the inceptive marker in the context of an inchoative verb *fé* ‘be(come) wealthy’ indicates that the change of state has begun. The inceptive marker in 27(b) encodes the start of the event of counting bottles with the verb *ká* ‘count’. When the inceptive marker collocates with the verb *dígièn* ‘squat’, it produces a habitual/modal reading ‘X (can) now squat(s)’. These different interpretations will be used as the basis for a predicate classification schema in chapter 5.

4.2.5 *fò-nẹ* Marks the Terminative in *Èdo*

The phasal aspect marker *fò* occurs clause finally and literally means ‘finish’. However, its meaning and cooccurrence with *nẹ* ‘already’ depends on the actionality of the verb. The meanings attributable to *fò(nẹ)*¹⁵ include exhaustivity and terminativity.

28. (a) *Òsàsú gbé ẹwé fò*
 Osasu kill.FACT goat TERM
 ‘Osasu finished killing goats’

¹⁵ *Fò* is translated as ‘finish’ while *nẹ* translates to ‘already V=ed’. However, in the context of the terminative when both lexical items combine, the low tone on *fò* changes to a high tone, hence, *fó nẹ*.

[Context (appropriate): Osasu was instructed to kill goats, he killed all three so there was none left.]

- (a') Òsàsú gbé ẹwé fò-né
Osasu kill.FACT goat TERM
'Osasu finished killing goats'

[Context (appropriate): Osasu is done killing one or more goats because the goat(s) is dead hence the event has ended]

- (b) Àmẹzẹ kà ọgọ fò
Amẹze count bottle TERM
'Amẹze finished counting the bottles'

[Context: There were 50 bottles to be counted and Amenze counted all of them]

- (b') Àmẹzẹ ká ọgọ fò-né
Amẹze count bottle TERM
'Amẹze finished counting the bottles'

[Context: Amenze completed the task of counting bottles]

- (c) ọvbì mwẹ sàán fò *(né)
child POSS jump TERM
'My child has finished jumping'

[Context: Children are taking turns jumping on a trampoline, the speaker asserts that his/her child has completed her turn and will no longer partake in jumping]

- (d) ọdẹ nà wẹnrén fò *(né)
Road/path DEM narrow COMPL
'The road/path has become completely narrow'

[Context: The path cannot be narrow any further because grass has completely covered it]

In example 28(a), *fò* has an exhaustive interpretation with the accomplishment *gbé ẹwé* 'kill goat (s)'. It means *Osasu* killed goats until there were no more goats for him to kill. Although, this appears to be a terminative reading, the end-of-event is coerced from the exhaustive interpretation of *fò* on the accomplishment verb¹⁶. Example

¹⁶ This is not the case with all accomplishment verbs as *bọ ọwá* 'build house' for example only has the terminative reading and not the exhaustive one.

28(a') illustrates the combination of *fó* with *nẹ*. Here, we get a terminative reading as it means the goat-killing event has come to an end. The case is the same with accomplishment verbs such as *ká ọgọ* 'count bottles' – an exhaustive interpretation with *fó* (28b) and a terminative reading with *fó nẹ* (28b'). With verbs which encode punctuality such as achievement verbs, e.g., *sàán* 'jump' only the terminative reading is available and *fó + nẹ* is required for grammaticality (28c). Inchoative verbs are like achievements in their collocation with the terminative marker as they require both *fó + nẹ* for grammaticality. They however differ with respect to the interpretations available. While achievements have a terminative interpretation with *fó nẹ*, inchoatives have a present state (which has undergone a change) which can undergo no further change.

This is a pointer to how the actional phases encoded in a verb determine the interpretation of aspectual markers. In the next chapter, where verbs will be classified based on verb senses will be classified based on their interpretation in the context of aspectual markers/phasal polarity elements, the varied interpretations of *fó nẹ* will be shown to arise from aspect actionality-interactions.

4.2.6 *té* Marks the Counter-Expectation/'almost' in Edo

The pre-verbal (not clause-initial) phasal particle *té* is translated as 'almost' by Agheyisi (1986:142). However, I show that this particle could be ambiguous between an 'almost' reading and a counter-expectation interpretation i.e., the event took place, but the 'outcome' is atypical.

This pre-verbal particle was chosen for discussion because of its varied interpretations with different verbs – an indication of its potential in selecting different aspectual phases and hence sensitivity to actionality. The varied interpretations *té* has include (i) an event almost happened but did not because of some intervention before

its inception, (ii) the event occurred but with an unintended/unexpected outcome, (iii) the event started but was not completed (iv) a past state which no longer holds.

29. (a) Ọmọmọ té dé
Baby PART fall.FACT
'The baby almost fell'
[Context: The baby was about to fall from a platform but was prevented from falling by someone close by]

(b) ọ té wọn àmè
3.SG almost drink.FACT water

1. S/he almost drank the water
[Context: The person was about to drink the water when s/he found some dirt and then decided not to drink]
2. S/he drank the water but ...
[Context: The person drank the water but was not satisfied]

(c) ọsẹ mwèn té bọ òwá
friend POSS almost build.FACT house

1. 'My friend almost built a house.'
[Context: My friend started building the house but did not complete it]
2. 'My friend built a house but ...'
[Context: My friend built the house, but the house is too substandard to be considered a house]

(d) ọdẹ nà té wẹnrèn
Road/path DEM almost narrow
'The road was narrow'
[Context: The road was narrow but not anymore because of some intervention]

In example 29(a) with a punctual verb like *dé* 'fall', *té* is unambiguous. It means the event was about to take place but did not because of some external intervention that prevented it from taking place. With activity verbs, *té* induces an additional reading in addition to the 'almost' reading earlier pointed out. It encodes an event that took place but did not achieve the desired/expected result. So, in example 29(b), in addition to the 'almost' reading where the subject almost drank the water but was prevented from doing

so because of the dirt in it, the sentence is licensed by a context where the event occurred but did not achieve its desired purpose, which in the case of 29(b) is quenching the thirst of the subject. Example 29(c) shows the cooccurrence of *té* with accomplishment predicates illustrated here with the verb *bó òwá* ‘build.house’. Like activities, accomplishments also have two possible interpretations with *té*. The first is that the event began but was not completed/culminated. The second is that although the event was completed, it did not achieve the desired purpose (e.g., the house is too small or below the expected standards of what a house should be). Inchoative verbs with *té* encode a past state which no longer holds because of some external intervention. For example, 29(d) shows that the context which licenses the sentence is one where the road was narrow but has now been widened.

4.2.7 The Edo -rV suffix

In this section, I argue the -rV suffix marks completive aspect when suffixed to verbs. The suffix was previously analyzed as a simple past tense (Dunn 1968; Aikhionbare 1986; Agheyisi 1986; Omoreuyi 1991; Ogie 2008; Yuka and Omoregbè 2008, 2011), a perfective marker (Omoregbè 2013) and present perfect (Iyamu 2016). These three analyses have in common some ‘pastness’ – the simple past temporally locates a situation prior to speech time (ST), the perfective encodes the external view of a situation as bounded (closely related to ‘completeness’) and hence past, and the present perfect encodes the present discourse relevance of a past situation.

Omoreuyi (1991:2-3) claims that ‘the past tense suffixes basically refer to a completed action or state in relation to the time of utterance’. He describes the suffix as follows.

The underlying form of the simple past suffix is *-rè* but it is realized as *-rì*, *-rù* or *-rò* depending on the oral vowel that occurs in the verb stem. If the vowel in the verb stem is nasalized, the suffix is realized as *-rìn*, *-rùn* or *-rèn* ... They do not occur whenever a verb is followed by an object noun in sentence structure.

He provides the following examples to illustrate the observations.

30. (a) íghó wí-rì
 Money lose-PST
 'The money was lost'
- (b) ẹwé wú-rù
 goat die-PST
 'The goat died'
- (c) iyán zọọ-rè
 yam germinate-PST
 'The yam germinated'
- (d) Òzó vbiẹ-rè
 Ozo sleep-PST
 'Ozo slept'
- (e) Òsàsú dé-rè
 Osasu fall-PST
 'Osasu fell'
- (f) Iran rhàá-rè
 3.PL steal-PST
 'They stole'

The following sentences in (31) illustrate the occurrence of the simple past suffix when nasalized vowels occur in the verb stem.

31. (a) Òsàsú dín-rìn
 Osasu brave-PST
 'Osasu was brave'
- (b) ẹrò bùún-rùn
 knife break-PST
 'The knife broke'
- (c) àkhé vọn-rèn
 pot be.full-PST
 'The pot was full'
- (d) Òzó sàán-rèn

Ozo jump-PST
'Ozo jumped'

Ọmọruyi (1991:3)

Ọmọruyi further observes that some 'adjectival verbs' are incompatible with the past tense suffixes, hence the ungrammaticality of the sentences in 31.

32. (a) *Áyì khòrìọ̀n-rẹ̀n
Ayi be.ugly-CPL
'Ayi was ugly'
- (b) * Òzó mọ̀sẹ̀-rẹ̀
Ozo be.handsome/beautiful-CPL
'Ozo was handsome'
- (c) * Ò wẹ̀nrẹ̀n-rẹ̀n
3.SG be.slim-CPL
'S/he was slim'
- (d) * Írà̀n kọ̀lọ̀-rẹ̀
3.PL be.fat-CPL
'They were fat'

He accounts for the ungrammaticality of the sentences in (31) by arguing that because these verbs encode permanent attributes, they can only be pre-modified by a past-continuous auxiliary marker when these attributes have ceased to exist.

Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ (2012) claims that "the -rv suffix marks perfective aspect in the post-verbal positions of intransitive verbs ... The -rv suffix selects all simple verbs which do not subcategorize for object complements irrespective of any preverbal form or pure verbal modifying elements". The two major claims made here are (i) the -rV suffix marks perfective aspect and (ii) the suffix co-occurs only with intransitive verbs. These are discussed in turn.

(i) the -rV suffix marks perfective aspect: Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀' s evidence for arguing that the -rV suffix marks perfective aspect is based on the position the suffix occupies in the clause. She argues that in Èdo language, tense markers occupy the pre-verbal position

while aspectual markers are attested post-verbally. Since the -rV morpheme is a verbal suffix (hence occurring after the verb), it must be an aspectual marker. Although the position of an affix could be an indication of its status as a tense/aspectual marker, it is not a fool-proof diagnostic.

I also disagree that the -rV suffix marks perfective aspect based on evidence from the past-progressive auxiliary marker *ghárá*. This temporal marker can be decomposed into *ghá* earlier argued to be the prospective marker with two possible interpretations viz. progressive and prospective/potential. The second part of the past-progressive marker is the -rV suffix. Examples (33) below illustrates the past progressive in Edo.

33. (a) Òsàsú ghá-rá ká ògọ
 Osasu PROSP-PST count bottle
 'Osasu was counting bottles'
- (b) Ímádé ghá-rá bùún áró
 Imade PROSP-PST break eye
 'Imade was blinking'
- (c) ọ ghá-rá gbé ẹwé
 3.SG PROSP-PST kill goat
 'S/he was killing a goat'
- (d) Ékítá nà ghá-rá khóriọn
 dog DEM PROSP-PST be.ugly
 'This dog was ugly'
- (e) Òsàmédé ghá-rá fé
 Osamẹde PROSP-PST be.rich
 'Osamẹde was becoming rich'
- (f) * ẹsiá ghá-rá dámẹ
 morning.dew PROSP-PST liquefy

The examples in (33) show that the -rV suffix combines with the prospective marker to produce a past-progressive reading. A few observations to be made before discussing the varied interpretations of the past-progressive marker. First, *ghá* is

currently analyzed as a prospective marker with two possible interpretations – progressive and future/potential readings. However, in the context of the past-progressive, only the progressive interpretation is available. I propose that this is the case because while the progressive reading is compatible with a past interpretation, the future/potential reading of *ghá* is incompatible with the past interpretation when it co-occurs with the past marker – the -rV suffix. Secondly, the syllable-bearing unit of the -rV was shown to bear a low-tone. However, in the context of past-progressive marking, it bears a high-tone. I currently do not have a plausible explanation for the tonal alternation of the past marker in the context of past-progressive marking.

The past-progressive marker has three possible interpretations: (a) the past-progressive as shown in (33a-33c). (b) a past state that no longer holds as illustrated by example (33d). (c) a gradual change of state that occurred in the past. In addition to these interpretations, some predicates are incompatible with the past-progressive marker *ghára* (33f). In chapter 5, the varied readings will be shown to be because of the specific actional phases that are ‘activated’ when predicates of different classes co-occur with temporal markers.

(ii) the suffix cooccurs only with intransitive verbs: Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ (2013) claims that the -rV suffix which marks perfective aspect only co-occurs with intransitive verbs; in the case of transitive verbs, a past/complete event is encoded by the high-tone on the verb. She demonstrates the interaction between the -rV suffix and transitivity with the examples in (33) below.

34. (a) ọ̀ kpòlọ́ òwá nódẹ̀
 he past+sweep house yesterday
 3.SG sweep.FAC house yesterday
 ‘He swept the house yesterday’

- (b) ọ̀ kpòlò-rò
 he past+sweep+-rv
 3.SG sweep-CPL
 'He swept'
- (c) *Úyì dàá-rè àmẹ̀
 Uyi past+collect+rv water
 Uyi collect-CPL water
 'Uyi collected water'

I however disagree that the past-progressive marker only cooccurs with intransitive verbs. This is because this claim does not reflect the full range of co-occurrence possibilities of the -rV suffix which marks the completive in the language. At first glance, it appears the suffix only cooccurs with intransitive predicates as shown above and reinforced by other lexical examples presented without sentential or situational contexts as shown in 35 below.

verb	verb + suffix	gloss
35. (a) lẹ̀ẹ́ 'flee'	lẹ̀ẹ́ + rẹ̀ = lẹ̀ẹ̀rẹ̀	'fled'
(b) gọ́ 'shout'	gọ́ + rò = gọ̀rò	'shouted'
(c) sàán 'jump'	sàán + rẹ̀n = sàárẹ̀n	'jumped'
(d) giẹ́ 'laugh'	giẹ́ + rẹ̀ = giẹ̀rẹ̀	'laughed' (Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ 2012:)

However, in the same study, examples of transitive verbs which cooccur with the completive marker were provided, shown below as example (36).

verb	verb + suffix	gloss
36. (a) kọ́ 'plant'	kọ́ + rẹ̀ = kọ̀rẹ̀	'planted'
(b) fí 'throw'	fí + rì = fírì	'threw'
(c) gbẹ̀n 'write'	gbẹ̀n + rẹ̀n = gbẹ̀nrẹ̀n	'wrote'
(d) bùún 'break'	bùún + rùn = bùúnrùn	'broke' (Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ 2012:)

While the examples in (35) are intransitive verbs, those in (36) are transitive. There is no explanation for this contradiction in Ọmọ̀rẹ̀gbẹ̀ (2012). In fact, transitive verbs do cooccur with the -rV suffix. However, when this happens, the internal argument of the verb is focused as shown in 37 below.

37. (a) Òsàsú dé íbátà
 Osasu buy.FAC shoe
 'Osas bought a shoe'
- (a') íbátà nè Òsàsú dé-rè
 shoe FOC Osasu buy-CPL
 'The shoe that Osasu bought'
- (a'') * Òsàsú dé-rè íbátà
 Osasu buy-CPL shoe
- (b) Ímádé fí úgbé
 Imade throw.FAC stone
 'Imade threw (a) stone(s)'
- (b') ùgbé nè Ímádé fí-rì
 stone FOC Imade throw-CPL
 'The stone that Imade threw'
- (b'') * Ímádé fí-rì úgbé
 Imade throw-CPL stone
- (c) ọ wọn àmẹ
 3.SG drink.FAC water
 'S/he drank water'
- (c') àmẹ nè ọ wọn-rẹn
 water FOC 3.SG drink-CPL
 'The water that s/he drank'
- (c'') * ọ wọn-rẹn àmẹ
 3.SG drink.FAC water
- (d) Áísósà rhié èbé nè Ìvié
 Aisosa take.FAC book BEN Ivie
 'Aisosa gave Ivie a book'
- (d') *Áísósà rhié-rè èbé nè Ìvié
 Aisosa take-CPL book BEN Ivie
- (d'') *èbé nè Áísósà rhié-rè né Ìvié
 Book FOC Aisosa take-CPL BEN Ivie

Example (37) shows that for transitive verbs to co-occur with the past marker, the direct object of the verb must be focused as illustrated in (37a'), (37b') and (37c').

Ditransitive verbs do not license the past marker as demonstrated by example (37d'),

not even when the direct object of the verb is focused (37d’). Since the -rV completive marker is not compatible with all verbs, how then are past events encoded? The gap created because of the cooccurrence restriction between transitive verbs and the completive marker is filled by the factative (with dynamic verbs) as illustrated with (37a), (37b), (37c) and (37d).

Bybee et al (1994:57) defines completives as grams which encode “to do something thoroughly and completely”. They describe three ‘semantic nuances’ associated with completives. These are.

- (i) The object of the action is totally affected, consumed or destroyed by the action.
- (ii) The action involves an exhaustive/universal plural subject (in intransitive clauses) or object (in intransitive clauses).
- (iii) The action is reported with some emphasis or surprise value.

The -rV suffix proposed to be the incompletive aspect marker in Èdo encodes (i) and (iii) above. Evidence that the suffix encodes completeness comes from its incompatibility with *té* ‘almost’ while evidence for its emphatic meaning can be found in the different contexts that license the suffix (compared to the factative) as shown in example (38).

38. (a) Òsàsú dé
 Osasu fall.FAC
 ‘Osasu fell’
- (b) Osasu dé-rè
 Osasu fall.FAC-CPL
 ‘Osasu fell completely’
 [Context: Osasu fell very hard and was severely injured]
- (c) * Òsàsú té dé-rè

Intended: Osasu almost fell

4.4 Phasal Polarity (PhP) Items

In this section, I discuss two phasal polarity items in Edo, *nè/né* ‘already’ and *yéré* ‘still’. First, I define phasal polarity and highlight its peculiar characteristics in line with the literature. In subsections 4.4.1 and 4.4.2, I discuss two polarity items *nè* ‘already’ and *yéré* ‘still’ with respect to previous analyses, available readings and the polarity scenarios available to each marker. In chapter 5, these PhP items will constitute part of the evidence used to ‘diagnose’ the actional phases encoded in verbs.

Studies in PhP build on works of Vandeweghe (1983, 1992); Lobner (1989, 1985, 1986, 1987, 1990; Van Der Auwera 1993, 1991, 1997; van Baar (1997) and Kramer (2021) (for PhP elements in African languages) who propose that PhP items such as ‘already’, ‘still’, ‘not yet’ and ‘no longer’ are expressions which contrast a situation as encoded in the sentence with a conceivable alternative courses of events. Van Baar (1997:40) defines phasal polarity items as “...structured means of expressing polarity in a sequential perspective”. Based on this definition, he notes that there are three defining properties of PhP items viz.

- (a) Structured: They form a small paradigm as they can be distinguished from other expression types in the language (van Baar 1997:40-41).
- (b) Polarity: PhP expressions relate the presence/absence of a counterfactual situation at an earlier/later stage or a counterfactual situation simultaneous with speech time implicitly present in the discourse. These counterfactual situations are presupposed and are prominent in the discourse, the mind(s) of the speaker, addressee, or both. The counterfactual (alternative) situations

are 'evaluated' against the factual (real) situation expressed by the sentence (van Baar 1997:41).

- (c) Sequential: The polarity oppositions as discussed above are evaluated as sequential i.e. the counterfactual situations are considered either sequentially prior or sequel to the factual situation (van Baar 1997:41). For example, the use of the PhP item 'still' in the sentence 'John is still eating' indicates that in addition to the scenario in the situation depicted in the clause, the situation held immediately prior to topic time (TT) and there is a presupposition of the possibility of alternative scenarios where John is no longer eating or will no longer be eating.

PhP items morphologically diverse strategies which facilitate the encoding of three domains: phasal properties (inchoative, continuative, terminative), event polarity (the occurrence or otherwise of an event at ST) and speaker expectation (whether the time of occurrence of the event meets the speaker's expectation, occurred earlier than expected or later than expected).

Van der Auwera (1993b; 1997) proposed the 'double alternative' hypothesis which accounts for PhP elements in terms of the contexts which license their use. He argues that there are three possible 'scenarios' which license the use of PhP items. These are.

- (i) The neutral scenario: PhP items used in this context are used to contrast the actual situation with a counterfactual one. In this context, there is no additional implicature of the event occurring earlier or later than expected. This can be demonstrated from the example provided in van Baar (1997:27) for 'already'.

Context:

3 p.m. John and Peter have arranged to meet at Heathrow airport, in order to discuss some financial matters.

4 p.m. Peter will fly to Amsterdam.

5 p.m. Peter will arrive in Amsterdam.

Given this background context, imagine a scenario where because of a traffic jam, John is not able to reach Heathrow until 6 pm. In the neutral scenario, when John says “(Yes, I know) Peter is already in Amsterdam”, he is contrasting/evaluating the actual situation (his late arrival at the airport at 6 pm and Peter’s absence at the airport as a result of his arrival in Amsterdam) with an alternative counterfactual one (where John arrived the airport at 3 pm as earlier arranged and Peter was not yet in Amsterdam).

- (ii) The simultaneously counterfactual scenario: The use of PhP items in this scenario does not only indicate change (as is the case with (i) above) but early change. Consider the context where Peter left London at 1 pm and arrived in Amsterdam at 2 pm earlier than planned. John arrives at the airport at 3 pm to discover that Peter left London at 1 pm and arrived in Amsterdam at 2 pm, John can then say “(Damn) Peter is already in Amsterdam” to signify surprise at Peter’s (earlier than expected) arrival in Amsterdam. The expected scenario (which is also counterfactual) represents a polarity opposition with the actual situation.
- (iii) The non-simultaneously identical scenario: this scenario can be described as the opposite of scenario (ii) above. Here, the actual situation occurs later than

expected. For example, Peter leaves London at 5 pm instead of 3 pm as earlier arranged, John can then say at 7 pm “Peter is finally in Amsterdam”. Although ‘finally’ is used in English for this context, some languages like Spanish use the same word for all three scenarios. It will be shown later in this section that this is also the case with Edo.

Although the three scenarios which license PhP items were illustrated with ‘already’ and ‘finally’, they are ‘available’ to ‘no longer’ as well. However, the other PhP elements viz. ‘still’ and ‘not yet’ have only two scenarios available - scenario one (the neutral scenario) and scenario two (the simultaneously counterfactual/late scenario). This is as a result of the ‘illogical consistency’ of positioning both the actual and counterfactual situations either in the future (as is the case with ‘still’) or in the past (as is the case with ‘not yet’).

In the rest of this section, I discuss two PhP items *nẹ* ‘already’ (subsection 4.4.1) and *yèré* ‘still’ (subsection 4.4.2) as they will be relevant in the actional classification of verbs in chapter 5.

4.4.1 *Nẹ* ‘already’

The clause-final temporal marker *nẹ* has been a source of some controversy in the Edo literature. First, it is important to note that this morpheme has been previously analyzed as having two varieties – (i) *nẹ* (which translates to ‘X has V-ed already’) has been argued to be a perfective aspect marker (Dunn 1968; Agheyisi 1990; Omoreuyi 1991; Yuka and Omoregbẹ 2011; Omoregbẹ 2012) and (ii) *nẹ* (which translates to ‘X is V-ing already’) has been argued to be an imperfective marker by Yuka and Omoregbẹ (2008; 2011) and Omoregbẹ (2012). In this section, I propose that, *nẹ* marks ‘already’ . .

The presupposition of ‘already’ is that it contrasts a situation (+situation) with a possible alternative which has not come into existence. So, in the sentence ‘John has eaten already’, the situation of John eating (+eating) is contrasted with a possible situation where John has not yet eaten (-eating).

When *nẹ* combines with the factative in non-inchoative contexts, it results in a ‘past event with present relevance interpretation’ and when *nẹ* combines with imperfective aspect (marked by the low tone), it results in ‘an ongoing event with present relevance’ interpretation. The present relevance interpretation is because of the polarity opposition between ‘already’ and ‘not yet’.

As stated at the beginning of this sub-section, several authors have proposed that *nẹ* is a perfective marker including Dunn (1968), Agheyisi (1990), Ọmọruyi (1991), Yuka and Ọmọreğbẹ (2011) and Ọmọreğbẹ (2012). Example 38 below was presented in support of a perfective marker analyses for *nẹ*. A summary of their analyses and data presented as evidence for their claims are presented below.

Dunn (1968:6)

39. (a) i họn nẹ
 1.SG hear.FAC already
 (1.SG hear PFV)
 ‘I have heard’

Dunn (1968:6)

According to Agheyisi (1990:79-80), “The perfective marker is the particle *nẹ* which occurs post verbally ... expressing various aspectual meanings in the various contexts. With verbs in the past tense, it expresses completive meaning (i.e., the event is over and done with or the state has already been achieved)”

39. (b) Ọzó dé èbé né

Ozo buy.FAC book already
(Ozo bought book PERF)
'Ozo has bought a book'

Agheyisi (1990:80)

Omoruyi (1991)

"When an action or state was terminated before the time of speech, it is marked by the occurrence of *nẹ* 'already ... the verb bears a high tone because the action or state expressed by it is in the past'" Omoruyi (1991:5).

39. (c) Òzó wú nẹ
Ozo die already
(Ozo die already)
'Ozo has died'

Omoruyi (1991:5)

Yuka and Omoregbe (2011)

"Perfective aspect is marked by the overt post-verbal morphological form *nẹ* 'already' Yuka and Omoregbe (2011:18)"

39. (d) Ò lé èvbàré nẹ
3.SG cook.FAC food already
(he pst-cook food non-prog-already)
'He has already cooked food'

Yuka and Omoregbe (2011:18)

Omogbe (2012)

"Perfective aspect in Edo is marked by the overt post-verbal morphological form *nẹ* while imperfective is marked by its counterpart *nẹ́* both of which translate literally as 'already' Omogbe (2012:149-150)".

39. (e) ò rí èvbàré nẹ!
3.SG eat.FAC food IAM
(he past-eat food perf-already)
'He has eaten already'

Omogbe (2012:150)

Some observations with respect to the analyses presented above are that (i) they do not include the context(s) that license the use of *nẹ* in the examples provided (ii) the examples refer to events which precede Speech Time (ST) – typical of past/perfective events, (iii) except for Dunn (1968) and Agheyisi (1990), the literal translations contain the word 'already'. I propose in line with Omoruyi (1991), that *nẹ* is the phasal polarity

marker 'already' and the past interpretation of clauses with *nè* is because of its simultaneous marking with the factative (i.e. factative + *nè* = 'V-ed already').

It is not surprising that previous accounts have analyzed *nè* as a perfective marker since both the perfect and perfective are similar in that they both involve the temporal positioning of Event time (E) and Speech time (S). In the case of the perfect, the event time precedes the Reference time (R), (which happens to overlap with S in this instance) (i.e., E-R, S), whereas for the perfective, event time and reference time overlap, while preceding S – (i.e., E, R - S (Reichenbach 1947). This point is further buttressed by Nurse (2016:26-27) who highlights the similarities between the perfect, the perfective and the factative in the context of Niger-Congo languages, hence the confusion amongst the categories. He states that:

“It ought to be clear from what has been said so far about Perfective, Perfect, and Factative that they share areas of overlap so the differences and similarities need to be made clear .Perfective and Perfect both represent complete situations but whereas **Perfectives show no particular connection to the present** ('He lived in Lagos for twenty years', the implication being that he doesn't now), **Perfect representations do show such a connection** ('He has lived in Lagos for twenty years', the Implication being that he still does) (emphasis mine).

The analyses of *nè* as perfective can therefore be attributed to its 'complete' reading which has been shown to result from factative marking of the clauses in question.

Similarly, *né* has been argued to be the imperfective marker by Aghevisi (1990), Omoreuyi (1991), Yuka and Omoregbe (2008, 2011) and Omoregbe (2012) as shown below in 38.

Aghevisi (1990)

“With verbs in the present tense, it expresses inceptive meaning (i.e., the event has started to take place, or the state has started to exist)” Agheḃyisi (1990:80).

40. (a) Ozo dè èbé nẹ
 Ozo buy.IPFV book already
 (Ozo buy book PERF)
 ‘Ozo is already buying a book’ Agheḃyisi (1990:80)

Omoruyi (1991)

“The tone borne by this perfective marker (*nẹ*) changes from low to high if the action or state expressed by the verb began in the immediate or remote past but it has not terminated at the time of speech. In other words, *nẹ* marks the inception of an action or state in the past (Omoruyi 1981:5)”.

40. (b) Òsàsú tiè èbé nẹ
 Osasu read.IPFV book already
 (Osasu read book already)
 ‘Osasu has begun to read (a book)’

Yuka and Omoregbe (2011)

“The imperfective aspect is also marked by *nẹ* ‘already’ (Yuka and Omoreḃḃe 2011:18)”

40. (c) ọ kpòlò òwá nẹ
 3.SG sweep.IPFV house already
 (he pres-sweep house already)
 ‘He is already sweeping the house’ (Yuka and Omoreḃḃe 2011:18)

Omoregbe 2012

“Imperfective is marked by its counterpart *nẹ*. Both of which translates literally as ‘already’” Omoreḃḃe (2012:150).

40. (d) ọ dọlò ùkpọn nẹ
 3.SG sew.IPFV cloth already
 (he pres-sew cloth imperf-already)
 ‘He is sewing the cloth already’

Examples 40 (a-d) show that *nẹ* occurs in the context of imperfective marked verbs – the imperfective marked by the low tone on the last syllable of the verb is thus

the source of the ongoing interpretation. Hence, imperfective + already' results in a 'X is V-ing already'. The low tone on the verb is therefore the source of the imperfective reading and not *nẹ́*. I therefore propose that like *nẹ̀*, *nẹ́* marks the PhP element 'already' and the ongoing interpretation attributed to clauses which contain *nẹ́* are because of the verb being marked with the imperfective low tone not *nẹ́*. Currently, I am unable to account for the difference in prosodic form between *nẹ̀* and *nẹ́*.

The reason why *nẹ̀* was confused for the perfective is because it occurs in clauses which occurred in the past and are 'completed' in the case of non-inchoatives. However, with inchoatives, it yields a present state resulting from a change of state. Example (39) below shows data provided by previous authors as evidence for proposing that *nẹ̀* is a perfective marker in Edo. I have also provided the contexts that would license these sentences.

41.(a) *i họn nẹ̀*
 1.SG hear.FAC already
 (1.SG hear PFV)
 'I have heard'

Dunn (1968)

[Context: In response to someone currently being advised to mean 'all you said (past event) I will do']

[Context (inappropriate): I heard X say Y earlier this morning]

(b) *Òzó dẹ̀ èbé nẹ̀*
 Ozo buy.FAC book already
 (Ozo bought book PERF)
 'Ozo has bought a book'

Aghẹyisi (1990:80)

[Context: The speaker informing the hearer that Ozo has now (present) bought a book (past) after so much delay]

[Context (inappropriate): The speaker informing the hearer that Ozo bought a book two days ago]

(c) *Òzó wú nẹ̀*
 Ozo die.FAC already

(Ozo die already)
'Ozo has died'

Ọmọruyi (1991:5)

[Context: Ozo is dead (present) despite all that was done to help him recover to full health (past)]

[Context (inappropriate): Ozo died yesterday]

(d) Ọ lé èvbàré nẹ
3.SG cook.FAC food already
(he pst-cook food non-prog-already)
'He has already cooked food'

Yuka and Ọmọregbẹ (2011:18)

[Context: He cooked food (past) so there is no need to do so now (present)]

[Context (Inappropriate): He cooked food last week]

(e) ọ rrí èvbàré nẹ!
3.SG eat.FAC food already
(he past-eat food perf-already)
'He has eaten already'

Ọmọregbẹ (2012:150)

[Context: He ate (past) hence he is not hungry (present)]

[Context (inappropriate): He ate last night]

The sentences in example 39(a-d) show that the contexts that license clause final *nẹ* are those whose event times (E) are temporally located in the past, have discourse relevance to the present and are evaluated against a counterfactual situation hence exhibit phasal polarity. Events which encode past interpretation only (without current discourse relevance or phasal polarity) are infelicitous with *nẹ*. In example (39a), it is infelicitous to use this sentence to encode only that the 'hearing' event is contained in a temporal frame preceding the reference time (R) which in this case overlaps with the speech time of the sentence utterance i.e., S and R overlap. Instead, the temporal context which licenses the utterance is one where E precedes R and is discourse-

relevant to it. This also applies to examples (39b) to (39e) where *nẹ* is licensed by contexts that ‘link’ a past event with the present/speech time.

In terms of phasal polarity, *nẹ* is compatible with all three possible scenarios that license the use of PHP items. This is illustrated with example (42) below.

Context: Imade knows that Osasu eats his lunch at 2 pm every day.

Scenario 1 (neutral scenario): Imade visits Osasu at 2pm and meets Osasu eating his lunch. Imade can then say.

42.(a) Òsàsú rri èvbàré nẹ
Osasu eat.IPFV food already
‘Osasu is eating already’

In this scenario, Imade expects Osasu to be eating his lunch at 2 pm. The real situation occurs neither earlier nor later than expected. The actual situation is contrasted with one where Osasu is not yet eating his lunch.

Scenario 2 (the simultaneously counterfactual scenario): In this scenario, Imade visits Osasu at 1 pm and finds him eating his lunch, Imade can then say

42.(b) (ẹ̀mwántà) Òsàsú rri èvbàré nẹ
(truth) Osasu eat.IPFV food already
‘(really), Osasu is eating already’

In this scenario, the actual situation (i.e. Osasu eating lunch at 1 pm) is evaluated against two counterfactual situations: John eating lunch at 2 pm and John not yet eating lunch. The speaker also expresses surprise at the ‘earlier than expected’ event.

Scenario 3 (the non-simultaneously identical scenario): Imade visits Osasu who is sick. As a result of ill health Osasu did not eat his lunch at 2 pm. After some persuasion, Osasu begins to eat at 4 pm. Imade can then say.

42.(c) Òsàsú rri èvbàré nẹ
Osasu eat.IPFV food already

‘Osasu is eating, finally.’

In this scenario, the actual situation (i.e. Osasu eating at 4 pm) contrasts with Osasu not eating and Osasu eating at 2 pm. The speaker also expresses some form of ‘relief’ at the eventual occurrence of the situation.

In the same vein, factative + *nẹ* licenses all three scenarios compatible PhP items. To illustrate this, I present a context where Imade is to meet Osasu at home at 2 pm, Osasu is expected to depart Benin for Lagos at 3 pm. Osasu is expected to arrive in Lagos at 4 pm.

Scenario 1 (neutral scenario): Imade experienced some delay and arrives late at Osasu’s house at 5 pm. Imade can then say.

43. (a) Òsàsú sẹ Èkó nẹ
Osasu arrive.FAC Lagos already
(I know) ‘Osasu has arrived in Lagos already’

In this scenario, Imade evaluates the actual situation (i.e. Osasu’s arrival in Lagos) against a counterfactual situation (Osasu has not yet arrived in Lagos). There is no expression of ‘surprise’ at the ‘earlier-than- expected’ event occurrence as is the case with scenario 2 or expression of ‘relief’ at the ‘eventual-occurrence’ of as is the case with scenario 3.

Scenario 2 (the simultaneously counterfactual scenario): Osasu left earlier than initially planned at 12 noon and arrives in Lagos at 1 pm. Imade arrives at Osasu’s house at 2 pm only to find out that Osasu left at noon. Imade can then say.

43. (b) Òsàsú sẹ Èkó nẹ
Osasu arrive.FAC Lagos already
(So) ‘Osasu has arrived in Lagos already’

In this scenario, the actual situation (Osasu's arrival in Lagos at 1 pm) is contrasted with two counterfactual situations (Osasu not yet arrived in Lagos and Osasu's arrival in Lagos at 4 pm). As is characteristic of scenario 2, the actual situation occurred earlier than expected.

Scenario 3 (the non-simultaneously identical scenario): Osasu was delayed in Benin and was unable to depart for Lagos at 3 pm as earlier agreed. Instead, his flight left Benin at 5 pm and he arrived in Lagos at 6pm. He calls Imade at 7 pm to inform her of his arrival in Lagos at 6 pm. Imade can then say.

43. (c) Òsàsú sé Èkó nẹ
 Osasu arrive.FAC Lagos already
 'Osasu has arrived in Lagos finally'

In this scenario, the actual situation (Osasu's late arrival in Lagos at 6 pm) is evaluated against the counterfactual situation where Osasu left Benin at 4 pm and arrived in Lagos at 5 pm. The actual situation occurs later than expected and is posterior to the counterfactual situation.

Example (44) shows inchoative verbs in the context of the factative. As indicated by the contexts which license these sentences, *nẹ* in the context of inchoatives + factative encodes a result state with present relevance. In (44a) the speaker is not only asserting that 'the cloth is faded' but also that the result state following the change requires some present action – not putting on the shirt for example. In (44b), the yam cannot be cooked (present relevance) because it is rotten (current result state).

44. (a) úkpòn nà fàfá nẹ
 cloth DEM fade.FAC already
 'The cloth is faded (now)'

[Context: The speaker is suggesting to the hearer that because the cloth is faded (present result), it should not be worn (now)]

44. (b) ìnyá nè ò yè úkónì kèké nè
yam REL PRO LOC kitchen be.rotten already
'The yam in the kitchen is rotten'

[Context: The speaker informing the hearer about the current state of the yams and hence why they cannot be cooked]

When *nẹ* occurs in the context of imperfective + non-inchoatives, the interpretation is 'an ongoing situation with present relevance'. Situations that only encode continuous events such as an out-of-context 'what is X doing' is infelicitous in this context as shown in (45).

45. (a) Òsàsú lè èvbàré né
Osasu eat.IPFV food already
'Osasu is already eating'

[Context: The speaker's response to a request to invite Osasu to join an ongoing eating event]

[Context (Inappropriate): The speaker's response to the question 'what is Osasu doing?']

45. (b) Òsazẹ fí úgbé nẹ
Osazẹ throw stone already
'Osazẹ is already throwing stones'

[Context: In response to a request to the speaker to warn Osazẹ not to throw stones]

[Context (inappropriate): In response to the question 'what is Osazẹ doing?']

45. (c) ó khiàn yè èsúkù nẹ
3.SG walk to school already
'S/he is already walking to school'

[Context: The speaker is advising the hearer that there is no need to give the person in question a ride because s/he is headed to school on foot]

[Context (inappropriate): In response to the question 'what is s/he doing?']

In (45a), the eating event is ongoing, and the speaker is directed to invite Osasu to join in the meal. The speaker's response not only indicates that Osasu is currently

engaged in the act of eating (the progressive element of the event) but also that the need for Osasu's invitation to the meal is no longer necessary (the discourse relevance element of the event) since he is eating somewhere else. Example (45b) shows that the need to warn Osazę to stop throwing stones is no longer necessary (as it is too late) since he is currently engaged in the act. In other words, the progressive event (throwing stones), invalidates the warning not to throw stones (discourse relevance). In example (45c), the speaker informs an interlocutor that a discourse salient subject is currently walking to school (the progressive element of the event) hence invalidating the need to give him/her a ride (discourse relevance).

The context which licenses the use of *nę* also supports the analysis that it does not encode imperfective aspect. Imperfective aspect encodes a temporally unbounded, event-internal perspective of an event. It is therefore an appropriate response to a question eliciting a temporally unbounded response (progressive or habitual). Example 45 once again shows that clause-final *nę* is unacceptable with questions such as 'what is X doing?' or 'what does X do?' as would be expected of an imperfective marker.

In summary, I propose that *nę* (both *nę* and *nę*) marks the PhP item 'already' for two reasons (i) it's use in all three scenarios that are compatible with phasal polarity elements (ii) the presence of aspectual markers (the factative in the case of *nę* and imperfective in the case of *nę*) in *nę* clauses which 'bear' the 'aspectual load' of the clause. Hence, the previous analyses as perfective and imperfective aspect respectively failed to account for the phasal polarity characteristics of *nę* but instead proposed an aspectual analysis which is inadequate because grammatical aspect in the clauses containing *nę* were already marked by the factitive and imperfective.

4.4.2 yèré ‘still’

The persistive aspect encodes an event that started before UT and is still ongoing. According to Nurse (2008:145), the persistive encodes an event that “has held continuously since an implicit or explicit point in the past up to the time of speaking”.

In Èdo the PhP item ‘still’ is marked by *yèré* while *yé* is a concessive marker which translates to ‘X still V-ed even though ...’. Faller (2020:235) defines concessivity as “an essentially modal notion: the actual world does not conform to contextual assumptions, expectations or priorities”. In other words, “if p then normally not q” (Konig and Eisenberg 1984; Konig 1986). The concessive is marked by preverbal *yé* (46a, 46b and 46c), while the persistive is marked by *yèré* (46a’, 46b’, 46c’) resulting in a ‘X is still V-ing’ interpretation.

46. (a) *Ímádé yé gbè èwé*
Imade CONC kill goat
‘Imade still killed a goat’
[Context (appropriate): Despite warnings to the contrary. Imade still went ahead to kill a goat]
- (a’) *Òsàsú yèré gbé èwé*
Osasu PERS kill goat
1. ‘Imade is still killing a goat’
[Context: The speaker is complaining that Imade is taking too long in the event]
2. ‘Imade still kills goats’
[Context: Imade kills goats as a profession and the speaker is asserting that Imade hasn’t changed professions]
- (b) *Àdésúwà yé gbèn èmwí*
Adesuwa CONC write thing
‘Adesuwa still wrote’
[Context: Adesuwa still wrote despite warnings not to write]
- (b’) *Àdésúwà yèré gbèn èmwí*
Adesuwa PERS write thing
‘Adesuwa is still writing’
[Context: The speaker asserts that Adesuwa began writing before ST and is still doing so]

(c) Òzó yé buún áró
Ozo CONC break eye
'Ozo still blinked'
[Context: Ozo was advised not to blink because of glue on his eyelids but he still did so]

(c') Òzó yèré buún áró
Ozo PERS break eye
1. 'Ozo still blinks'
[Context: Despite Ozo becoming blind he still blinks]
2. 'Ozo is still blinking'

(d) òdé nà yé wẹ̀nrẹ̀n
Road/path DEM CONC narrow
'The road still became narrow'

(d') òdé nà yèré wẹ̀nrẹ̀n
Road/path DEM PRS.PERS narrow
'The road/path is still narrow'

With accomplishments such as *gbé ẹ̀wẹ́* 'kill a goat', *yé* has a past concessive reading (46a) while *yèré* is ambiguous between a persistive continuous interpretation and a persistive habitual interpretation (46a'). When *yé* collocates with activity verbs such as *gbẹ̀n ẹ̀mwí* 'write', it yields a past concessive reading (46b) while *yèré* with activities yields a persistive continuous interpretation (46b'). With semelfactive verbs such as *bùún áró* 'blink', *yé* has a past persistive reading (46c), whereas with *yèré*, it is ambiguous between a persistive habitual and a persistive continuous interpretation (46c'). Inchoative predicates have a persistive change of state interpretation with *yé* (46d) but a persistive state (i.e., a change-of-state that occurred despite efforts to prevent the change) with *yèré* (46d').

As a PhP item, 'still' is compatible with only the first two scenarios (i.e. the neutral and simultaneously counterfactual scenarios) that license phasal polarity items. To illustrate the contexts which license the use of *yèré*, I will reuse the context provided for

nẹ where Imade is expected to meet with Osasu at 2 pm, Osasu is scheduled to leave Benin at 3 pm and arrive in Lagos at 4 pm.

Scenario 1 (the neutral scenario): Imade arrives Osasu's house and is told Osasu is expecting him and has not left for Lagos. Imade can then say.

47. (a) Òsàsú yèré r̀ré Èdó
Osasu PERS EXIST Benin
(Yes, I know) 'Osasu is still in Benin'

In this scenario, the factual situation (Osasu's presence in Benin) is contrasted with a counterfactual situation where Osasu is no longer in Benin. Like scenario 1 of *nẹ* 'already' the factual situation neither occurs earlier nor later than expected. However, scenario 1 of *yèré* 'still' differs from scenario 1 of *nẹ* as the counterfactual situation of the former is sequentially ordered after the factual situation whereas the counterfactual situation of the latter, is sequentially ordered prior to the factual situation.

Scenario 2 (the simultaneously counterfactual scenario): In this scenario, Imade experiences some delay and does not arrive at Osasu's house until 4 pm and finds Osasu missed his flight and was unable to travel to Lagos at 3 pm. On realizing that Osasu did not travel. Imade can then say.

47. (b) Òsàsú yèré r̀ré Èdó
Osasu PERS EXIST Benin
(So) 'Osasu is still in Benin'

In this scenario, the factual situation (Osasu's presence in Benin at 4pm) is contrasted with two counterfactual situations (Osasu no longer present in Benin but in Lagos). This second scenario of *yèré* differs from that of *nẹ* in that the former is licensed by a 'later than expected' scenario while the latter is licensed by an 'earlier than expected scenario'.

Like the *nẹ*, the persistive marked by *yé* and *yèré* are also PhP items. *Ye* has a terminative phase (indicating X V-ed but no longer in progress), positive polarity (the event came into existence) and implicates an event that occurred later than the speaker expected. On the other hand, *yèré* has a continuative phase in terms of aspectual polarity, positive polarity (the same event began at an adjacent time and continues up until ST (and possibly into the future)) and neutral with respect to encoding the speaker's expectation.

In chapter 5, these varied interpretations associated with the persistive will be shown to emanate from how the actional phases encoded in verbs 'shift' and subsequently influence the semantics of the phasal polarity item in *Èdo*.

4.4 Summary and Conclusion

In this chapter I presented an account of the Tense-Aspect system of the *Èdo* language. First, I presented the work of previous scholars and highlighted some disagreements with respect to some temporal markers. For example, it was argued that the past tense was marked by the high tone and the -rV suffix, the low tone was said to mark imperfective aspect and the present tense, while the perfective was said to be marked by *nẹ*, the high-tone and the -rV suffix. Previous analyses of the temporal marking system as well as the analysis proposed in this dissertation are presented in Fig. 4-1 below.

	Dunn 1968	Aikhionbare 1986	Aghevisi 1986	Aghevisi 1990	Omoruyi 1991	Omozuwa 2003	Ogie 2008	Yuka & Omogbe 2008	Yuka & Omogbe 2011	Omogbe 2012	Present study
PST	HT	-rV	-rV	-	-rV	HT	-rV	-rV	-rV	HT	-
PFV	nè	-	-	nè	nè	-	-	nè	HT and nè	-rV/nè!	-
IPFV	Unmarked	-	-	-	-	-	-	nè	nè	nè	LT
PRS	-	-	-	-	-	LT	-	LT	LT	LT	-
FUT	ghá	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	gha	ghá	-
HAB	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	LT	-
PROG	ghá/ghaa	-	-	gha	-	-	-	-	-	LT	-
FAC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	HT
PROSP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ghá
'already'	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	nè/nè
PERS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	yèé
INCEP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	suén ghà
TERM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	fó(nè)
'almost'	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	te
COMP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-rV

LT = Low tone
HT = High tone
-rV = r + vowel
! = Downstep HT
_ = not proposed/discussed in study

Figure 4-1: Previous and present analyses of the TA marking system in Èdo

One of the aims of this study is to classify verbs based on their aspect-actionality interaction. It was therefore important to first present a unified analysis of the TA marking system in the language. This was done by proposing that the HT marks the factative (a temporal category not previously proposed, but typologically available in closely related languages), the -rV suffix marks completive, the low tone marks imperfective, *ghá* marks prospective aspect and *nè/nè* are Php items that translate to ‘already’ – the former marking the present perfect while the latter marks the iterative. I also show that Èdo is an aspect prominent language as it has just one tense marker – the -rV suffix.

This chapter sets the stage for the next chapter where the temporal marker discussed here will be used as diagnostics to classify verb senses, following the bidimensional approach to actional classification of verbs. There it will be shown how different temporal markers have different readings in the context of different verbs. This may be the reason why some previous accounts were unable to ‘pin’ a single analysis to some of the markers. Discussing the various readings of temporal markers will

highlight how the actional phases encoded in verbs contribute to the different interpretations associated with each temporal marker.

CHAPTER 5 AN ACTIONAL CLASSIFICATION OF ẸDO VERBS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the classification of predicates in Ẹdo based on their actional properties. The classification schema is based on the actional phases encoded by the predicates as well as characteristics of these phases (i.e., whether the phase in question is punctual, durative, or inchoative). The analysis is done following Botne and Kershner's (2000) bidimensional approach to actionality in which the co-occurrence (or otherwise) of grammatical aspectual markers (e.g., perfective, imperfective etc.) with predicates as well as the temporal interpretations arising thereof serve as diagnostic tools to identify the actional classes in the language.

The chapter is organized as follows. In section 5.2 I present some background information relevant to follow the discussion on actional classification as analyzed in this study. Section 5.3 discusses the temporal markers which will be used to demonstrate the actional phases encoded in Ẹdo verbs. These temporal markers were earlier discussed in detail in chapter 4 where I presented alternative analyses of the temporal marking system of Ẹdo. I will discuss the phases selected by each aspectual/temporal marker and whether the marker indicates the presence of a punctual/durative nucleus phase or inchoative nucleus. Section 5.4 builds on the discussion of the diagnostics earlier discussed to specify the actional classes present in Ẹdo based on the diagnostics presented. It will illustrate how different aspectual diagnostics are utilized in classifying verbs which will be shown to have implications for the grammar of the language. Section 5.5 summarizes and concludes the chapter.

5.2 Actional Classification in Edo: Some Background Introduction

In this section, I provide relevant background information required to understand the actional classification schema of verbs adopted in this study. The section will discuss theoretical assumptions, a preview of the actional classes proposed for Edo and the phasal composition of verb classes proposed.

As earlier pointed out in chapter 2, Vendler's (1957) four-way classification of verbs in the English language into states, achievements, activities, and accomplishments has served as the start-point of classification schemas based on the inherent temporal meaning of verbs. However, there have been several modifications to Vendler's initial proposal. For example, Smith (1991) adds 'semelfactives' to Vendlerian classes, while Van Valin and LaPolla (1997) add 'active accomplishment' to the four classes initially proposed. These modifications have come to be known as neo-Vendlerian theories of actionality. For this study, Vendler's initial characterization of states, activities, achievements and accomplishments in terms of the semantic primitives [+/- stative/dynamic], [+/- punctual/durative] and [+/- telic] is adopted when reference is made to these classes. The classification schema adopted in this dissertation however differs from that of Vendler/neo-Vendlerian approaches in that I classify verbs based on the temporal phases encoded by verbs and the properties of the phases encoded as made explicit by their combination with grammatical aspect. The (neo) Vendlerian approaches are based solely on the three semantic primitives earlier mentioned.

This dissertation adopts Botne and Kershner's (2002) approach to actional classification which proposes that verbs can be classified based on the actional phases they encode. The phases that verbs encode can be diagnosed by the co-occurrence

restrictions/variation in interpretation verbs receive when they combine with temporal/aspectual markers and other actionality sensitive particles. The choice of this theory is motivated by its robustness in accounting for actional phenomena in Niger-Congo languages. The theory has been applied in the actional classification of languages such as - Sukwa (Bantu, M.20) in (Kershner (2002), Yeyi (Bantu, R.41) in Seidel (2008), Totela (BantuK.41) in Crane (2011, 2013), Lusekelo (2016) for Swahili (Bantu G.42), Persohn (2017b) for Nyakyusa (Bantu, M.31) and Gunnink (2018) for Fwe (Bantu, K.402).

Actional classes encode one or more of the following actional phases – onset, nucleus, and coda shown in Fig. 5-1. The nucleus is always obligatory while the onset and coda may or may not be encoded in a verb class.

Figure 5-1: Phase representation

Onset (O)	Nucleus (N)	Coda (C)
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The nucleus encodes the core actional character of the predicate – every predicate has a nucleus. The other 2 actionality primitives, the onset and coda may be optional. The optionality or otherwise of these phases is not determined apriori but based on the results of applying actionality diagnostics to the predicates in question. The onset represents the pre-nucleus phase also known as the ‘coming-to-be’ phase while the coda represents the post-nucleus phase also known as the ‘result state’ phase.

Èdo verbs are classified into two broad categories in this study viz inchoatives and non-inchoatives. Inchoatives are verbs which encode a change-of-state nucleus and a result state coda. Non-inchoatives do not encode a change of state nucleus + a

result state coda. Inchoatives are further sub-divided into durative inchoatives and punctual inchoatives. Durative inchoatives encode a coming-to-be onset phase in addition to a change-of-state nucleus phase + a result-state coda phase. Punctual inchoatives differ from durative inchoatives in that they do not encode a coming-to-be onset phase. The sub-class of non-inchoatives is sub-divided into duratives, accomplishments and achievements. Duratives encode a durative nucleus phase without onset or coda phases. Duratives are further sub-divided into activities which encode a durative, atelic nucleus phase and series which encode multiple instances of an event in the nucleus. Accomplishments are verbs which encode a durative nucleus phase + a coda phase (the culmination of the event). Achievements encode a punctual nucleus with neither an onset nor a coda phase. Section 5.3 discusses the diagnostics used in identifying the phasal components of each of these classes/sub-classes while section 5.4 discusses each class in more detail.

5.3 Diagnostics for Actional Classes in Edo

The importance of tests in identifying actional classes has never been in question. However, the approach adopted in applying these tests has varied. While some have proposed a universalist approach in the diagnosis and classification of predicates across languages (Dowty 1979), others have argued for a more parametric approach where diagnostics are identified and applied based on the aspectual peculiarities of individual languages (Tatevosov 2002). This study adopts the bidimensional and parametric approach i.e. classifying predicates based on their interaction with temporal particles, grammatical aspect, and phasal polarity items in the Edo language.

In the following subsections, I specify the phases selected by each temporal marker and if the phase(s) in question is durative in nature or encodes a change and/or a result state. This will be determined by the co-occurrence restrictions between predicates and aspectual markers as well as the temporal readings available as a result of this aspect-actionality interaction.

5.3.1 The Factative

In section 4.2.1 of chapter 4, I argued that the high tone on the last syllable of the verb marks the factative. This was based on evidence that this prosodic marker has two possible readings – a present state reading and a past reading. I propose that the factative serves two actionality functions in the Edo language – It serves to classify predicates into two broad categories (inchoatives and non-inchoatives). The factative also indicates that an inchoative predicate encodes a present result-state as shown by the present reading obtained with inchoative verbs compared to a past interpretation with non-inchoative verbs.

Evidence that the factative marker serves to categorize verbs into two broad categories comes from the opposing readings predicates marked with the factative receive. Some verbs receive a present state interpretation (1a and 1b), while others have a past interpretation (1c). Verbs that have a present-result-state interpretation with the factative belong to the inchoative class of verbs while those that do not have this interpretation in the context of the factative are non-inchoative verbs. The fact that the same marker can achieve polar temporal readings is therefore taken as evidence for two broad categories of verbs in the language.

1. (a) ùkpón nà fàfá
cloth DEM fade.FAC
'This cloth is (now) faded' (i.e., the cloth transformed into a faded state)

(b) Ìyóbósà m̀osé
lyobosa beautiful. FAC
'lyobosa is beautiful'

(c) Òsàsú dé èbè
Osasu buy.FAC book
'Osasu bought (a) book(s)'

Secondly, the present-result state reading available with some verbs indicates that the verbs in question encode a coda (i.e., the result state following the change from a previous state). For such verbs, the factative can be said to 'highlight' the result state after the change of state has occurred. For example, (1a) shows that the cloth is in a faded state following the change from a state where the cloth was not faded. Evidence that we are dealing with the factative is found in the observation that the result state interpretation is not available to all verbs, when marked with the factative as shown in example (2).

2. (a) ómómó kú
baby play. FAC
i. 'The baby played'
ii. # 'The baby is now in a playful state'
- (b) Òsàsú dé
Osasu fall.FAC
i. 'Osasu fell'
ii. # 'Osasu is now in a fallen state'
- (c) Ímádé bọ òwá
Imade build.FAC house
i. 'Imade built a house'
ii. # 'The house is now built'

Example 2 shows that Vendlerian activities (2a), achievements (2b) and accomplishments (2c) do not license a present result state interpretation. I propose that the reason why a present result interpretation is not available for these verbs is because they do not encode a state which can be selected by the factative.

5.3.2 The Imperfective

The imperfective aspect in Edo is marked by the low tone on monosyllabic verbs and the final syllable in disyllabic verbs. In chapter 4, I argued in favor of an imperfective aspect analysis for this marker because it has habitual reading as one of its interpretations. The imperfective aspect as an actionality diagnostic in Edo serves as a test to identify predicates which encode a durative nucleus.

Evidence that the imperfective aspect in Edo indicates that punctual inchoatives in the language do not encode a durative nucleus comes from its incompatibility with inchoative predicates. In general, predicates marked with the imperfective aspect have an on-going or habitual interpretation as shown in (3).

3. (a) *néné òkhuò rri ízè*
DET woman eat.IPFV rice
(i) The woman is eating rice [right now].
(ii) The woman eats rice [as a habit].
- (b) *Ìvié mò ètó*
Ivie weave.IPFV hair
(i) Ivie is weaving her hair [right now]
(ii) Ivie weaves her hair [regularly as a habit]
- (c) *òhuẹn tọlọ Ẹfọmọ*
cough itch.IPFV Ẹfọmọ
(i) 'Ẹfomo is coughing' [multiple coughing events not one cough]
(ii) 'Ẹfọmọ coughs' [whenever she inhales smoke]
- (d) *Ẹsọhẹ tótà*
Ẹsọhẹ sit.IPFV
(i) 'Ẹsọhẹ is seated' [i.e. Ẹsọhẹ sat and is still seated]
(ii) # 'Ẹsọhẹ is in the process of sitting'
- (e) * *òkhuó nà mọ̀sẹ̀*
woman DEM beautiful.IPFV
Intended: 'This woman is beautiful'
- (f) * *ìnyán nìí kẹ̀kẹ̀*
yam DEM rotten.IPFV
Intended: 'That yam is rotten'

In example (3a), both the ongoing and habitual readings are available when the activity verb *rri ízẹ* ‘eat rice’ combines with the imperfective. The availability of the ongoing reading is an indication that the verb encodes a durative nucleus. Accomplishments like *mó ẹ́tọ́* ‘weave hair’ encode a durative nucleus phase leading to a culmination (the coda) as illustrated with example (3b). Just as with activities, the imperfective aspect selects this durative phase to produce an ongoing interpretation in addition to a habitual one. Example (3c) shows that semelfactive verbs like *tọ́lọ ọ́huẹ́n* ‘cough’ have an iterative reading in the context of the imperfective. The iterative reading of semelfactives when they co-occur with imperfective aspect indicates that they encode a durative phase. However, unlike activities and accomplishments, they have an iterative interpretation instead of an ongoing one. Verbs which encode event repetition in the context of the imperfective will be known as “series”, following Kanijo’s (2019) work on actionality in Nyamwezi. Verbs which do not encode a durative nucleus phase for example ‘posture’ verbs such as *tọ́tá* ‘sit’ as in example (3d), have a present ‘position’ reading when combined with imperfective aspect. Predicates which encode result-states (e.g. the coda phase of inchoatives as shown with (3e) and (3f)) are incompatible with the imperfective aspect in Edo.

5.3.3 The Inceptive + prospective

The inceptive aspect in Edo is marked by the phasal verb particle *suẹ́n* ‘start/begin’. However, *suẹ́n* occurs alone only with nominalized/gerundived verbs; in other contexts, it precedes the prospective marker *ghá* as shown in (4).

4. (a) *íràn suẹ́n ì-gbìnnà*
 3.PL INCEP NOM-fight
 ‘They have started fighting’
- (b) *íràn suẹ́n ghá gbìnnà*

3.PL INCEP PROSP fight
'They have started fighting'

- (c) * íràn suẹn gbínná
3.PL INCEP fight
Intended: 'They have started fighting'

The inceptive aspect denotes an event that has just begun. Depending on the actionality of the verb, verbs could either have an inceptive reading (X has started doing Y) or the onset of a change-of-state (X has started to become Y). These interpretations are a result of the actional phases encoded by the verb. Non-inchoative verbs have a 'started to V' reading available to them while inchoative verbs have a 'beginning-of-change' reading indicating that these verbs encode a change-of-state phase (the nucleus phase). However, verbs which encode a punctual change of state (i.e. punctual inchoatives) are incompatible with the inceptive marker. Sentences illustrating the use of the inceptive marker as an actionality diagnostic are presented in (5) below.

5. (a) Òsàzẹ suẹn ghá giẹ
Osazẹ INCEP PROSP laugh
'Osazẹ has started laughing'
- (b) íràn suẹn ghà kpé ọbọ
3.PL INCEP PROSP clap hand
'They have started clapping hands'
- (c) ọkpiá suẹn ghà dọ-ẹrhẹn-yọ
man INCEP PROSP extinguish.fire
'The man has started putting out the fire'
- (d) né ẹrhán suẹn ghà bígọ
DET tree INCEP PROSP bend
'The tree has started to become bent'
- (e) * ékítà nà suẹn ghà wù
Dog DEM INCEP PROSP die
Intended: 'This dog has started dying'

Example 5 shows that the inceptive has a ‘start-of-a-progressive-event’ reading with Vendlerian activities (5a), semelfactives (5b) and accomplishments (5c). With these verbs, this diagnostic identifies predicates which do not encode a durative change-of-state. Change of state verbs like *bígò* ‘be(come) bent’ in (5d) have a ‘start-of-change-of-state’ meaning in the context of the inceptive. In this context, it ‘highlights’ the transition from one state to another and indicates the onset of that change. Some verbs are incompatible with the inceptive as shown in (5e) with the verb *wú* ‘die’. This is an indication that this verb does not encode a durative-transition nucleus phase i.e., the change-of-state is punctual.

5.3.4 The PhP Marker *nẹ* ‘Already’

The phasal polarity marker *nẹ* contrasts two situations (a factual situation where the event has occurred or is ongoing vs a counterfactual situation where the event has not yet started or not yet occurred) on one hand and three scenarios (the event occurred earlier than the speaker expected vs the event occurred at the expected time vs the event occurred later than expected). The Edo language marks ‘already’ in two ways, distinguished by prosody. *nẹ* + imperfective contrasts an ongoing event with a counterfactual scenario where the event has not yet begun. *nẹ* in the context of the factative contrasts a past event (the actual scenario) with one where the event has not yet taken place (the counterfactual scenario).

The different interpretations *nẹ* has with different verbs serves as an actionality diagnostic to distinguish inchoatives from other verbs. This is illustrated below with example (6).

6. (a) *lyóbósà rẹn èbé nẹ*
 lyobosa know book already
 ‘lyobosa has become intelligent’

- (b) né ófígbò rànrán nè
 DET palm.oil melt already
 'The palm oil has melted' [i.e., in a melted state]
- (c) Òzó khué nè édè ná
 Ozo swim already day this
 'Ozo has swam today already'
- (d) Òghòghò yó éwù nè
 Oghòghò wear shirt already
 'Oghòghò has worn a shirt'
- (e) ò gbé èrè úbí nè
 3.SG.NOM hit 3.SG.ACC slap already
 'S/he has slapped him/her already'

Inchoatives have a present (result) state interpretation with *nè* in Edo. For example (6a) shows the inchoative *rèn èbé* 'be(come) intelligent' in the context of the *nè* + factative having a present state reading following a change of state. Similarly, the inchoative *rànrán* 'be(come) melted' in (6b) has a present result state interpretation following a change of state (from when it was semi-liquid). Activities (6c), accomplishments (6d) and Vendlerian achievements (6e) have a 'past-event-with-current-relevance' interpretation in the context of *nè*.

Né temporally denotes an ongoing event that has current relevance as discussed in chapter 4. As an actionality diagnostic, *né* is used to test for verbs which encode a durative nucleus phase. I use the same verbs and sentence paradigms presented in (6) to highlight the actional differences between *nè* in (6) and *né* in (7).

7. (a) ófígbò rànrán né
 palm.oil melt already
 'The palm oil is melting already'
- (b) Òzó khué né edè ná
 Ozo swim already day this
 'Ozo is swimming today already'
- (c) Òghòghò yó éwù né
 Oghòghò wear shirt already

‘Oghoḡḡo is putting on his shirt already’
[i.e., in the process of putting on his shirt]

(d) * ò gbé éřè úbí nẹ
3.SG.NOM hit 3.SG.ACC slap already
Intended: ‘S/he is slapping him/her already’

(e) ékítà ná wú nẹ
dog DEM die already
i. ‘This dog seems to be dying’
ii. # ‘This dog is already dying’

The PhP item *nẹ* ‘highlights’ the nucleus in inchoatives which encode a durative onset prior to the change-of-state preceding the result state (coda) – thus denoting a change which has begun but has not been completed as shown with the verb *rànrán* ‘melt’ in (7a). Activities (7b) and accomplishments (7c) have the default ‘X is already V-ing’ reading as they both encode durational nuclei – activities being durational temporally unbounded events and accomplishments being durational events that culminate. Predicates which encode a punctual nucleus are incompatible with *nẹ* (7d) and (7e).

5.3.5 The Terminative

The terminative in Edo is marked by *fó* literally translated as ‘finish’. Temporally, it denotes an event which has been carried out to completion, however, as will be shown, it has different readings with different verbs depending on the actionality of the verb. Although most verbs collocate with the terminative marker, some verbs exhibit a co-occurrence restriction with it. Such verbs, however, use the terminative + already (*fó* + *nẹ*) to express completion/termination. The range of readings available to the terminative without *nẹ* ‘already’ are (i) a durative event that has culminated (X has finished V-ing) illustrated with example (8a) (ii) an exhaustive reading (an event coming to an end because the ‘quantized NP’ on which the action was being performed on has

been exhausted) shown in (8b) (iii) an emphatic/degree reading (X V-ed Y very hard) as in (8c) (iv) a present state following a change (8d) and (iv) ungrammaticality with *fó* illustrated in (8d).

8. (a) Òsàsú bọ òwá fó
 Osasu build.FAC house TERM
 'Osasu finished building a house'
 [Context: Osasu was building a house but he is done building because the house is completed]
- (b) íràn tọn erhan fó
 3.PL fell.FAC tree TERM
 'They finished felling trees'
 [Context: There are no more trees to fell]
- (c) ọ gbé ẹrè úbí fó
 3.SG.NOM hit.FAC 3.SG.ACC slap TERM
 'S/he slapped him/her very hard'
- (d) Ímádé kpòlọ fó
 Imade be.fat.FAC TERM
 'Imade is fat...and cannot get fatter'
 [Context: She cannot become fatter than she is]
- (e) * ọ sàán/khián/bigọ/viẹ/dín/yó fó
 3.SG jump/walk/bend/cry/be,brave/be.high TERM
 Intended: 'He/she/it has finished jumping/walking/bending/crying/ being brave/being high'

The terminative as a diagnostic serves to identify verbs which possess a durative phase leading up to a culmination of the event. Only verbs which encode a durative phase + culmination, i.e., Vendlerian accomplishments, have a 'finished V-ing' reading e.g., *mó ètó* 'weave (a person's) hair' and *bọ òwá* 'build a house' (8a). All other verbs are either incompatible with *fó* or have a coerced reading in the context of the terminative. I argue that this diagnostic should only be used to identify accomplishments because other verb classes are associated with the other interpretations in the context of *fó*. For example, the following verbs are incompatible with *fó*, *sàán* 'jump', *wí* 'to.smell' *dín* 'be.brave', *viẹ* 'cry'; the following verbs have an exhaustive reading when

they co-occur with the terminative, *tọn èrhán* ‘fell trees’, *biẹ ọmọ* ‘to give birth’ i.e. ‘she has finished having children’ and *wọn àmẹ* ‘drink water’ i.e. the event ended because there was no more water to drink. The only consistency with respect to actionality observed is that verbs which encode a durative nucleus followed a culmination coda phase have a ‘finished V-ing’ interpretation while other verbs have a related coerced reading (such as exhaustive, emphatic) or are incompatible with it.

The terminative + *nẹ* (*fó + nẹ*) also has a range of interpretations with different verbs. Its default interpretation is a durative event that culminates. Other readings available with this construction are cessation (X has stopped V-ing already), reverse state (X is no longer V), ‘peak’ state i.e., in a state and cannot progress any further in that state (X is V and cannot beyond this point) while some verbs are incompatible with *fó nẹ*.

9. (a) *Áizẹnósà dọlọ¹⁷ íkékẹ mwẹn yí fó nẹ*
Aizẹnosa repair bicycle POSS TERM already
 ‘Aizẹnosa has finished repairing my bicycle already’
- (b) *érhà mwẹ gbẹn èmwí fó nẹ*
father POSS write thing TERM already
 ‘My father has stopped writing’
- (c) *né úkpókò bígò fó nẹ*
DET tree.branch be.bent TERM already
 ‘The branch is fully bent ... and cannot bend any further’
- (d) *íràn ghòghò fó nẹ*
3.PL be.happy TERM already
 ‘They are no longer happy’
- (e) * *ógbà yó fó nẹ*
fence be.high TERM already
 Intended: ‘The fence is fully high’

¹⁷ The verb *dọlọyí* ‘to repair’ is a split-verb. i.e. Its argument is inserted within the word – in this case between *dọlọ* and *yí*.

Accomplishments have an ‘X has finished V-ing already’ interpretation in the context of *nẹ̀*. This shows that verb senses like *dọ̀lọ̀yí* ‘repair’ in example (9a) encode a durative phase prior to event culmination. Activities like write (without a quantized NP) have a cessative reading as shown with the verb *gbẹ̀n* ‘write’ in (9b). Inchoative verbs have a ‘peak of change-of-state’ reading in the context of the terminative + *nẹ̀*. This diagnostic highlights the change-of-state nucleus phase and indicates the change has reached its limit as illustrated with (9c). Some inchoatives have a reverse state reading while others are incompatible with this construction as a diagnostic. It is currently unclear why some states cannot co-occur with this construction while others have a reversed state interpretation. This diagnostic is thus helpful in identifying accomplishments, activities and durative inchoatives based on the different temporal interpretations verbs have with this diagnostic.

5.3.6 The Persistent

The persistent aspect temporally denotes events which begun before speech time (ST) and continues up to ST (and possibly beyond). As a PhP item, it contrasts two situations (a factual situation where the event began before speech time and is still ongoing vs a counterfactual situation where event is no longer in progress) and two scenarios (the event is in progress earlier than expected vs the event is happening at the expected ST). It is marked in Edo by *yẹ́é*. The possible interpretations of verbs in the context of the persistent include: (i) an event that began prior to ST continues through ST (X is still V-ing), illustrated with example (10a); (ii) a change of state in progress (X is still becoming V), as in (10b); (iii) a persistent state holds despite expectation to the contrary (X is still V/still Vs Y despite/in spite of ...), as shown with

(10c); (iv) a habitual/professional reading (X is a V-er), as illustrated with (10d) and (v)
 Incompatibility with the persistive aspect.

- (a) ò yèé kpòlò òwá
 3.SG PERS sweep house
 'S/he is still sweeping the house'
- (b) úkpòn ẹrè yèé fàfá
 cloth his/her PERS fade
 'His/her cloth is still fading'
- (c) íràn yèé ghòghó
 3.PL PERS happy
 'They are still happy despite...'
 [Context: They are still happy despite the challenges they have faced]
- (d) Ímádé yèé dọ̀lọ̀ íkẹ̀kẹ̀ yì
 Imade PERS repair bicycles
 (i) 'Imade is still repairing a bicycle'
 (ii) 'Imade still repairs bicycles' [as a profession]
- (e) # Ékítà yèé wú
 dog PERS die
 Intended: 'The dog is still dying'

Activities have an 'event that began prior to ST and continues through ST (X is still V-ing)' interpretation with the persistive. In (10a) the sweeping event began in the past (i.e., prior to speech time) and continues through and beyond ST. Durative inchoatives such as *fàfá* 'fade' in (10b) have an 'ongoing change' interpretation in the context of the persistive. So, in (10b) the cloth is not completely faded but is still in the process of fading. Accomplishments like *bọ̀ òwá* 'build a house' and *dọ̀lọ̀yí* 'repair (something)', shown in (10d), are ambiguous between an ongoing persistive event and a habitual interpretation (X V-s regularly/as a profession). Not all predicates are compatible with the persistive aspect and this is indicative of a verb which encodes a punctual nucleus as illustrated with example (10e). The relevance of the use of the persistive aspect as a diagnostic for actional phases is that it highlights/selects a

durative nucleus phase (in the case of durative inchoatives, a durative change), hence its compatibility with activities and accomplishments. Inchoatives which encode a durative change of state are also compatible with the persistive, in which case the aspectual marker ‘picks-out’ the transformation phase of the event. Verbs which do not encode a durative phase such as punctual inchoatives and achievements are infelicitous with the persistive aspect in Edo.

5.3.7 The Prospective

The default interpretation of the prospective marker *ghá* is ‘X will V’. This is the interpretation with states (11a), accomplishments (11b and 11e) and inchoatives (11d) and (11e). However, activities are ambiguous between a prospective and an on-going reading. This may be the reason why Aghẹyisi (1990) proposes that it is a progressive marker as the only verb used to illustrate *ghá* as a progressive marker is *kpòlò* ‘sweep’ which is an activity verb. This is not the case however as with other verb classes, the only interpretation available is the prospective reading.

10. (a) Òsàsú ghá yà Òsàńóbua yí¹⁸
 Osasu PROSP believe God
 ‘Osasu will believe in God’
- (b) ọ ghá khiẹn íbátà
 3.SG PROSP sell shoe
 ‘S/he will sell shoes’
- (c) Ìvbí mwẹ ghá kù vbe ìyèkè òwá
 children POSS PROSP play PREP back house
 i. ‘My children will play at the backyard’
 ii. ‘My children are playing at the backyard’
- (d) òghèdè nì ghá kẹkẹ
 plantain DEM PROSP be.rotten
 ‘These plantains will become rotten’
- (e) né ékítá ghá wú

¹⁸ Part of the split verb *yáyí* in ‘yá NP yí’

DET dog PROSP die
'The dog will die'

(f) Néné! òkhuò ghá bò òwá
DET woman PROSP build house
'The woman will build a house'

The prospective marker therefore serves as evidence that Edo language privileges an activity actional class because it is the only class of verbs which has a possible additional progressive reading in the context of the prospective. It will therefore serve as a diagnostic for activity verbs since it has no varied temporal effects on other classes of verbs.

5.3.8 The Temporal Particle 'te'

The aspectual particle *té* 'almost' has different temporal interpretations with different verbs, hence its use as an actional diagnostic.

Three interpretations are associated with *té* according to Agheyisi (1986), (i) an event that was about to happen but did not happen (cf. 'almost fell' as in (12a)), (ii) a deontic modal meaning with psych-state verbs (cf. 'had wanted ...' as in (12b)), (iii) an event that occurred but was not consistent with expectations (cf. 'the cloth was sewn but it did not fit' as in (12c)).

11. (a) ò té dé
3.SG almost fall.FAC
'He almost fell'

(b) ò té hòó né í wú
3.SG almost want REL 1.SG die
'He had wanted me to die'

(c) ò té sẹ́ ẹ̀rẹ̀, sòkpán ò má
3.SG almost sew.FAC 3.SG.ACC but 3.SG NEG
guá mwén ẹ̀gbé
have.enough.room POSS body
'He sewed it alright, but it did not fit me'

Based on elicitation sessions conducted in this study, I found that verbs which encode a punctual nucleus have the reading in (i) above, verbs which do not encode a punctual nucleus have the interpretation in (iii). I am skeptical about the modal meaning associated with *té* as the verbs chosen to illustrate this already have some modal meaning associated with them (cf. *hòó* ‘to want’, *ròò* ‘to think/assume’) and this interpretation did not show up in my elicitation sessions. The cooccurrence interpretations associated with *té* are further illustrated with examples in (13).

12. (a) *lyòbò té mò ètó sòkpán ọ má mósè*
 lyobò almost weave hair but 3.SG NEG beautiful
 ‘lyobo weaved her hair, but it is not beautiful’
- (b) *néné inyá té kèkè sòkpán írán yé rẹ ẹrẹ*
 DET yam almost be.rotten but 3.PL PERS eat 3.SG.ACC
 ‘The yam became rotten but they still ate it’
- (c) *néné ọmọ ọkpiá té giẹ sòkpán ...*
 DET child man almost laugh but
 ‘The boy laughed but ...’
 [Context: The boy laughed but the man didn’t think he was funny]
- (d) *Òzó té fí úgbé sòkpán ...*
 Ozo almost throw stone but ...
 ‘Ozo almost threw a stone, but ...’
 [Context: Ozo was about to throw a stone but just as he was about to throw it but his mother prevented him from doing so]
- (e) *néné ọmọ té wú sòkpán ...*
 DET child almost die but
 ‘The child almost died ...’
 [Context: The child was about to die but a doctor came in time to save him/her]

Accomplishments (13a) and activities (13b) have a ‘X V-ed but...’ interpretation in the context of *té*, inchoatives (b) have a ‘present state following a change, but ...’ reading. Predicates which encode a punctual nucleus phase + result state (13e) (i.e. punctual inchoatives) or punctual nucleus minus result state (achievements) (13d) have an ‘almost V-ed but did not’ reading. This diagnostic is thus helpful in distinguishing

verbs which encode a punctual nucleus from those which do not on one hand and inchoatives which encode a change-in-state from verbs which do not, on the other hand.

5.3.9 The Completive (-rV) Marker

The -rV suffix proposed to be the completive marker in chapter 4 serves to distinguish verbs which encode a result-state from those which do not. Inchoatives e.g., *nwién* 'be(come) rumped' in example (14c) have a present state interpretation when they co-occur with the completive marker. All other verbs such as activities which encode a durative nucleus without a coda (14a), accomplishments which encode a durative nucleus + culmination (14d), verbs which encode a punctual nucleus without a result state (14b) and verbs which encode a punctual nucleus leading to a result state (14e) all have past/complete interpretations in the context of the -rV suffix. This can be taken as further evidence that the language privileges a distinction between inchoatives and non-inchoatives.

13. (a) *nénè ọmọmọ viẹ-rè rhúmwùndá ọ dé*
 DET baby cry-CPL because 3.SG fall.FAC
 'The baby cried because s/he fell'
- (b) *úgbé nè ọ fi-rì má sẹ Òsàsú*
 stone REL 3.SG throw-CPL NEG reach Osasu
 'The stone s/he threw did not reach Osasu'
- (c) *ùtáláwẹ mwẹ nwién-rèn*
 trouser POSS be.rumped-CPL
 'My trouser is rumped'
- (d) *àkhé nè Ìziégbè má-rèn yé khérhé*
 pot REL Iziegbe mould-CPL to.be small
 'The pot that Iziegbe moulded is small'
- (e) *èsùgùsùgù wú-rù nódè*
 owl die-CPL yesterday
 'An owl died yesterday'

5.4 Actional Classes of Edo Verbs

Based on Botne and Kershner's (2000) framework, verbs in Edo can first be broadly classified into two aspectual classes Inchoatives and non-inchoatives. Inchoatives have also been known by other names such as "punctive" (Kershner 2002) or "change-of-state" (Crane 2011: Seidel 2008). I will show that in Edo, the primary distinction is between inchoatives and non-inchoatives. The former are verbs which encode a change-of-state and result state (such as *fàfá* 'be(come) faded', *kèkè* 'be(come) rotten', *kpòlò* 'be(come) fat', *wú* 'die') while the latter lacks this phasal structural combination (e.g., *rhùlẹ̀* 'run', *bọ̀ òwá* 'build a house', *dé* 'fall', *tòlọ̀ òhuẹ̀n* 'cough'). **There were no tests to convincingly show that the language privileges a distinction between 'pure' states and inchoatives.** Therefore, this study does not adopt this distinction.

Inchoatives can be further subdivided into punctual and durative inchoatives. Punctual inchoatives encode a punctual nucleus (transition) leading to a result-state (coda) whereas durative inchoatives encode a durative/coming-to-be phase (nucleus) + result state (coda).

Non-inchoatives are subdivided into three classes: duratives (verbs which have a durative nucleus and are temporally unbounded/atelic e.g., *kú* 'play', *kpòlọ̀* 'sweep', *bùún àrò* 'blink'), Duratives are further subdivided into activities (which encode a single durative, atelic event e.g., *rhùlẹ̀* 'run') and series (atelic iterations of an event e.g., *tòlọ̀ òhuẹ̀n* 'cough'), accomplishments (verbs which encode a durative phase + culmination e.g., *dọ̀lọ̀yí* 'repair') and achievements (verbs which encode a punctual nucleus without a resulting-state *gbé úbí* 'slap').

5.4.1 Inchoatives vs non-inchoativeness

Evidence that the Edo language encodes a distinction between inchoatives and non-inchoatives in its verbal system, can be determined from the observation that some verbs have a change-of-state/coming-to-be phase + a result state phase, whereas other verbs lack this phasal combination/structure.

That inchoatives encode a change of state phase which other verb classes do not can be determined by the coming-to-be reading which these verbs have when they cooccur with the *nẹ̀* (15a), the persistive (15b) and the inceptive (15c).

14. (a) *òpià gbín nẹ̀*
cutlass be.blunt already
'The cutlass is already becoming blunt'
- (a') *Ùhùnọ́má rri èvbàré nẹ̀*
Uhunoma eat food already
'Uhunoma is already eating'
- (b) *òpià yèé gbín*
cutlass PERS be.blunt
'The cutlass is becoming blunt'
- (b') *Ùhùnọ́má yèé rri èvbàré*
Uhunoma PERS eat food
'Uhunoma is still eating'
- (c) *òpià suẹn-ghá gbìn*
cutlass INCEP be.blunt
'The cutlass has started becoming blunt'
- (c') *Ùhùnọ́má suẹn-ghá rri èvbàré*
Uhunoma INCEP eat food
'Uhunoma has started eating'

With inchoatives, aspectual markers which denote durative events (such as the persistive, the *nẹ̀* 'already' and the inceptive) select the transitive nucleus phase of durative inchoatives (illustrated with 15a, 15b and 15c) thus yielding a 'coming-to-be' / 'X is becoming V' interpretation. All other verbs, except for punctual inchoatives (to be

discussed in the next section) have an ‘ongoing’/‘X is V-ing’ + the inherent aspectual meaning of the marker (i.e., persistive, ‘already’, inceptive meanings) readings in the context of these durative aspectual markers as exemplified with the activity verb *nnì èvbàré* ‘eat’.

Evidence that inchoative verbs encode a result state comes from the present (state) interpretation they receive when they cooccur with temporal markers which denote past/complete events. These markers include the factative (16a), *nè* ‘already’ (16b) and the completive marker (16c).

15. (a) *néné èbé kàkà*
 DET leaves be.dry.FAC
 ‘The leaves are dry’
- (a’) *néné ọkhaẹmwẹn bọ òwá*
 DET chief build.FAC house
 ‘The chief built a house’
- (b) *néné èbé kàkà nè*
 DET leaves be.dry already
 ‘The leaves are already dry’
- (b’) *néné ọkhaẹmwẹn bọ òwá nè*
 DET chief build house already
 ‘The chief has built a house’
- (c) *néné èbé kàkà-rè*
 DET leaves be.dry-CPL
 ‘The leaves are dry’¹⁹
- (c’) *néné òwá nè ọkhaẹmwẹn bọ-rè dígbà*
 DET house REL chief build-CPL be.large
 ‘The house which the chief built is large’

These markers which denote ‘past/completeness’ select the coda phase of inchoatives to yield a present-state interpretation. With other verb classes, these

¹⁹ Some speakers did note that the difference in meaning between (16a) and (16c) is that the latter has some ‘emphatic’ meaning in addition to its past interpretation.

temporal markers retain their past reading. The presence of a present state reading in the context of past markers is thus evidence that the verb in question is inchoative as it encodes a result-state. In this study, inchoatives are defined as verbs which encode both a change-of-state/transition nucleus phase and a result-state coda phase. Predicates which lack this phasal structure are classified as non-inchoatives.

5.4.1.1 Inchoatives

Inchoative verbs in Èdo can be further subdivided into punctual and durative inchoatives. The difference between these two sub-classes is that the former encodes an instantaneous change-of-state leading to a result state while durative inchoatives encode a gradual change-of-state leading to a result state. Evidence for proposing this sub-division comes from the temporal ‘behavior’ of verbs within the inchoative class with three diagnostic tests viz. the inceptive, the persistive and *té* ‘almost’.

5.4.1.1.1 Punctual inchoatives

Punctual inchoatives are incompatible with temporal markers that denote durativity such as the inceptive (17a), the persistive (17b) and *nẹ* + imperfective (17c). This indicates that these verbs do not encode a durative nucleus phase which these temporal markers could select. Examples of punctual inchoatives in Èdo are *wú* ‘die’ and *yèé* ‘remember’. Example 17(d) shows that punctual inchoatives have an ‘almost’ reading when they co-occur with *té*.

16. (a) * òlògbò suẹn-ghá wú
 cat INCEP die
 Intended: ‘The cat has started dying’
- (b) * òlògbò yèé wú
 cat PERS die
 Intended: ‘The cat is still dying’
- (c) * òlògbò wú nẹ

cat die ALREADY
Intended: 'The cat is already dying'

(d) òlògbò té wú
cat almost die
'The cat almost died'

Examples (17a-17d) show that durative aspectual markers such as the inceptive which denotes that a durative event has begun (17a), the persistive which denotes that an event which began before speech time and is still ongoing (17b) and *né* + imperfective which denotes the present relevance of an ongoing event (17c) are incompatible with punctual inchoatives as there is no durative phase encoded by these verbs for these aspectual markers to 'select'. Example 17(d) shows that *té* 'almost' has an 'almost V ...but did not' interpretation which indicates that the verb encodes a punctual phase as earlier presented. As will be shown in the next section, durative inchoatives do not have this temporal compatibility restrictions/interpretation with these four durative temporal markers discussed in this subsection. Examples (18) to (20) show the interpretations verbs other than punctual inchoatives receive in the context of the inceptive (18), the persistive (19), *né* + imperfective (20) and *té* (21).

17. (a) *nènè úkpòn suén-ghá fàfá*
DET cloth INCEP fade
'The cloth has begun to fade'
- (b) *Òsàsú suén-ghá kpòlò néné òwá*
Osasu INCEP sweep DET house
'Osasu has started sweeping the house'
- (c) *Òzó suén-ghá gbè Òsàrọ úbì*
Ozo INCEP hit Osaro slap
'Ozo has started slapping Osarọ'
- (d) *Nènè òkpiá suén-ghá bọ òwá*
DET man INCEP build house
'The man has started building a house'

- (e) * Ọmọmọ suẹn-ghá dè
 baby INCEP fall
 'The baby has started falling'

Example (18a) shows that durative inchoative verbs such as *fàfá* 'fade' have a 'start-of-change' reading compared with punctual inchoatives which are incompatible with the inceptive as shown with example (17a). Activities (18b), series (18c) and accomplishments (18d) have a 'X has started V-ing' interpretation. Achievements (18e) which do not encode a durative phase, hence do not license the inceptive.

Example (19) shows the interpretation of verbs belonging to classes other than punctual inchoatives in the context of the persistive *yèé*.

18. (a) úkpọn yèé fàfá
 cloth PERS fade
 'The cloth is still fading'
- (b) Ọsàsú yèé kpòlọ néné òwá
 Osasu PERS sweep DET house
 'Osasu is still sweeping the house'
- (c) Ọzó yèé gbé Ọsàrọ úbì
 Ozo PERS hit Osarọ slap
 'Ozo is still slapping Osarọ'
- (d) Nèné òkpiá yèé bọ òwá
 DET man PERS build house
 'The man is still building a house'
- (e) * Ọmọmọ yèé dè
 baby PERS fall
 Intended: 'The baby is still falling'

. Activities (19b) have a persistive atelic event reading, series (19c) have a persistive iterative interpretation and accomplishments (19d) have a pre-culmination persistive interpretation. Achievements which encode a punctual nucleus like punctual inchoatives do not co-occur with the persistive.

Example (20) provides instances of the co-occurrence restrictions/interpretations of verbs belonging to different classes with *né*.

19. (a) úkpòn fàfá né
 cloth fade already
 'The cloth is already fading'
- (b) Òsàsú kpòlò néné òwá né
 Osasu sweep DET house already
 'Osasu is already sweeping the house'
- (c) Òzó gbé Òsàrọ úbì né
 Ozo hit Osarọ slap already
 'Ozo is already slapping Osarọ'
- (d) Nèné òkpiá bọ òwá né
 DET man build house already
 'The man is already building a house'
- (e) * Òmómọ dé nẹ
 baby fall already
 Intended: 'The baby is already falling'

Durative inchoatives (20a) have a 'post change-of-state-in-progress' reading compared to punctual inchoatives which do not license the *né*. Activities (20b) have an 'ongoing atelic event with current relevance' reading, series (20c) have an 'ongoing atelic-iterative event with current relevance' interpretation, accomplishments have an 'ongoing pre-culmination event phase' reading and achievements such as the verb *dé* 'fall' do not license *né* because they encode a punctual nucleus.

In example (21), I present sentences illustrating the varied readings verbs receive in the context of *té* as this is one diagnostic that helps distinguish verbs which encode a punctual nucleus from those which encode a durational nucleus.

20. (a) néné úkpòn té fàfá
 DET cloth almost fade
 'The cloth faded but ...'
 [The cloth faded but was restored]

- (b) Òsàsú té kpòlò néné òwá
 Osasu almost sweep DET house
 ‘Osasu swept the house but ...’
 [Osasu swept the house but the house still looks unkept]
- (c) Òzó té gbè Òsàró úbì
 Ozo almost hit Osaro slap
 ‘Ozo attempted to slap Osaro but ...’
 [Ozo raised his hands to slap Osaro but was held back]
- (d) Nèné òkpiá té bọ òwá
 DET man almost build house
 ‘The man built a house but ...’
 [The man built a house but it is uninhabitable]
- (e) Òmómọ té dè
 baby almost fall
 ‘The baby almost fell but ...’
 [The baby crawled to the edge of the bed but was held back from falling]

Although both punctual inchoatives and durative inchoatives can co-occur with *té*, their interpretations in that context vary. Punctual inchoatives have an ‘almost V-ed’ interpretation (17d) while durative inchoatives have a ‘counter-expectation’ reading (21a). Achievements (21e) like punctual inchoatives encode a punctual nucleus phase and has an ‘almost’ interpretation. Series (21c) have an ‘almost’ interpretation because the sub-events which make up the series are punctual (e.g., give a slap) so the temporal particle has scope over sub-events and not the atelic chain of sub-events which make up the series. Verbs which encode a durative nucleus (i.e., activities (21b) and accomplishments (21d)) have a counter-expectation interpretation in the context of *té*.

5.4.1.1.2 Durative Inchoatives

Durative inchoatives like punctual inchoatives encode both a change-of-state phase and result phase. However, they differ from punctual inchoatives in that they encode a durative change-of-state also known as a coming-to-be phase. The same

tests applied to punctual inchoatives will be used to prove that these verbs encode a durative change-of-state in example (22).

- 21.(a) íbà ní suén ghá khuó
slab DEM INCEP PROSP be.slippery
'This slab has started becoming slippery'
- (b) íbà ní yèé khuó
slab DEM PERS be.slippery
'This slab is still slippery'
- (c) íbà ní khuó nẹ
slab DEM be.slippery already
'This slab is already becoming slippery'
- (d) íbà ní té khuó sòkpán ì má dé
slab DEM almost slippery but 1.SG NEG fall
'This slab is slippery, but I didn't fall'

Whereas punctual inchoatives were incompatible with the inceptive, durative inchoatives have an inceptive-transitional reading in the context of *suén ghá* i.e., 'beginning to become V' (22a). Punctual inchoatives were also incompatible with the persistent. However, durative inchoatives have a 'present-state-that-still-pertains-at-ST' interpretation as demonstrated with the verb *khuó* 'be.slippery' in example (22b). In the context of the *nẹ* (22c), durative inchoatives have a 'transition-in-progress' reading whereas their punctual counterparts are incompatible with this marker. Both punctual and durative inchoatives are compatible with *té* 'almost'. However, their actional interpretations differ. With verbs which encode a durative nucleus (22d), an 'X is V, but ...' reading is observed while verbs which encode a punctual nucleus have a 'X almost V-ed, but ...' interpretation. This difference between the compatibility/interpretation of inchoatives is thus proposed as evidence that the language makes a distinction between change-of-state verbs which encode a durational transition in contrast to those which do not.

5.4.1.2 Non-inchoatives

Non-inchoatives are verbs which do not encode a change-of-state + result state. Evidence for this major class of verbs comes from the actional behavior with tests earlier used to illustrate the existence of inchoatives. These verbs do not have a ‘coming-to-be’ reading with aspectual markers which denote durativity (23) and they do not have a present result interpretation in the context of markers which denote past/complete events (24). Sub-classes of this major class of verbs are duratives (further divided into activities and series), accomplishments and achievements. Each class/subclass and diagnostic tests to prove the phasal composition/structure of each class is discussed below.

22. (a) íràn khuẹ
3.PL swim.IPFV
i. ‘They are swimming (now)’
ii. ‘They swim (everyday)’
- (b) néné òkpiá suẹn-ghá bò òwá
DET man INCEP build house
‘The man has started building a house’
- (c) ò yèé tọlọ òhuẹn
3.SG PERS itch cough
‘He is still coughing’
- (d) òvbí mwé digiẹn nẹ
child POSS squat ALREADY
‘My child is already squatting’

When non-inchoatives collocate with aspectual markers which denote durativity, they have an ongoing reading compared to inchoatives which have a transition/‘coming-to-be’ interpretation in this context (cf. examples 14a, 14b and 14c). Example (23) shows that with the imperfective (23a), the inceptive (23b), the persistive (23c) *nẹ* ‘already’ (23d), these verbs have an ‘ongoing’ meaning.

Example (24) shows non-inchoatives in the context of temporal markers which denote past events viz. the factative (24), *nẹ* ‘V-ed already’ (25) and the completive marker (26).

23. (a) Òsàsú kpòlò òwá
 Osasu sweep.FAC house
 ‘Osasu swept the house’
- (b) Òzó gbé Òsàrọ úbì
 Ozo hit.FAC Osarọ slap
 ‘Ozo slapped Osarọ’
- (c) Nènè òkpiá bọ òwá
 DET man build.FAC house
 ‘The man built a house’
- (d) Òmómó dé
 baby fall.FAC
 ‘The baby fell’

Inchoative verbs (both punctual and durative) in the context of the factative have a present (result) state interpretation (cf. *wú* ‘is dead’ and *fàfá* ‘is faded’). Non-inchoative verbs have a past interpretation in the context of the factative. Activities have a ‘past atelic’ interpretation (24a), series (24b) have a past event reading, accomplishments (24c) have a ‘past culminated event’ interpretation and achievements (24d) have a ‘past punctual-event reading’.

Example (25) shows instances of non-inchoative verbs in the context of the marker *nẹ* ‘has already X-ed’

24. (a) Òsàsú kpòlò néné òwá nẹ
 Osasu sweep DET house already
 ‘Osasu has already swept the house’
- (b) Òzó gbé Òsàrọ úbì nẹ
 Ozo hit Osarọ slap already
 ‘Ozo has already slapped Osarọ’
- (c) Nènè òkpiá bọ òwá nẹ

DET man build house already
'The man has already built a house'

(d) Ọmómọ dé nè
baby fall ALREADY
#'The baby has already fallen' [The baby was expected to fall]

25. (a) néné òwà nè Òsàsú kpóló-rò
DET house REL Osasu sweep-CPL
'The house that Osasu swept'

(b) néné úbí nè Òsàsú gbé-rè tọn
DET slap REL Osasu hit-CPL
'The slap that Osasu gave'

(c) néné òwà nè nene òkpiá bọ-rè
DET house REL man build-CPL
'The house that the man built'

(d) néné ọmómọ dé-rè
DET baby fall-CPL
'The baby fell'

It was earlier shown (cf. data presented in example (15)) that inchoatives have a present result state reading in the context of past temporal markers. Example (24-26) show that non-inchoatives do not have a present state reading with these markers but instead have a 'past' event interpretation. The absence of a change-of-state reading when non-inchoatives occur with durative aspectual markers and a past reading (instead of a present state reading) when they cooccur with temporal markers denoting past events is evidence for this broad class of verbs which includes duratives, accomplishments and achievements.

5.4.1.2.1 Duratives

Duratives are a sub-class of non-inchoatives which encode duration and atelicity (temporal unboundedness). Duratives are further sub-divided into activities and series. The need to distinguish activities from series is based on the observation that the

language marks a distinction between homogenous durative verbs (activities) and iterative durative verbs (series). The Evidence that duratives encode durativity comes from the actional interpretations they receive in the context of temporal markers which denote durativity (e.g., the persistive, the imperfective and *né*) and the temporal interpretation they receive in the ‘use x time to V’ construction which is used as a test for telicity. Another evidence for creating a durative class of verbs is their ability to have a habitual reading in addition to an ongoing reading in the context of the imperfective and a prospective/ongoing reading in the context of the prospective as shown in (27a) with activities and (27b) with series.

26. (a) ọ̀sẹ̀ mwẹ̀ kpòlò néné òwá
 friend POSS sweep.IPFV DET house
 i. ‘My friend is sweeping the house (now)’
 ii. ‘My friend sweeps the house (everyday)’
- (a’) ọ̀sẹ̀ mwẹ̀ ghá kpòlọ́ néné òwá
 friend POSS PROSP sweep DET house
 i. ‘My friend will sweep the house (tomorrow)’
 ii. ‘My friend is sweeping the house (now)’
- (b) ékítà nì luẹ̀ èbé
 dog DEM chew.IPFV paper
 i. ‘This dog is chewing paper (right now)’
 ii. ‘This dog chews paper (all the time)’
- (b’) ékítà nì ghá luẹ̀ èbé
 dog DEM PROSP chew paper
 i. ‘This dog will chew paper (later today)’
 ii. ‘This dog is chewing paper (right now)’

The ambiguous reading durative verbs receive in the context of these two aspectual markers is evidence that there are two phases encoded in these verbs that could potentially be selected by these aspectual markers. The availability of the habitual reading with the imperfective is evidence that these verbs encode atelicity.

5.4.1.2.1.1 Activities

Activities are single-event durative and atelic events. Examples of activities are *só ìhuán* 'sing', *rhùlẹ̀* 'run' and *kpòlò* 'sweep'. Evidence that activity verbs encode a durational phase comes from their ongoing interpretation with temporal markers which denote durativity as illustrated with example (28) below.

27. (a) *néné ìkhuò sò ìhuán*
DET women sing.IPFV song
i. 'The women are singing (now)'
ii. 'The women sing (everyday)'
- (b) *néné ìkhuò yèé sò ìhuán*
DET women PERS sing song
'The women are still singing'
- (c) *néné ìkhuò sò ìhuán nẹ̀*
DET women sing.IPFV song already
'The women are singing already'

When activities occur in the context of durative aspectual markers such as the imperfective (28a), the persistive (28b) and *nẹ̀* (28c), they have an ongoing interpretation as one of the possible interpretations. This is an indication that activities encode a durative phase. It was earlier stated that activities are both durative and atelic. The evidence for the atelic status of activities comes from their temporal interpretation in the 'use x time to V' construction as illustrated with example (29).

28. (a) *néné ìkhuò yá áwà ọkpá sò ìhuán*
DET woment INSTR hour one sing song
'The women spent one hour singing'
- (b) *ọ̀ yá áwà ọkpá biẹ ọ̀mọ̀*
3.SG INSTR hour one give.birth child
'She delivered the baby in one hour'

Activities (29a) in the context of the 'use X time to V construction' have a 'spent x time V-ing'/'engaged in V-event for x time' interpretation. Accomplishments (29b) on the other hand have a 'completed V-event in x time' reading when this diagnostic is applied

to them. Activity verbs in the context of the telicity diagnostic, have a ‘spent x time V-ing’, i.e., the women were engaged in singing for one hour in example (21a). In (21b), the accomplishment verb *bié òmọ* ‘give birth’ does not have a ‘spent x time V-ing’ but instead has a ‘spent x time to complete V-ing’, so (21b) means that the woman spent an hour in labor before the baby was born. This is taken as evidence that activities (and duratives in general) do not encode event culmination whereas accomplishments do.

Example (30) further illustrates this with a punctual inchoative (30a), a durational inchoative (30b), an accomplishment (30c) and an achievement verb (30d).

29. (a) * *néné ékítà yá èdè èvá wú*
 DET dog INSTR day two die
 intended: The dog died in two days
- (b) *nènè úkpòn yá ìkpédè èvá fàfá*
 DET cloth INSTR day.count two fade
 ‘The cloth faded in two days’
- (c) *néné òkpíá yá ìkpédè ìgbé bọ òwá*
 DET man INSTR day.count ten build house
 ‘The man built the house in ten days’
- (d) * *ómómọ yá ífuánrò ọkpá dé*
 baby INSTR minute one fall
 ‘The baby fell for/in one minute’

Examples (30a punctual inchoative) and (30d achievement) show that verbs which encode a punctual nucleus (punctual inchoatives and achievements) do not license the ‘use x time to V’ construction. Durational inchoatives (30b), have a ‘took x time to become V’. in example (30d), the sentence is interpreted as “it took x time to complete building the house” a predicted for accomplishment verbs. The ‘use x time to V’ construction is therefore useful in distinguishing verbs which encode a durative nucleus phase + event culmination (coda phase) from those which encode a durative

nucleus phase minus event culmination. It is not applicable to verbs which encode a punctual nucleus phase (e.g. punctual inchoatives and achievements).

5.4.1.2.1.2 Series

Series (a term adopted from Kanijo 2019) are durative, atelic, iterative events. They differ from activities in that they encode iteration and activities do not. Examples of series include *tòlọ òhụn* ‘cough’, *bùún áró* ‘blink’, *kpè òbọ* ‘clap’. Evidence that these verbs encode a durative phase, and no culmination comes from their ongoing interpretation with durative aspectual markers and a ‘spent x time V-ing’ in the context of the ‘use x time to V’ construction as illustrated with example (31).

30. (a) Òsàdébàmwẹ kpè òbọ
 Osadèbamwẹ clap.IPFV hand
 i. ‘Osadèbamwẹ is clapping (now)’
 ii. ‘Osadèbamwẹ claps (everytime in church)’
- (b) Òsàdébàmwẹ ghá kpè òbọ
 Òsàdébàmwẹ PROSP clap hand
 i. ‘Òsàdébàmwẹ will clap (when he goes to church)’
 ii. ‘Òsàdébàmwẹ is clapping (right now)’
- (c) Òsàdébàmwẹ yèé kpé òbọ
 Òsàdébàmwẹ PERS clap hand
 ‘Òsàdébàmwẹ is still clapping’
- (d) Òsàdébàmwẹ kpè òbọ nẹ
 Òsàdébàmwẹ clap hand already
 ‘Òsàdébàmwẹ is already clapping’
- (e) Òsàdébàmwẹ yá áwà ókpá kpè òbọ
 Òsàdébàmwẹ INSTR hour one clap hand
 i. ‘Òsàdébàmwẹ clapped for one hour’
 ii. # ‘Òsàdébàmwẹ completed a clap in one hour’

Series like activities have an ongoing reading in the context of durative temporal markers such as the imperfective (31a), the prospective (31b), the persistive (31c) and *nẹ* (31d). This is evidence that series encode a durative phase. In example (31e), the verb *kpè òbọ* ‘clap’ which is classified as a series has a ‘spent x time V-ing’ reading

instead of a ‘completed the event in x time’ reading. This shows that series like activities do not encode culmination.

Series and activities share the same features viz. encoding duration, atelicity, and no culmination. They however differ in that series are iterative (i.e., they consist of repetitions of an event encoded as one event) whereas activities are not. Evidence for this claim comes from the compatibility (or otherwise) of activities/series with some adverbs such as *mùniè* ‘slowly’ as shown with example (32).

31. (a) Èghósà só ìhuán mùniè
Èghosa sing song slowly
Èghosa is singing slowly’
- (b) * Èghośa kpè obó mùniè
Èghosa clap hand slowly
Intended: ‘Èghosa clapped slowly’

Activity verbs like *só ìhuán* ‘sing’ are compatible with these adverbs (32a) whereas series are not (32b). I propose that this is the case because the adverb has scope over a single event in the case of activities but cannot scope over series verbs because they encode atelic repetitions of an event,

5.4.1.2.2 Accomplishments

Accomplishments are verbs which encode a durative nucleus phase followed by an event culmination coda phase. Examples of accomplishment verbs in Èdo are *bó òwá* ‘build a house’, *dòlòyí* ‘repair’, *mó ètó* ‘weave hair’ and *biè òmó* ‘give birth’.

Evidence that accomplishments encode a durative nucleus phase comes from the ongoing reading they receive in the context of temporal markers which denote durativity as illustrated with the imperfective (33a), the prospective (33b) and the persistive (33c). Accomplishments also encode culmination as shown by the ‘spent x time to complete V-

ing' interpretation they receive in the context of the 'use x time to V' construction as shown with (33d).

32. (a) *Ìvié biẹ ọmọ*
 Ivie give.birth.IPFV child
 i. 'Ivie is having a baby'
 [Context: Ivie is currently in labor having a baby]
 ii. # 'Ivie gives birth'
 [Context: Ivie gives birth to children every other year]
- (b) *Ìvié ghá biẹ ọmọ*
 Ivie PROSP give.birth child
 i. 'Ivie will give birth'
 [Context: The speaker knows Ivie is pregnant and expected to give birth in a few months]
 ii. # 'Ivie is giving birth (right now)'
- (c) *Ìvié yẹé biẹ ọmọ*
 Ivie PERS give.birth child
 i. 'Ivie is still giving birth'
 [Context: Ivie is currently in labor]
 ii. # 'Ivie still gives birth'
 [Context: The speaker is asserting that Ivie still gives birth to children every other year]
- (d) *Ìvié yá áwà ọkpá biẹ ọmọ*
 Ivie INSTR hour one give.birth child
 i. 'Ivie gave birth in one hour'
 [Context: Ivie spent one hour in labor before the baby was delivered]
 ii. # 'Ivie was giving birth for one hour'

Example (33a) shows that an ongoing reading is available for accomplishments in the context the imperfective whereas the habitual reading is not. This indicates that accomplishments encode a durative phase but not an atelic one as was found with duratives (activities and series). In example (33b), only the prospective reading is available to the accomplishment verb in the context of the prospective marker *ghá*, whereas with activities, both a prospective and ongoing interpretation were available.

This is another indication that we are not dealing with an activity verb. Example (33c) shows that when accomplishments co-occur with the persistive, they have an ‘event that began before ST and continues beyond ST’ reading and not a persistive habitual reading where *Ivie* has had children in the past and still intends to have more. Accomplishments encode a culmination, and this is demonstrated by the availability of the ‘spend x time to complete V-ing’ instead of the ‘engaged in V activity for x time’ which atelic verbs such as duratives receive in this context.

5.4.1.2.3 Achievements

Achievements are non-inchoative predicates that encode only a punctual nucleus phase, no change-of-state phase and no result-state coda phase. Examples of achievements in Edo are *fián* ‘cut’, *bigbé* ‘to shut’, *fi* ‘shoot’ and *gié* ‘rip/tear off’. Example (34) below shows the achievement verb *dé* ‘fall’ in the context of various actional tests viz. the ‘almost’ test (34a), durativity tests with the imperfective (34b), *né* ‘already’ (34c), the inceptive (34d) and the persistive (34e).

33. (a) Òsàsú té dé
 Osasu almost fall
 i. ‘Osasu almost fell’
 [Context: Osasu slipped but did not fall]
 ii. # ‘Osasu fell but ...’
 [Context: Osasu fell but did not injure himself]
- (b) * Òsàsú dè
 Osasu fall.IPFV
 Intended: ‘Osasu is falling (right now)’ / ‘Osasu falls (everytime he walks)’
- (c) * Òsàsú dé né
 Osasu fall ALREADY
 Intended: ‘Osasu is falling already’
- (d) * Òsàsú suén-ghá dè
 Osasu INCEP fall
 Intended: ‘Osasu has started falling’

- (e) Òsàsú yèé dé
Osasu PERS fall
- i. # 'Osasu is still falling'
[Context: Osasu is still in the 'process' of falling]
- ii. 'Osasu still falls'
[Context: Osasu is a child still learning to walk]
- (f) * Òsàsú yá èmínìt èvá dé
Osasu INSTR minute two fall
Intended: 'Osasu fell for two minutes' / 'Osasu completed the fall in two minutes'

Example (34a) shows that achievements like punctual inchoatives have an 'almost V-ed' reading compared to durative verbs which have a 'V-ed but ...' interpretation when they cooccur with *té*. This is evidence that achievements encode a punctual nucleus. When verbs which encode a durative phase collocate with temporal markers which denote durativity, the result is an ongoing reading. However, achievements are incompatible with these temporal markers as illustrated with the verb *dé* 'fall' in the context of the imperfective (34b), *né* 'already' (34c), the inceptive (34d), the persistive (34e). This is evidence that these verbs do not encode a durative phase. Achievements have a coerced habitual reading with the persistive instead of the 'X is still V-ing' interpretation it has with other verbs. Example (34f) shows that achievements do not encode an atelic phase or event culmination as none of the two interpretations previously associated with the 'use x time to V' is available to this class of verbs.

5.5 Summary and Conclusion

This chapter presented and discussed actional diagnostics applied to the classification of verbs in Edo. The actional classes and phasal structure of each class were proposed based on the interpretation verbs received in the context of temporal markers as well as their compatibility or otherwise with these markers. Ten temporal

contexts were selected as tests for which phases were encoded in each verb class. The temporal contexts are the factative, the imperfective, the inceptive, the perfect, the terminative, the persistentive, *té* 'almost', the completive and the 'use x time to V' construction.

Evidence for inchoativity came from the coming-to-be reading these verbs receive when they co-occur with durative temporal markers such as the persistentive, *né* + imperfective and the inceptive. Non-inchoatives have an ongoing reading with these markers. Durative phases are diagnosed by an ongoing interpretation when verbs which encode this phasal property collocate with aspectual markers which denote durativity. Verb classes which do not encode a durative phase such as punctual inchoatives and achievements are incompatible with such aspectual markers. Additional evidence for verbs which encode a non-durative phase comes from their interpretation in the context of *té* 'almost'. Punctual inchoatives and achievements have an 'almost V-ed, but ...' reading while verbs which encode durativity have a 'V-ed, but...' one. The 'use x time to V' construction is used as a test for culmination/telicity. Verbs which encode telicity such as accomplishments (e.g., *bọ òwá* 'build a house') are interpreted as 'X completed V-ing in x time' whereas verbs which do not encode culmination are either incompatible with this construction (achievements) or have a 'X spent x time V-ing' interpretation (duratives).

Based on the results of the application of these tests, Edo verbs were split into two major classes – inchoatives and non-inchoatives. Inchoatives are predicates that encode a change-of-state + a result state. Non-inchoatives on the other hand do not possess this phasal structure. The inchoative class was further split into punctual and

durative inchoatives. Whereas the former encodes a punctual change-of-state leading to a result-state, the latter encodes a durative change-of-state leading to a result-state, The class of non-inchoatives was split into duratives (which encode durativity and atelicity), accomplishments (which encode dynamicity, durativity, and culmination) and achievements (which encode dynamicity, non-durativity, no result state, and no culmination).

This chapter answers one of two major research questions posed at the start of this dissertation, which is to determine the diagnostics required to classify verbs in the language and to identify the actional classes of verbs in the Edo language. With respect to unresolved issues, there were no tests to distinguish between pure states and inchoatives and so that distinction was not made since I only proposed classes for which I have evidence.

CHAPTER 6 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

6.1 Overview

This dissertation has explored the intricate relations that result from the interaction between grammatical aspect and lexical aspect in Edo. A classificatory schema based on this interaction as indicated by actional-phasal diagnostics was then proposed. This chapter concludes this study by presenting a summary of the chapters in the dissertation (section 6.2.1), presenting the findings of the dissertation (section 6.2.2), stating some challenges/limitations encountered in classifying Edo verbs based on their actional phases (section 6.3) and proposing some recommendations for future research (section 6.4).

6.2 Summary of chapters and main results

This section summarizes the goals and findings of each chapter (section 6.2.1) as well as the key findings of the study in relation to the research aims/questions outlined in chapter one (section 6.2.2)

6.2.1 Summary of Chapters

Chapter one served as the background of the study. There, I stated the research aims and objectives, the research questions for which the study set out to provide answers, the data and methods adopted to answer the research questions, a brief explanation of relevant studies and theories necessary to understand the analyses, the findings of the study and its significance.

Chapter 2 undertook a deep 'dive' into the literature with the goal of providing the relevant theoretical background and findings of previous studies that influence this research work. Key concepts of the study were defined, and topics such as tense,

aspect and actionality, the relationship between TA and actionality were broached. A brief survey of temporal marking in Niger-Congo was also present. As one of the aims of the study is the classification of verbs, the chapter discussed extensively the current dominant universalist (neo-) Vendlerian approaches to verb classification, highlighting some of their shortcomings and reasons why they are inadequate in capturing the nuances of aspect-actionality interactions in Èdo. The chapter also presented the bidimensional parametric approach to accounting for aspect-actionality interactions as advocated by researchers such as Botne and Kershner (2000) and Tatevosov (2002) and implemented in several Bantu languages.

Aspects of Èdo grammar relevant to understanding the data, discussion, analyses, and findings of the study were presented in Chapter 3 in the form of a sketch grammar. The chapter discussed the basic phonology of the language (including its sound system, phonological processes, and tone system), nominal morphology (the pronominal and number marking systems) and aspects of Èdo morphosyntax (word-order, serial verbs, verbal affixes, negation, and the stative verb vs adjective debate).

The diagnostics used in the actional classification of verbs in this study rely heavily on the TA system of the language because they are based on the interpretations which these TA markers receive in the context of different classes of verbs. Chapter 4 discussed the TA system of Èdo. The categories discussed include the factative (high-tone on the final syllable), the imperfective (low-tone on the final syllable), the prospective (*ghá*), the terminative (*fó...né*), the concessive (*té*), the completive marker (-rV suffix) and two phasal polarity markers (*nẹ* 'already' and *yèré* 'still'). The chapter also resolved previous disagreements on the markers of different TA categories in the

language. For example, the high tone on the final syllable of the verb previously analyzed as a past tense or perfective marker was reanalyzed as a factative marker, and *nẹ*, which was previously claimed to be a perfective marker, was reanalyzed as the phasal polarity marker 'already'. This chapter set the stage for discussing the diagnostics used in classifying verbs in Chapter 5.

The primary concern of Chapter 5 was the classification of verbs based on the actional phasal structure encoded in each verb. First, I showed how each of the TA markers and PhP items discussed in Chapter 4 are used as diagnostics to identify the phasal structure encoded in verbs. Consequently, I classified verbs into two broad classes (inchoatives and non-inchoatives) based on their phasal structure. Inchoatives are verbs which encode a change-of-state phase and a result-state phase. The class of inchoatives was further split into two sub-classes viz punctual inchoatives (which encode a non-durative change-of-state phase plus a result-state phase) and durative inchoatives (which encode a durative change-of-state phase plus a result-state phase). Non-inchoative verbs do not encode a change-of-state phase. They include duratives (further subclassified into activities and series), accomplishments and achievements.

6.2.2 Summary of Key Findings

In this section, I answer the research questions that this study set out to answer in Chapter 1 with the analyses and findings outlined in Chapters 4 and 5. The research questions are as follows.

(i) Research question 1: Is Edo a tense, aspect, or mood prominent language?

Edo is an aspect prominent language. As demonstrated in Chapter 4, the language has three aspectual markers (the factative, the imperfective and the prospective) and only one tense marker (the -rV suffix).

(ii) Research question 2: What are the temporal/aspectual markers in Edo and what temporal categories do they mark? There are three aspectual markers and one temporal marker in Edo. The aspectual markers are the high-tone on the final syllables of verbs which marks the factative, the low-tone on the final syllable of verbs which marks imperfective aspect and *ghá* which marks prospective aspect. *Nẹ* previously analyzed as an aspectual marker is reanalyzed as a PhP item which translates to 'already'.

(iii) Research question 3: What are the possible temporal interpretations when grammatical aspect interacts with lexical aspect in Edo? How can this system of interactions serve as a classification schema for verb senses in the language?

Actional diagnostics were designed using co-occurrence restrictions between verbs and TA markers (as well as two PhP items). The diagnostics also relied on the temporal interpretations resulting from this interaction. The possible interpretations that result when grammatical aspect interacts with actionality can be summed up as follows.

- (a) **Factative:** The factative marker has a present interpretation with inchoative verbs and a past interpretation with non-inchoative verbs.
- (b) **Imperfective:** The imperfective marker has an ongoing/habitual interpretation with activities and accomplishments, iterative reading with series and incompatible with inchoatives.
- (c) **Inceptive + prospective *suẹn ghà*:** With non-inchoative verbs, the inceptive +prospective has a 'started to V' interpretation, a started to become V interpretation with durative inchoatives, and is incompatible with punctual

inchoatives and achievements because they encode a non-durative nucleus phase.

- (d) **The Phasal polarity item *nẹ* ‘already’:** *nẹ* has a present result interpretation with inchoatives. When it co-occurs activities, accomplishments, and achievements, it has a ‘past event with current relevance’ interpretation. *Nẹ* on the other hand has an ‘ongoing but incomplete change’ interpretation with durative inchoatives, an ‘X is already V-ing’ reading with activities and accomplishments and is incompatible with achievements and punctual inchoatives.
- (e) **The terminative *fó nẹ*:** Accomplishment verbs have a ‘durative event that has culminated’ (i.e. X has finished V-ing) interpretation with the terminative, an exhaustive reading with quantized NP, a ‘peak of change-of-state’ reading with inchoatives, and a cessative interpretation with activities without quantized NPs.
- (f) **The persistentive *yèré*:** The PhP item *yèré* ‘still’ has ‘an event that began prior to speech time and continues through speech time’ (i.e., ‘X is still V-ing’) interpretation with activities and a ‘change-of-state in progress’ (i.e., ‘X is still becoming V’) reading with durative inchoatives. Accomplishments are ambiguous between a habitual and a professional reading (i.e., ‘X Vs regularly/as a profession’) while punctual inchoatives and achievements are incompatible with the persistentive.
- (g) **The prospective marker *ghá*:** Activities are ambiguous between a prospective and an ongoing interpretation. All other verbs have a prospective reading with *ghá*.

(h) **Té ‘almost’**: *té*, which literally means ‘almost’, has different interpretations with different verbs, hence it is actional sensitive. Achievements and punctual inchoatives have an ‘event that was about to happen but did not’ (‘X almost V-ed’). Durative inchoatives, activities, series and accomplishments have an ‘event that took place but not consistent with expectations’ (i.e., ‘X V-ed but...’) interpretation.

(i) **The completive -rV suffix**: the completive marker, like the factative, distinguishes inchoative verbs from non-inchoative verbs. Inchoative verbs have a present interpretation while non-inchoative verbs have a past interpretation.

(iv) What actionality primitives do Edo verbs encode? Actional primitives are phases which either solely or in combination with other phases constitute the phasal structure of verb classes. The actional primitives which Edo verbs encode and the classes which encode them are punctual change-of-state nucleus (punctual inchoatives), durative change-of-state nucleus (durative inchoatives), present result-state coda (inchoatives), punctual nucleus (achievements), durative nucleus (activities, accomplishments), iterative durative nucleus (series) and a non-stative coda (accomplishments).

(v) How can the actional properties of Edo verbs be utilized in classifying verbs in the language? Verbs are classified in this study based on the phasal structure encoded in predicates as identified by the diagnostics in (iii) above. This is not an a priori operation as verbs can only be categorized based on their individual interaction with the aspect-actionality diagnostics earlier identified. Specifically, the classification is based on one or more primitives identified in (iv) above encoded in the verb. Punctual

inchoatives encode a punctual change-of-state + a result state, durative inchoatives encode a durative change-of-state + a result state, accomplishments encode a durative nucleus + a (non-stative) coda, activities encode a durative nucleus, series encode an iterative durative nucleus, and achievements encode a punctual nucleus. The actional primitives (or a combination of these) is therefore the basis on which verbs are classified.

(vi) What are the grammatical implications of this classification schema for the language? The classification schema adopted in this study, which is based on the parametric, bi-dimensional approach to verb classification is useful for accounting for the TA system of Edo as it does not only explain why certain verbs encode certain interpretations with the TA markers in the language but also explains the source of disagreement on the meanings of TA markers in Edo. For example, the factative was previously proposed to be a past tense marker or a perfective marker based on its interpretation with non-inchoative verbs. However, when inchoative verbs are considered, the marker has a different albeit opposite meaning (present). This is atypical of past/perfective markers as they do not yield present interpretations in any context. This served as an indication that this was not a past or perfective marker but the factative. Aspect-actionality interactions thus serve to disambiguate the meanings encoded in TA markers as it reveals the actional phasal structure of verbs.

6.3 Contributions of the Study

The following are the main contributions of this study.

(a) The resolution of disagreements in the TA marking system of Edo language.

The previous state of affairs in the TA marking system of the language was such that there were multiple proposals as to the specific meaning of TA

markers. This led to a situation where several meanings were attributed to the same TA marker by several authors. This study presented the perspectives of the different authors and specified the semantics each TA marker in the language taking into account all classes of verbs and using contextual cues to specify the temporal contexts that license each TA marker. The result of this is a clear-cut, specified presentation of the TA system.

- (b) The design of diagnostics that specify the actional phasal structure of verbs: since this study advocates for a parametric bi-dimensional approach to the classification of Edo verbs, diagnostics to identify the actional primitives and phasal structure of verbs were designed to avoid the pitfalls of the apriorist universalist approach to actional classification. These diagnostics consist of compatibility or otherwise of verbs with Edo TA markers (such as the factative, imperfective, prospective, completive marker), phasal markers (such as the inceptive, concessive and terminative), and phasal polarity items (such as 'already', and the persistive 'still'). Although these diagnostics, are designed for application in Edo, they could serve as a cue on the type of TA particles that are actional sensitive and hence relevant as diagnostics for classifying verbs in other languages.
- (c) Proposal of verb classification relevant to Edo grammar: the result of applying the aforementioned diagnostics is a verb classification schema that is based on aspect-actionality interactions, and such a classification is relevant to some other aspects of the grammar. For example, the classification schema proposed is useful in explaining the 'behavior' of verbs with different TA

markers in the language as this is attributed to the difference in the phasal structure encoded in verbs and the actional properties which TA markers and other diagnostics can 'highlight'.

The classification schema is also relevant in explaining the morpho-semantics of the Edo -lv suffix. In chapter 3, it was pointed out that the -lv suffix which marks pluractionality is actional sensitive because it is incompatible with [-atelic] verbs. Based on the verb classification proposed in this study, it can be concluded that only achievements and accomplishments license the pluractional marker; inchoatives, activities and series are incompatible with the -lv suffix. In addition, the iterative interpretation is associated with achievements whereas the plural argument interpretation is associated with accomplishments. The classification schema not only explains the (in)compatibility of the suffix with verbs in the language, but also the different interpretations attributed to verbs that license it.

6.4. Limitations of the study and recommendations for future research

This section briefly discusses so shortcomings of the study in terms of data sampling/collection and the scope of study (section 6.4.1). In section 6.4.1, I present some suggestions to address some of the limitations of the study on one hand and possible future research areas.

6.4.1 Limitations of the study

The analysis done in this study is based on 50 verbs and not all the verbs in the language. Although special care was taken to select a representative sample, this represents only a small fraction of the verbs in the language. However, considering the time constraints within which this study was conducted, a small representative sample

of verbs needed to be collected with the aim of extending the results to the verb system of the Edo language. Secondly, although the study collected and utilized conversational data, they were limited to conversations over zoom calls as I was unable to travel to Nigeria for data collection.

The scope of this study is limited to aspect-actionality interactions in basic affirmative clauses in Edo. It does not cover all the possible grammatical constructions such as embedded clauses, serial verb constructions, and questions. This does not, however, diminish the value of the study as it covers its intended scope and purpose as stated in the introduction.

6.4.2 Recommendations for future research

In order to address the limitations of this study, I suggest the following actions.

- (i) Analyze aspect-actionality interactions with a different and more robust sample of verbs.
- (ii) Investigate aspect-actionality interactions in constructions other than affirmative basic clauses such as serial verb constructions, embedded clauses, negative constructions, and questions.

In addition to the above recommendations to address the limitations of this study, I suggest the following actions to build on the findings and analyses of this study.

- (iii) Compare and contrast aspect-actionality interactions in Edo as presented in this study with other Edoic languages such as Esan, Emai and Urhobo with the aim of identifying similarities and differences in actional primitives, phasal structure and verb classes. The TA systems of these Edoic languages should also be reexamined to identify and rectify any disagreements that stem from verbs having varied interpretations in the

context of TA markers. In addition, the aspect-actionality system of Edo which encodes a factative-imperfective division can be compared to other Niger-Congo Bantu languages which lack the factative.

APPENDIX A

VERB LIST

D. Inchoatives	P.Inchoatives	Activities	Series	Achievements	Accomplishments
<i>Fàfá</i> 'fade' <i>Bígò</i> 'bend' <i>Rànrán</i> 'melt' <i>Kèkè</i> 'rot' <i>Kàkà</i> 'dry' <i>Gbín</i> 'blunt' <i>Khuó</i> 'slippery'	<i>Wú</i> 'die' <i>Tótà</i> 'sit' <i>Rẹn</i> 'know' <i>Kpòlò</i> 'fat' <i>Dín</i> 'brave' <i>Yó</i> 'high' <i>Nwiẹn</i> 'rumped' <i>Ghòghó</i> 'happy'	<i>Kú</i> 'play' <i>Rrì èvbàré</i> 'eat' <i>Gbìnná</i> 'fight' <i>Giẹ</i> 'laugh' <i>Khuẹ</i> 'swim' <i>Khian</i> 'walk' <i>Viẹ</i> 'cry' <i>Gbẹn</i> 'write' <i>Sò ihuán</i> 'sing' <i>Rhùlẹ</i> 'run'	<i>Sàán</i> 'jump' <i>Tòlọ òhuẹn</i> 'cough' <i>Kpè òbó</i> 'clap' <i>Luẹ</i> 'chew' <i>Bùún áró</i> 'blink' <i>Fí</i> 'throw' <i>Fí ósísí</i> 'shoot' <i>Gbè úbí</i> 'slap'	Buun 'break' Beghe 'see/sight' Se 'arrive' Dé 'fall'	<i>Mò ètó</i> 'weave hair' <i>Dòyọ èrhẹn</i> 'extinguish fire' <i>Yọ ẹwù</i> 'Put on shirt' <i>Bọ òwá</i> 'build house' <i>Sé</i> 'sew' <i>Má</i> 'mould' <i>Biẹ ọmọ</i> 'give birth' <i>Vú</i> 'uproot' <i>Fiẹnwẹn</i> 'wean'

APPENDIX B
DIAGNOSTICS

	<u>D.Inchoative</u>	<u>P.Inchoative</u>	<u>Activities</u>	<u>Series</u>	<u>Achievements</u>	<u>Accomplishments</u>
<u>Factative</u>	Present result state	Present result state	Past	Past	Past	Past
<u>Imperfective</u>	*	*	Ongoing	Iterative	*	Ongoing
<u>Incept + Prosp</u>	Inceptive change-of-state	*	Inceptive event	Inceptive event	Inceptive event	Inceptive event
<u>Nè 'already'</u>	Ongoing change-of-state + 'already'	*	Ongoing + 'already'	Ongoing + 'already'	*	Ongoing 'already'
<u>Nè 'already'</u>	Ongoing result-state + 'already'	Present result state + 'already'	Past event + 'already'	Past event + 'already'	Past event + 'already'	Past event + 'already'
<u>Terminative</u>	#	#	#	#	#	'Finished' V- <u>ing</u>
<u>Fo + ne</u>	'Peak' Present-state	*/completely V	Cessative (with QNPs)	Finished V- <u>ing</u> "already"	Finished V- <u>ing</u> already	'Finished' V- <u>ing</u> + 'already'
<u>Persistent</u>	Persistent change-of-state	*	Ongoing persistent	Ongoing persistent	*	Ongoing persistent/habitual (professional)
<u>Prospective</u>	Prospective	Prospective	Prospective/Ongoing	Prospective	Prospective	Prospective
<u>te</u>	X almost V-ed	X 'almost' V-ed	X V-ed ...but	X V-ed ...but	X V-ed ...but/X desired to	X V-ed ...but
<u>Past tense</u>	Past result state	Past result state	Past event	Past event	Past event	Past event
<u>Yá 'use' X to V</u>	X took Y time to V	*	Engaged in V for X time	Engaged in V for X time	*	Used X time to complete V

LIST OF REFERENCES

- Abdoulaye, Mahamane Laoualy. 1992. *Aspects of Hausa morphosyntax in role and reference grammar*. State Univ. of New York Buffalo dissertation. Retrieved from https://pure.mpg.de/rest/items/item_408161/component/file_408160/content
- Agbo, Maduabuchi Sennen. 2013. *A role and reference grammar analysis of the Igbo verb*. University of Ibadan, Nigeria. dissertation. Retrieved from <http://140.105.46.132:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/214>
- Agheyisi, Rebecca N. 1986a. *An Edo-English Dictionary*. Ethiope publishing corporation.
- Agheyisi, Rebecca N. 1986b. *An Edo-English Dictionary. Benin City: Ethiope Publishing Corporation* 39.
- Agheyisi, Rebecca N. 1990. *A grammar of Edo. Unpublished Ms., UNESCO*.
- Aikhionbare, Osayaba Matt. 1986. *Aspects of the verb phrase in Edo*.
- Ameka, Felix K. 2006. Ewe serial verb constructions in their grammatical context. *Serial Verb Constructions: A Cross-Linguistic Typology* 124–143.
- Arkadiev, Peter M. 2009. Lexical and compositional factors in the aspectual system of Adyghe. *Cross-Linguistic Semantics of Tense, Aspect, and Modality* 55–82.
- Arkadiev, Peter M. 2011. Aspect and actionality in Lithuanian on a typological background. *Langues Baltiques, Langues Slaves* 57–86.
- Bar-El, Leora. 2015. Documenting and classifying aspectual classes across languages. *Methodologies in Semantic Fieldwork* 75–109.
- Bertinetto, Pier Marco. 1997. *Il dominio tempo-aspettuale*. Rosenberg e Sellier.
- Bickel, Balthasar. 1997. Aspectual scope and the difference between logical and semantic representation. *Lingua* 102(2–3). 115–131.
- Bickel, Balthasar. 2000. Unlogischer Aspekt: Zur Bedeutungsstruktur von Aspekt und Aktionsart, besonders im Belharischen. *Probleme Der Interaktion von Lexik Und Aspekt (ILA)* 1–20.
- Binnick, Robert I. 1991. *Time and the verb: A guide to tense and aspect*. Oxford University Press. Retrieved from [https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=A1fSUowGY8kC&oi=fnd&pg=PR17&dq=Binnick,+Robert+\(1991\).+Time+and+the+Verb.+A+Guide+to+Tense+and+Aspect.+Oxford+University+Press.+New+York.&ots=pBmb0gZxrb&sig=MrM3ORyyXotTgkmlY6mFsBwp_QI](https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=A1fSUowGY8kC&oi=fnd&pg=PR17&dq=Binnick,+Robert+(1991).+Time+and+the+Verb.+A+Guide+to+Tense+and+Aspect.+Oxford+University+Press.+New+York.&ots=pBmb0gZxrb&sig=MrM3ORyyXotTgkmlY6mFsBwp_QI)

- Bohnenmeyer, Jürgen. 1998. Temporal reference from a radical pragmatics perspective: Why Yucatec does not need to express 'after' and 'before'. *Cogl* 9(3). 239–282. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/cogl.1998.9.3.239>
- Bohnenmeyer, Jürgen & Swift, Mary. 2004. Event Realization and Default Aspect. *Linguistics and Philosophy* 27(3). 263–296. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:LING.0000023371.15460.43>
- Boogaart, R.J.U. 2004. Aspect and Aktionsart. In J. Mugdan G. Booij & null C. Lehmann (eds.), *Morphology: An international Handbook on inflection and word formation*, 1165–1180. Berlin/New York: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Botne, Robert. 2003a. To die across languages: Toward a typology of achievement verbs. *Linguistic Typology* 7(2). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/lity.2003.016>
- Botne, Robert. 2003b. To die across languages: Toward a typology of achievement verbs. *Linguistic Typology* 7(2). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/lity.2003.016>
- Botne, Robert. 2008. *A Grammatical Sketch of of Cindali (Malawian Variety)*. American Philos. Soc.
- Botne, Robert & Kershner, Tiffany L. 2000. Time, tense and the perfect in Zulu.
- Botne, Robert & Kershner, Tiffany L. 2008. Tense and cognitive space: On the organization of tense/aspect systems in Bantu languages and beyond. *Cognitive Linguistics* 19(2). 145–218. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/COG.2008.008>
- Botne, Robert Dale Olson. 2010. Perfectives and perfects and pasts, oh my!: On the semantics of-ILE in Bantu. *Africana Linguistica* 16(1). 31–64.
- Breu, Walter. 1980. *Semantische Untersuchungen zum Verbalaspekt im Russischen*. Peter Lang International Academic Publishers.
- Breu, Walter. 1984. Zur Rolle der Lexik in der Aspektologie. *Welt Der Slaven* 29(1). 123–148.
- Breu, Walter. 1985. Handlungsgrenzen als Grundlage der Verbklassifikation. *Slavistische Linguistik* 9–34.
- Breu, Walter. 1994. Interactions between lexical, temporal and aspectual meanings. *Studies in Language. International Journal Sponsored by the Foundation "Foundations of Language"* 18(1). 23–44.
- Bybee, Joan L. & Perkins, Revere Dale & Pagliuca, William. 1994. *The evolution of grammar: Tense, aspect, and modality in the languages of the world* Vol. 196. University of Chicago Press Chicago. Retrieved from <http://jlc.jst.go.jp/DN/JST.JSTAGE/mea1984/1997.122?from=Google>

Carlson, Gregory Norman. 1977. *Reference to kinds in English*. University of Massachusetts Amherst. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/openview/8ae7fcc21ee148510d4820616d8ad4b1/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>

Chelliah, Shobhana L. & De Reuse, Willem J. 2010. *Handbook of descriptive linguistic fieldwork*. Springer Science & Business Media. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=d1FfE30hZ7EC&oi=fnd&pg=PR3&dq=Chelliah,+Shobhana+Lakshmi+%26+Willem+Joseph+de+Reuse.+2011.+Handbook+of+descriptive+linguistic+fieldwork.+Dordrecht:+Springer.&ots=kEbw0wuVCH&sig=En3VlaFUNJn7Oqr-pbUa695V7Lc>

Chelliah, Shobhana L. & De Reuse, Willem J. 2011. *Handbook of Descriptive Linguistic Fieldwork*. Dordrecht: Springer.

Christaller, Johann Gottlieb. 1875. *A grammar of the Asante and Fante language called Tshi [Chwee, Twi]*. Рипол Классик. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=MugLAWAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA23&dq=christaller+1875&ots=14L4dBsBQD&sig=kKT-1PNhkVwybyqvJe2XKiMIBAI>

Comrie, Bernard. 1976. *Aspect: An introduction to the study of verbal aspect and related problems* Vol. 2. Cambridge university press. Retrieved from [https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=Z4FM00GAwIUC&oi=fnd&pg=PP9&dq=Comrie,+Bernard+\(1976\).+Aspect.+In+Introduction+to+the+study+of+Verbal+Aspect+and+Related+Problem.+Cambridge+University+Press,+Cambridge.&ots=9xvEBNbcKa&sig=FsUmhYODRyiY2gWEedLQ2lqMOTjl](https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=Z4FM00GAwIUC&oi=fnd&pg=PP9&dq=Comrie,+Bernard+(1976).+Aspect.+In+Introduction+to+the+study+of+Verbal+Aspect+and+Related+Problem.+Cambridge+University+Press,+Cambridge.&ots=9xvEBNbcKa&sig=FsUmhYODRyiY2gWEedLQ2lqMOTjl)

Comrie, Bernard. 1985. *Tense* Vol. 17. Cambridge university press. Retrieved from [https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=KmFMW40zyFcC&oi=fnd&pg=PR7&dq=Comrie,+Bernard+\(1985\).+Tense.+Cambridge+University+Press,+Cambridge.&ots=VlrrGILKUi&sig=a_NBVI5TkLNcRqUJCpqiXvnUpU](https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=KmFMW40zyFcC&oi=fnd&pg=PR7&dq=Comrie,+Bernard+(1985).+Tense.+Cambridge+University+Press,+Cambridge.&ots=VlrrGILKUi&sig=a_NBVI5TkLNcRqUJCpqiXvnUpU)

Cover, Rebecca Tamar. 2015. Semantic fieldwork on TAM. *Methodologies in Semantic Fieldwork* 233–268.

Crane, Thera Marie. 2011. *Beyond time: Temporal and extra-temporal functions of tense and aspect marking in Totela, a Bantu language of Zambia*. UC Berkeley dissertation. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/openview/7b8ac57757a69d780282c5c80077a520/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750>

Crane, Thera Marie & Fleisch, Axel. 2016. Event type lexicalization across language boundaries: Verbs in South African Ndebele varieties. Presented at the 6th International Conference on Bantu Languages.

Crane, Thera Marie & Fleisch, Axel Gustav. 2019. Towards a fieldwork methodology for eliciting distinctions in lexical aspect in Bantu. *Linguistic Diversity Research among Speakers of isiNdebele and Sindebele in South Africa*.

Crane, Thera Marie & Persohn, Bastian. 2019. What's in a Bantu verb? Actionality in Bantu languages. *Linguistic Typology* 23(2). 303–345.

Croft, William. 2012. *Verbs: Aspect and causal structure*. OUP Oxford. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=CktoAgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Croft,+William.+2012.+Verbs.+Aspect+and+causal+structure.+Oxford:+Oxford+University+Press.&ots=mj6o2T077R&sig=YdVSK451x-0f3oR2G1PFq1x-mEo>

Dahl, Östen. 1985. Tense and aspect systems. Retrieved from https://pure.mpg.de/pubman/faces/ViewItemOverviewPage.jsp?itemId=item_407957

De Swart, Henriëtte. 1998. [No title found]. *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory* 16(2). 347–385. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1005916004600>

Dunn, Ernest. 1968. An introduction to Bini. *African Monograph* 9.

Dunn, Ernest F. & Agheyisi, Rebecca N. 1968. *An introduction to Bini*. African Studies Center, Michigan State University.

Ebert, Karen. 1995. Ambiguous perfect-progressive forms across languages. *Temporal Reference, Aspect and Actionality* 2. 185–203.

Emovon, Aimuamwosa. 1980. An Introductory Study of Tense and Aspect in Edo (Bini). Presented at the A paper Presented at the 14th Congress of West African Linguistics Conference at Cotonou, Republic of Benin. 14th-18th April.

Essegbey, James. 2003. Demystifying inherent complement verbs in Ewe. *Typologie Des Langues d'Afrique & Universaux de La Grammaire: Benue-Kwa, Wolof* 2. 97.

Evbuomwan, Osaigbovo & Usenbo, Perpetual. 2019. Acoustic Evidence for a Tonal Negative Marker in Èdo. *Journal of The Linguistic Association of Nigeria* 22(2). 97–112.

Faraclas, Nicholas & Rivera-Castillo, Yolanda & Walicek, Don E. 2007. 12. No exception to the rule: The tense-aspect-modality system of Papiamentu reconsidered. In *Synchronic and diachronic perspectives on contact languages*, 257–278. John Benjamins. Retrieved from <https://www.jbe-platform.com/content/books/9789027292018-cll.32.16far>

Faraclas, Nicholas G. 1984. *Obolo Grammar*. Bloomington: Indiana University Linguistics Club.

Filip, Hana. 2011. Aspectual Classes and Aktionsart. In Klaus von Heusinger & Claudia Maienborn & Paul Portner (eds.), *Semantics. An International Handbook of Natural Language Meaning*, Vol. 2, 1186–1216. Berlin: de Gruyter.

Filip, Hana. 2012. Lexical aspect. Retrieved from <https://academic.oup.com/edited-volume/38635/chapter/335334896>

- Freed, A.F. 1979. *The Semantics of English Aspectual Complementation*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Garey, Howard B. 1957. Verbal aspect in French. *Language* 33(2). 91–110.
- Goedsche, C.R. 1940. Aspect versus Aktionsart. *The Journal of English and Germanic Philology* 39(2). 189–196.
- Gruber, Jeff S. 1992. Proper argument projection in Igbo and Yoruba. *MIT Working Papers in Linguistics* 17. 139–165.
- Gruber, Jeffrey. 1992. Thematic configurational constraints in serial verb constructions. *ACAL, Michigan*.
- Gunnink, Hilde. 2018. *A grammar of Fwe: A Bantu language of Zambia and Namibia*. Ghent University dissertation. Retrieved from <https://biblio.ugent.be/publication/8553074>
- Hellwig, Birgit. 2011. *A grammar of Goemai* Vol. 51. Walter de Gruyter. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=scHHvM8QKhUC&oi=fnd&pg=PR5&dq=Hellwig,+Birgit.+2011.+A+grammar+of+Goemai.+Berlin:+De+Gruyter.&ots=7I6oaySOaR&sig=Y6YImkYqKLS198cyvcWCUqulShY>
- Hockett, Charles F. & Hockett, Charles D. 1960. The Origin of Speech. *Scientific American* 203(3). 88–97.
- Idiatov, Dmitry. 2000. Le sémantisme des marqueurs aspecto-temporels du bambara: une tentative d'analyse. *Mandenkan* 36. 1–59.
- Iyamu, Raphael Osarensese. 2016. *The Aktionsart and Morphosemantics of Edo Verbs*. University of Benin, Nigeria. dissertation. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/download/50472327/Thesis_Complete.pdf
- Jeschull, Liane. 2007. The pragmatics of telicity and what children make of it. In *Proceedings of the 2nd conference on generative approaches to language acquisition north america*, 180–187. Citeseer. Retrieved from <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=4dbe5a47ca6d3eb1ea6c269265d31163c00142e9>
- Johanson, Lars. 1971. Aspekt im Türkischen: Vorstudien zu einer Beschreibung des türkeitürkischen Aspektsystems.
- Johanson, Lars. 1996. Terminality operators and their hierarchical status. *Functional Grammar Series* 229–258.
- Johanson, Lars. 2000a. Linguistic convergence in the Volga area. In *Languages in contact*, 165–178. Brill.

- Johanson, Lars. 2000b. Viewpoint operators in European languages. *Empirical Approaches to Language Typology* (6). 27–188.
- Kanijo, Ponsiano Sawaka. 2019. Aspectual classes of verbs in Nyamwezi.
- Kari, Ethelbert E. 2002. Distinguishing between clitics and words in Degema, Nigeria. *African Study Monographs* 23(4). 177–192.
- Kershner, Tiffany Lynne. 2002. *The verb in Chisukwa: Aspect, tense, and time*. Indiana University. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/openview/0d5c367676dc4fad6bb97f740b1b8070/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
- Klein, Wolfgang. 2013. *Time in Language*. London: Routledge. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315003801>
- Kramer, Raija. 2021. *The expression of phasal polarity in African languages* Vol. 63. Walter de Gruyter GmbH & Co KG. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=IzcYEAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PT12&dq=crane+and+fleisch+actionality&ots=iC5aTbnIIA&sig=tPqIzS9TQ57EZJUBKDwyBzo75mE>
- Krifka, Manfred. 1992. Thematic Relations as Links between Nominal Reference and Temporal Constitution/Manfred Krifka. *Lexical Matters* (24). 29.
- Levin, Beth. 1993. *English verb classes and alternations: A preliminary investigation*. University of Chicago press. Retrieved from https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=6wIzWOrCBf8C&oi=fnd&pg=PA25&dq=Levin,+B.:+1993,+English+Verb+Classes+and+Alternation,+A+Preliminary+Investigation,+The+University+of+Chicago+Press.&ots=TD1CNVIX_O&sig=pJ8AljO--hbspYXvNclA7niFRaw
- Löbner, Sebastian. 1989. German ‘Schon - Erst - Noch’: An Integrated Analysis. *Linguistics and Philosophy* 12(2). 167–212.
- Lusekelo, Amani. 2016. Lexical semantics and selection of TAM in Bantu languages: A case of semantic classification of Kiswahili verbs. *International Journal of Society, Culture & Language* 4(1 (Special Issue on African Cultures and Languages)). 89–102.
- Lyons, John. 1977. *Semantics: Volume 1*. Cambridge University Press.
- Malchukov, Andrej. 2009. Incompatible categories 13–32. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1075/la.148.02mal>
- Marchese, Lynell. 1986. Tense/aspect and the development of auxiliaries in Kru languages. Retrieved from https://pure.mpg.de/pubman/faces/ViewItemOverviewPage.jsp?itemId=item_407757

- Moens, Marc & Steedman, Mark. 2005. Temporal ontology and temporal reference. Retrieved from [https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=cw9REAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA93&dq=Moens,+Marc+%26+Mark+Steedman.+1988.+Temporal+ontology+and+temporal+reference.+Computational+Linguistics+14\(2\).+15%E2%80%9328.&ots=1VBDjelQoU&sig=cras5kL9RITw_PRtsZqI2niC-lw](https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=cw9REAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA93&dq=Moens,+Marc+%26+Mark+Steedman.+1988.+Temporal+ontology+and+temporal+reference.+Computational+Linguistics+14(2).+15%E2%80%9328.&ots=1VBDjelQoU&sig=cras5kL9RITw_PRtsZqI2niC-lw)
- Mourelatos, Alexander P.D. 1978. Events, processes, and states. *Linguistics and Philosophy* 2(3). 415–434. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00149015>
- Nichols, Johanna. 2010. Indeterminate motion verbs are denominal. *New Approaches to Slavic Verbs of Motion* 47–65.
- Nurse, Derek. 2008. *Tense and aspect in Bantu*. Oxford University Press, USA. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=lqIUDAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR5&dq=derek+nurse+2008&ots=50xPjKWsSu&sig=dDIFKbyomovhJ7bHZxtGbXGjL38>
- Nurse, Derek & Rose, Sarah & Hewson, John. 2016. *Tense and aspect in Niger-Congo*. MRAC Musée royal de l’Afrique centrale.
- Ogie, Ota. 2003. About Multi-verb Constructions, Past Tense Suffixation and Syntactic Representation in Edo. In *Proceedings of the workshop on Multi-verb Constructions...*, Trondheim Summer School.
- Olsen, Mari Broman. 1994. The semantics and pragmatics of lexical aspect features. *Studies in the Linguistic Sciences*. Retrieved from <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=ccbfa8260d71adea7f71ec6009dcd556741be3>
- Omogbe, Esohe Mercy. 2012. *The Edo Basic Clause: A Morpho-Syntactic Analysis*. Benin, Nigeria.: University of Benin dissertation.
- Omogbe, M. & Aigbedo, William. 2012. Agreement patterns within the Edo NP. *European Scientific Journal* 8(5). 130–147.
- Omogbe, Osareh SB. 1983. *Edo grammar for schools and colleges*. T. Nelson (Nigeria) Limited.
- Omoruyi, Thomas. 1991a. Tense, aspect, and modality in Edo. *Afrika Und Ubersee* 74. 1–19.
- Omoruyi, Thomas. 1991b. Tense, aspect, and modality in Edo. *Afrika Und Ubersee* 74. 1–19.
- Omoruyi, Thomas O. 1986. Adjectives and adjectivalization processes in Edo. *Studies in African Linguistics* 17(3). 283–302.

Omozuwa, Victor E. 2010. *Edo Phonetics and Phonology*. Benin City: Ambik Press.
Retrieved from
<https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=1472685822627866332&hl=en&oi=scholar>

Omozuwa, Victor Edosa. 1993. Vowel Elision, "Floating" Tone, and Downstep in Edo. *アジア・アフリカ言語文化研究= Journal of Asian and African Studies/東京外国語大学アジア・アフリカ言語文化研究所 編* (45). p17-30.

Omozuwa, VICTOR EDOSA. 2003. Tones in Edo verbs: An experimental overview. *Kiabara: Journal of Humanities* 9(1). 57–65.

Oskolskaya, Sofia A. 2017. Aspekt v nanajskom jezyke [Aspect in Nanai]. *Saint-Petersburg: Institute for Linguistic Studies, Russian Academy of Sciences Doctoral Dissertation*.

Persohn, Bastian. 2017a. *The Verb In Nyakyusa: A Focus On Tense, Aspect And Modality*. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.926408>

Persohn, Bastian. 2017b. *The verb in Nyakyusa: A focus on tense, aspect, and modality*. Language Science Press.

Persohn, Bastian. 2018. Aspectuality in Bantu: on the limits of Vendler's categories. *Linguistic Discovery* 16(2). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1349/PS1.1537-0852.A.479>

Persohn, Bastian. 2019. Aspectuality in Bantu: On the limits of Vendler's categories. *Linguistic Discovery* 16(2).

Plungjan, Vladimir A. 2011. *Vvedenie v grammatičeskiju semantiku: grammatičeskie značenija i grammatičeskie sistemy jazykov mira; učebnoe posobie*. Rossijskij Gosudarstvennyj Gumanitarnyj Univ.

Polančec, Jurica. 2020. *A typology of aspect-actionality interactions*. University of Zadar dissertation. Retrieved from <https://repozitorij.unizd.hr/islandora/object/unizd:4966>

Rose, Sarah & Beaudoin-Lietz, Christa A.M. & Nurse, Derek. 2002. *A glossary of terms for Bantu verbal categories : with special emphasis on tense and aspect*. Lincom Europa. Retrieved from <https://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA67476871>

Rosen, Sara Thomas. 1999. The syntactic representation of linguistic events. *Glott International* 4(2). 3–11.

Rothstein, Susan. 2004. Derived accomplishments and lexical aspect. Retrieved from https://direct.mit.edu/books/edited-volume/chapter-pdf/2291729/9780262274494_cat.pdf

Rothstein, Susan. 2008. Telicity, atomicity and the Vendler classification of verbs. *Theoretical and Crosslinguistic Approaches to the Semantics of Aspect* 43–78.

Sasse, Hans-Jürgen. 2002a. Recent activity in the theory of aspect: Accomplishments, achievements, or just non-progressive state? *Linguistic Typology* 6(2). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/lity.2002.007>

Sasse, Hans-Jürgen. 2002b. Recent activity in the theory of aspect: Accomplishments, achievements, or just non-progressive state? *Linguistic Typology* 6(2). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/lity.2002.007>

Savić, Stefan. 2021. Tense and aspect in Xhosa. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/59002574/TENSE_AND_ASPECT_IN_XHOSA

Seidel, Frank. 2008. The hodiernal past domain and the concept of recentness in Yeyi. *Africana Linguistica* 14(1). 151–176.

Smith, Carlota S. 2013. *The parameter of aspect* Vol. 43. Springer Science & Business Media.

Smollett, Rebecca. 2005. Quantized Direct Objects Don't Delimit After All: A revised account of the role of quantized direct objects in aspectual composition. In Henk J. Verkuyl & Henriette De Swart & Angeliek Van Hout (eds.), *Perspectives on Aspect*, Vol. 32, 41–59. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/1-4020-3232-3_3

Stewart, Osamuyimen Thompson. 1998. Evidence for the distinction between resultative and consequential serial verbs. In *Annual Meeting of the Berkeley Linguistics Society*, 232–243. Retrieved from <http://journals.linguisticsociety.org/proceedings/index.php/BLS/article/download/1224/1006>

Stewart, Osamuyimen Thompson. 2001. *The serial verb construction parameter*. Routledge. Retrieved from https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=pSDfAQAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=info:LDaVMnippEQJ:scholar.google.com&ots=dLBMqazFVx&sig=iNKRvJpl3QM2FHXXbhLgDltA_WY

Storch, Anne & Jungraithmayr, Herrmann & Cyffer, Norbert. 1999. *Das Hone und seine Stellung im Zentral-Jukunoid* Vol. 20. Köppe. Retrieved from <http://kups.ub.uni-koeln.de/id/eprint/36058>

Talmy, Leonard. 2000. *Toward a cognitive semantics: Concept structuring systems* Vol. 1. MIT press. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=DS4TDgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=talmy+2000&ots=1zRTQ84jPM&sig=YmR-skclSO1zyx0Y-7qStCYh4WA>

Talmy, Leonard. 2007. Lexical Typologies.–Timothy Shopen (Ed.), *Language Typology and Syntactic Description: Vol. III: Grammatical Categories and the Lexicon*. New York: Cambridge University Press.

- Tatevosov, Sergei. 2015. Severing imperfectivity from the verb. *Zybatow, Gerhild; Biskup, Petr; Guhl, Marcel; Hurtig, Claudia* 465–494.
- Tatevosov, Sergei. 2016. Structure and interpretation of Tundra Nenets verbs: Eventuality types and conjugation classes. *Voprosy Jazykoznanija* (3). 81–114. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31857/S0373658X0001008-7>
- Tatevosov, Sergej. 2002. The parameter of actionality.
- Tatevosov, Sergey. 2002. The parameter of actionality. *Linguistic Typology* 6(3). 317–401.
- Timberlake, Alan. 1985. The temporal schemata of Russian predicates. *Issues in Russian Morphosyntax* 35–57.
- Toews, Carmela Irene Penner. 2015. *Topics in Siamou tense and aspect*. University of British Columbia dissertation. Retrieved from <https://doi.library.ubc.ca/10.14288/1.0166224>
- Uchihara, Hiroto. 2010. Final paper: Pronominals in Edo—a descriptive study. *Field Methods II*. https://www.academia.edu/1341848/Final_Paper_Pronominals_in_Edo_A_descriptive_study.
- van Baar, T.M. 1997. Phasal Polarity. Retrieved from <https://dare.uva.nl/search?identifier=816c2f26-8583-4676-9ae6-97a00b2ba65c>
- Van Der Auwera, Johan. 1993. ‘Already’ and ‘Still’: Beyond Duality. *Linguistics and Philosophy* 16(6). 613–653.
- Van Valin Jr, Robert D. 2005. *Exploring the syntax-semantics interface*. Cambridge University Press. Retrieved from [https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=C_VpmlRdtZgC&oi=fnd&pg=PR9&dq=Van+Valin,+Jr.,+R.+D.+\(2005\).+Exploring+the+Syntax-Semantics+Interface.+Cambridge:+Cambridge+University+Press.+&ots=TmR3ci2RSK&sig=6lk69tcPoEBMORfaZZA8w-g6-1w](https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=C_VpmlRdtZgC&oi=fnd&pg=PR9&dq=Van+Valin,+Jr.,+R.+D.+(2005).+Exploring+the+Syntax-Semantics+Interface.+Cambridge:+Cambridge+University+Press.+&ots=TmR3ci2RSK&sig=6lk69tcPoEBMORfaZZA8w-g6-1w)
- Van Valin, Robert. 2006. Some universals of verb semantics. *Linguistic Universals* 155–178.
- Vandeweghe, Willy. 1992. Perspectivistische evaluatie in het Nederlands - de partikels avan de AL/NOG/PAS-groep by VANDEWEGHE Willy | Antiquariaat Pieter Judo (De Lezenaar). (<https://www.abebooks.com/Perspectivistische-evaluatie-het-Nederlands-partikels-avan/837484399/bd>) (Accessed 2024-3-9)
- Vendler, Zeno. 1957. Verbs and times. *The Philosophical Review* 66(2). 143–160.
- Von Stechow, Kai & Heim, Irene. 2011. Intensional semantics. *Unpublished Lecture Notes*. Retrieved from <http://lingphil.mit.edu/papers/heim/fintel-heim-intensional.pdf>

Von Stechow, Kai & Matthewson, Lisa. 2008. Universals in semantics. *The Linguistic*

Review 25(1–2). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/TLIR.2008.004>

Walková, Milada. 2012. The aspectual function of particles in phrasal verbs. Retrieved from <https://research.rug.nl/en/publications/the-aspectual-function-of-particles-in-phrasal-verbs>

Welmers, Wm E. 1973. *African language structures*. University of California Press. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=Q7nADwAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA46&dq=Welmers,+William+E.+1973.+African+language+structures.+Berkeley:+University+of+California+Press.&ots=kzFtkL0fX0&sig=ItLOppRBMJ-T-QyTze1dmrSI5v8>

Wilhelm, Andrea. 2003. *The grammaticization of telicity and durativity*. University of Calgary dissertation. Retrieved from <https://prism.ucalgary.ca/bitstreams/e8fa64d7-50b0-483c-983b-571e1bdb8147/download>

Williamson, Kay. 1991. The tense system of Izon. *Afrikanistische Arbeitspapiere* 27. 145–167.

Yuka, Lenzemo Constantine & Omoregbe, Esohe Mercy. 2008. Tense and Aspect in Edo. *Ihafa: A Journal of African Studies (Special Edition)* 6(4–6). 114–131.

Yuka, Lenzemo Constantine & Omoregbe, M. 2011a. Tense and Aspect in Edo: A Re-Appraisal. *Edo North: Field Studies of the Languages of the Northern Edo. Essays in Honour of Professor BO Elugbe*. Ibadan: Zentih Book House 569–811.

Yuka, Lenzemo Constantine & Omoregbe, M. 2011b. Tense and Aspect in Edo: A Re-Appraisal. *Edo North: Field Studies of the Languages of the Northern Edo. Essays in Honour of Professor BO Elugbe*. Ibadan: Zentih Book House 569–811.

Zucchi, Sandro. 1998. Aspect Shift. In Susan Rothstein (ed.), *Events and Grammar*, Vol. 70, 349–370. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-3969-4_15

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